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Deliverable 4.1

Report on the Practical Management of the Pilot Assemblies

v.1

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PMIMG Persons Belonging to Multiple Intersecting Marginalised Groups

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.1 explains how the EU-CIEMBLY translates theory into practice through concrete design choices for three citizens' assembly pilots at local, national, and transnational level. The deliverable documents the micro design phase of the project, meaning the detailed preparation phase for the three pilots. It builds on Deliverable 3.4, which reported the project's macro design / strategic phase, and complements Deliverable 4.2, which focuses specifically on facilitators' training. Together, these three deliverables trace the project's progression from conceptual design to practical implementation.

The present report explains how the project team has sought to embed intersectionality in citizens' assembly design through specific pilot interventions. As explained in Deliverable 3.4, each of the three pilots focuses on one main targeted intervention, while all three are shaped by a cross-cutting intervention on facilitation. Specifically, the local pilot in Colchester, UK, adopts a community co-design approach seeking to involve affected communities in shaping the assembly. The national pilot in Cyprus explores whether intersectionality considerations can be operationalised through recruitment and/or content choices that reflect and surface PMIMG experiences. The transnational pilot examines an enclave-style approach inspired by the "deeply affected" principle, seeking to create a deliberative space for those impacted by housing insecurity in Europe. Across all three pilots, facilitation is treated as an important site for operationalising intersectionality. As such, we have developed an intersectionality-informed facilitation approach built around three activators: valuing diverse communication modes, understanding how power operates in deliberative settings, and practising reflexivity. This deliverable explains the project team's specific decisions, actions, and activities for testing our intersectionality-oriented planned interventions.

The three pilot assemblies are staggered to allow us to draw lessons for subsequent assembly pilots. This means that there is inevitably less certainty about the design of the second two assemblies (the national and the transnational) than about the design of the first (the local). As such, the present report provides a detailed description of the practical management for the first project pilot assembly, which took place in Colchester, UK, between February and March 2026. Where the design choices for the subsequent assemblies diverge from those of the local assembly, the report notes and explains the rationale behind this deviation in the planning. In this way, the deliverable fulfils two objectives: it explains the design choices for the local pilot assembly and provides an overview of the practical design of all the pilots.

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I. Introduction

1. Purpose of the Deliverable

The present report follows from Deliverable 3.4, which had set out the project's overarching ideas and plans for the three pilots that will be tested by the project team in Work Package 4 at a local, national, and transnational level. The reporting of the design and the planning for the EU-CIEMBLY pilots is divided across three deliverables: Deliverables 3.4, 4.1, and 4.2. Deliverable 3.4 reported the EU-CIEMBLY's **macro-design phase**, i.e. the strategic decisions that we made as a team regarding **how to operationalise intersectionality** across the different levels of the pilot assemblies. As explained in that deliverable, our method for embedding intersectionality into the design of the pilots is guided by four considerations, namely: (1) the need to be explicit about our normative understanding of intersectionality (Deliverable 2.2 and ongoing); (2) the need to be mindful of our own positionality (addressed in Section III, below); (3) the need to adopt a context-based approach (addressed in Section IV below); and, (4) the need to choose (and design around) targeted interventions that can improve current practices (Sections V-VIII below, and ongoing). We have designed targeted interventions that are specific to each pilot and which were inspired by the theoretical models that were developed in earlier parts of our project (see Deliverable 2.3). We have also designed a cross-cutting intervention, which concerns the way in which facilitation will take place across the three pilots, given its particular importance to intersectionality considerations.¹

Based on the macro-design decisions that we made as a project team, we moved into a more detailed preparation phase along the input-throughput-output stages, that included several more specific decisions, actions, and activities. This **micro-design phase**, the decisions that we made as part of it, and the rationale behind those decisions, are documented in the present Deliverable 4.1. One part of the micro-design phase was to decide how facilitation, as one of our project's cross-cutting interventions, would take place in the pilots. As part of that, we developed a training programme for the pilots' facilitators, which is described in Deliverable 4.2. The present report, though, goes beyond facilitation. It seeks to document our design choices as well as the intersectionality-driven rationale behind them and the challenges and limitations that we have faced along the way. In particular, it seeks to explain how we, as a project team, have

¹ For a thorough discussion on the project's interventions see Deliverable 3.4.

thought about ways to explicitly inform all the phases characterising a citizens' assembly design through an intersectionality lens. This ranges from the values that we should assume relevant, to our own positionality and that of the participants, to how we can make our intersectional focus more concrete during the deliberation process, and to the stage of the recommendations. This report further explains how we have thought about power dynamics in the assembly through an intersectionality lens. We explain how we tried to challenge and provide more intersectionality-oriented alternatives to deliberation mechanisms that have become embedded in citizens' assembly practices over the years and are often taken for granted, from the duration of the sessions, to recruitment traditions, to ice-breaking and rule-definition within the assembly process.

The three pilot assemblies of the project are staggered to allow us to draw lessons for subsequent assembly pilots. As such, there is inevitably less certainty about the design of the second two assemblies (the national and the transnational) than about the design of the first (the local). In addition, some design features are the same or similar for all three pilots, while leaving the possibility for adaptations reflecting lessons learned from previous pilots.

For these reasons (i.e. a staggered approach to the pilot design, and to avoid repetition) the present report provides a detailed description of the practical management of the **first project pilot assembly**, which took place in Colchester, UK, between February and March 2026. Where the design choices for the subsequent assemblies diverge from those of the local assembly, the report notes and explains the rationale behind this deviation. In this way, this deliverable fulfils two objectives: it explains the design choices for the local pilot assembly and provides an overview of the practical design of all the pilots.

Before we proceed to explain the structure of the deliverable, it is worth mentioning that the design and the implementation of the intersectionality-oriented pilots of the project have been a collaborative effort of our team, which consists largely of academics and researchers, one NGO, a civic tech partner, and a communications partner. This collaboration is exemplified by the fact that this deliverable reflects the input of all involved teams:

- Carmela Barbera, Antonella Di Maso, Laura Mariani, Mariafrancesca Sicilia, and Vera Lomazzi (UniBG) developed the foundations of the project's approach to facilitation, as well as a tailored icebreaking activity for the project;

- Alice Leal (WITS) led the discussion on language;
- Hendrik Nahr, Maria Tazi, and Guillemette Colombe (MO) developed the EU-CIEMBLy Handbook for Intersectional Facilitation and the civic tech dimension of the project, and collaborated with the UE team on the agenda of the pilots;
- Giulia Sandri (ECAS) researched the online dimension of deliberative instruments and provided advice on the best use of online tools;
- Sarah Noles and Eric Jensen (IMI) have been working on the organisation of the transnational pilot and developed the project's evaluation plan;
- Dulce Lopes and Lucía Muñoz (UC) provided expert input on the topic of housing;
- Antonis Karatzias and Panayiota Yiorka (ASPON) have been working on the organisation of the Cyprus pilot and the communications plan for the pilots;
- with Anastasia Karatzia, Niall O'Connor, Rebecca Warren, Ileana Steccolini and Samantha Woodward (UE) coordinating the overall design and implementation of the pilots, organising the local pilot assembly, and leading Work Package 4.

Figure 1. The planning outputs for the EU-CIEMBLy pilots' design

2. Structure of the Deliverable

The report proceeds as follows. Section II reminds the reader of the intersectionality-informed methodology that we developed (see Deliverable 3.4, Section III), and the way in which we applied it in practice in the pilots' micro-design phase. In Section III of this report, we reflect further on our positionality and what that means for the research project and the design of the pilots. Sections IV - IX then focus on aspects of the pilots' design that are of particular relevance to the project: contextual analysis, recruitment, facilitation, language, online deliberation, and engaging with the broader public via civic tech platforms. They explain our team's attempts to embed intersectionality considerations into each of these 'segments' and the respective design choices. These sections provide the background and the objectives, from an intersectionality point of view, that have guided organisational micro-design choices for the pilots. The report focuses especially on the first of the three pilots, explaining where the design might diverge for the forthcoming two pilots. In turn, Section X provides an outline of the pilots' evaluation plans, and Section XI concludes.

It should be mentioned from the outset that the present deliverable does not include any evaluation of the design choices even though the local pilot will have been completed by the time the report is submitted. Instead, it focuses on describing the organisational aspects of the pilot Assemblies, thus providing a foundation for the evaluation that will come at the final stage of Work Package 4 (Deliverable 4.4).

II. EU-CIEMBLY in Practice: An Overview

This section explains how we have worked to translate the project's values, assumptions, methods, and innovations into concrete assembly events. The motivation behind the EU-CIEMBLY pilots is linked back to the project's overall objective, which is to make recommendations for embedding intersectionality considerations into (EU) citizens' assemblies. As mentioned in Deliverable 3.4, the pilots aim to provide **empirical evidence** on the effectiveness of attempts to embed intersectionality considerations in the design, implementation, and evaluation of citizens' assemblies as forums seeking to enhance citizens' public participation. In that same deliverable, we expounded **four key considerations** that have guided the process of turning our analytical and normative framework into practical application. We argued there that being explicit about the project's normative understanding of intersectionality (Key Consideration 1) ensures that we will keep power relations and structural marginalisation at the centre of our work. Sustaining attention to our positionality (Key Consideration 2) resists the assumption that the team holds a neutral standpoint dislocated from intersecting structures of privilege and oppression. Adopting a context-based approach (Key Consideration 3) insists that membership of a social group and of the intersection of social groups is understood alongside an understanding of institutional, historical, and social structures rather than as a matter solely of personal identities. Finally, we developed specific targeted interventions per pilot (Key Consideration 4) to guide the adoption of considered design choices at the input, throughput, and output stages.²

While Deliverable 3.4 explained **what** interventions we are planning to test and **why** we chose those particular interventions, the focus in the current Deliverable 4.1 is on explaining **how** we are designing the pilots to materialise these interventions. Although formally speaking the design phase started with Task 3.5 in late 2025, as a team we had already been discussing and designing since the Work Package 2 Workshop that took place in Madrid in November 2024, with our efforts intensifying as our research focus, methodology, and objectives of the pilots became clearer through team meetings, discussions with external actors, co-design sessions, training sessions tailored to our project, and through the findings of the research that has taken place in Work Package 3. Real world limitations and the need to remain iterative and adaptable,

² For a more detailed discussion on our methodology for incorporating intersectionality into the pilot citizens' assemblies see Deliverable 3.4 pp. 13-22.

as well as to gain lessons from one pilot that we can apply to the next one means that not all organisational details can be set out for all pilots at this stage.

An Overview of the Pilots' Design			
Level	Local pilot	National pilot	Transnational pilot
Targeted Intervention	Community co-design	Intersectionality-driven recruitment and/or content	Enclave deliberation inspired by the deeply affected principle
Cross-cutting intervention	Facilitation		
Intersectionality guiding design choices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intersectionality as an analytical framework based on power relations understood in the relevant context • Awareness of our own positionality 		

Figure 2. An overview of the pilots' design

Figure 2 presents an overview of the targeted interventions per pilot. The local pilot aims to adopt a bottom-up, **community-led approach** to citizens' assembly design, aiming to address systemic power imbalances. The national pilot aims to explore whether and how experimenting with the recruitment stage and the information-providing throughput stage of the assembly can provide a way of ensuring intersectionality-oriented internal and external inclusion. The transnational pilot aims to examine whether an **enclave-style assembly** can add the participation of PMIMG (persons belonging to multiplate intersectional marginalised groups) voices to the current EU landscape of citizens' participation. Our micro-design choices were also informed by our prior empirical work in Deliverable 3.3, where we identified a number of good practice recommendations, including on the evaluation of participatory practices.³ The discussion that follows in this report seeks to highlight, among other things, our design choices for the input-throughput-output stages of the pilots and how these were shaped by our previous work; a context-based approach; and a constant awareness of our positionality as a team.

³ For a summary, see Deliverable 3.3 pp. 147-149.

As shown in the above Figure 2, our design choices were guided by intersectionality in the sense that we adopted a **context-based approach** for understanding the power relations that affect and shape marginalisation in a given context, and we designed and used a suite of positionality tools that allow us to remain **aware of our own positionality**. **Sections III** and **IV** focus on these two aspects while **Section V** explains how they informed the pilot recruitment efforts.

In addition, the project envisages a **cross-cutting intervention** regarding the facilitation stage of an assembly, which we have identified as particularly amenable to the operationalisation of theoretical considerations of intersectionality. Seeing facilitation both as an avenue for implementing such considerations in the actual assembly process, and as an operational tool for achieving intersectionality-oriented deliberation, Deliverable 3.4 put forward three '**activators of intersectionality-informed facilitation**'. The first activator is about valuing diverse communication methods: allowing space in the discussions for a relational dimension that reflects the diversity of experiences in the room. The second activator is about understanding how power operates in deliberative settings. This relates to the facilitators' task of identifying and mitigating power dynamics that may operate as barriers to participation. The third activator is about practising reflexivity: being aware of one's own individual positionality (i.e., thinking reflectively), and taking an external view of that positionality (i.e., thinking reflexively). We have attempted to turn these activators into practice during the pilot micro-design phase; this is documented in **Section VI** below.

As we have explained in the previous deliverable, all our planned interventions derive from our understanding of intersectionality as documented in Deliverable 2.2 (version 2). These interventions have been designed with intersectionality in mind, even though we may not be able to implement all possible design choices that could cater to intersectional equality, inclusion, and deliberation. Beyond our explicit focus on intersectionality-oriented facilitation across the three pilots, there are three other areas that cut across all the pilots and for which we have had to make micro-design choices: language, online deliberation, and online engagement with the broader public via civic tech platforms. Our design choices for each of these elements, and the rationale behind them, can be found in **Sections VII, VIII, and IX**.

Finally, the micro-design phase of our pilots took place at the same time as the design of the evaluation stage of the project. The team worked together in compiling an evaluation

methodology that responds to the intersectionality-oriented interventions of the pilots, and which is capable of providing us with the type of data needed to evaluate the pilot assemblies and draw recommendations. An overview of the evaluation plans is provided in **Section IX**.

Before turning to the design choices for pilots, the next section consists of a review of the positionality of the project team and of the facilitators who will be engaged in the pilot citizens' assemblies.

III. Reviewing our Positionality

As already mentioned, and as explained more fully in Deliverable 3.4, **awareness of our own positionality** is a crucial consideration in the incorporation of intersectionality into the design and delivery of citizens' assemblies. It is therefore important that we, as a project team, and as specific role holders, show awareness of our positionality and consider how this positionality might influence our engagement with participants in the pilot citizens' assemblies. As such, we conducted two **positionality reviews** in advance of the pilots, one for the project team as a whole⁴, and one for facilitators. The latter was thought particularly important given the project's emphasis on facilitation as a mechanism for effectively incorporating intersectionality considerations into citizens' assembly practice. The exercise was voluntary, given the potentially sensitive nature of the information to be shared. It was explained that it was up to the individual to share as little or as much reflection as they felt comfortable with sharing. Full ethics approval and informed consent were obtained before embarking on this exercise.

For many, this was the first time that they had engaged with such an exercise, and so we provided online training in advance delivered by Karen Bowlby, Inclusion Manager at the University of Essex on 13 January 2026 (see Appendix 1). Karen explained the notion of **'unearned' privilege**, a concept which we often do not think about on a daily basis due to its invisibility. She noted that the term 'privilege' can evoke feelings of guilt, shame, and denial, which can shut down conversations surrounding privilege, marginalisation, and positionality. It is important, therefore, that privilege and marginalisation be framed as 'structural' and 'systemic' rather than 'individual', which also echoes our project's understanding of intersectionality as being grounded in overlapping power relations rather than individual identities. The concept of positionality refers to the recognition that our social positions shape what we do, how we do it, and how we interpret findings. Understanding positionality helps ensure awareness of biases, promotes ethical design, and highlights power dynamics, all of which are important considerations as we engage in the design of intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly pilots.

⁴ It should be mentioned that the term 'project team' refers here to the consortium as a whole i.e., it expands beyond the persons that contributed to the design of the pilots per se.

As part of the online Facilitators Training held on 19 January 2026, Kathryn McCabe from The Change Agency, also delivered a session on Intersectionality, Positionality, and Power, which gave the facilitators an insight into how their positionality may shape their role in engaging and interacting with the pilot citizens' assemblies participants (see Deliverable 4.2 for a copy of the presentation). Kathryn's presentation allowed us to consider how facilitators can understand and navigate power dynamics in diverse groups by reflecting on the ways in which our social positions and identities shape our perspective, actions, and interpretations. Kathryn also reiterated (as Karen had done in her presentation for the project team), that (unearned) 'privilege' can provide often invisible advantages to those who possess it (in the same way that marginalisation can often be 'covert' or hidden). The overall message from the presentation was that achieving (intersectional) equality and inclusion requires an understanding of systemic power dynamics and a commitment to *actively* use one's position to dismantle oppressive structures. This can involve both learning about, but also 'unlearning', existing biases and assumptions.

In addition to the online training sessions, more detailed guidance and instructions were provided through our development of a **Toolkit** for conducting positionality reviews in the context of citizens' assemblies, which consists of a **Positionality Review of Project Team** (see Appendix 2) and a **Positionality Review of Facilitators** (see Appendix 3). Both positionality reviews (project team and facilitators) consisted of two broad processes, namely: (1) 'reflection' on the individual's own positionality as it relates to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation; and (2) 'reflexion' on what this positionality might mean for the individual's role as a project team member (researcher) or as a facilitator. The reflection involved the completion of a 'Power Flower', whereby the individual could identify their positionality in relation to those holding the most 'privilege' in a given context, using the 'Wheel of Privilege' for guidance. Individuals were then invited to reflect on this positionality in order to identify their own markers of privilege or marginalisation. The reflexion consisted of a series of questions tailored to the individual's role (whether as a project team member or as a facilitator). For project team members, the focus was on their role as a 'researcher', with questions grouped into the following categories: selecting research topics and questions; ontological assumptions; epistemological assumptions; methodological assumptions; reciprocity; and communication. For the facilitators, the questions were more targeted to their specific role and were grouped as follows: motivation for engaging in facilitation; designing and managing the facilitation process; ensuring intersectional good deliberation; and reciprocity and capacity building.

The purpose of these activities was to allow the UE team to conduct a **general assessment** of the positionality of the project team and facilitators and to consider the potential **impact** of our positionality on the conduct of the pilot citizens' assemblies. As these exercises were voluntary, there was not universal engagement with the exercise, which, following discussion with the team, may be reflective of continued trepidation in taking part in what remains an unfamiliar process to many, despite the training provided. Of course, the nature of the exercise required participants to answer a wide range of (complex) questions to allow for sufficient high-quality information to be gathered for the purpose of properly considering our positionality. This complexity may have been off-putting for some, and we have taken this into account when considering how to engage the pilots' participants in a similar reflective and reflexive exercise in a way that is more accessible, familiar, and less time-consuming.⁵ Nevertheless, there was sufficient engagement with the exercise from both project team members and facilitators, to allow for a considered review of our positionality and its potential influence on the design and conduct of the pilot citizens' assemblies. Overall, 14 project team members submitted a completed exercise, while seven facilitators completed theirs (note that there was some overlap in that certain project team members are also acting as facilitators, and that the project team is larger than the facilitators' team).

Overall, both the project and facilitation teams exhibited a degree of privilege, meaning we must take care to **avoid** centering the project's goals and conduct around **dominant narratives and perspectives**. At the same time, there were several markers of marginalisation visible across both teams, particularly with regard to sex, sexual orientation, and neurodivergence. There were frequent references to caring responsibilities as a marker of disadvantage, particularly within an academic setting. It was also notable that certain markers of privilege/marginalisation changed over time, particularly with regard to housing security and socio-economic status and which is perhaps reflective of the educational background evident across the teams, which tends towards the privileged (university educated). There was also a good deal of reflection on the 'dynamic' nature of positionality, including the fact that while certain markers of privilege or marginalisation may remain 'static', the way in which they are experienced can change over time and across locations and contexts.

⁵ We have developed a tailored icebreaking activity for the pilots, inspired by concepts of positionality, power, and privilege. Please see Section VI and Appendix 8.

An obvious 'gap' in the team's positionality with regard to marginalisation is **race/ethnicity**, with almost all participants in the exercise being members of the dominant social group in that category, within their relevant geographical/social contexts. Having said that, many project team members are living and working in a country other than that of their birth, and in a language that is not their own, with attendant feelings of '**outsider**' status. It is also worth noting that several respondents framed both their markers of privilege and marginalisation as potential 'constraints', or sources of shame or embarrassment, leading to 'trade-offs' or attempts to 'blend in', demonstrating the complex interaction within and across social groups and how we perceive our interactions with others.

There was some useful consideration of the capacity of team members and facilitators to exercise **power** over the pilots' participants, and the need for ongoing and continuous reflection on **managing this relationship**, including the need to **avoid assumptions of equivalence** across markers of marginalisation. It should of course be noted that there is a degree of 'self-selection' at play here, in that most respondents recognised that their decision to work on this project stemmed from an underlying interest in issues of equality, marginalisation, and participation and so most team members were already aware of these issues. There was, therefore, reference throughout the reflective statements of a desire to display **empathy** and to ensure that all voices are heard and valued in the pilot citizens' assemblies, as well as an awareness of how **privilege** influences 'access' to decision-making spaces. With regard specifically to the local pilot, which will engage with the University of Essex student community, it was interesting to note that many respondents referenced their professional capacity as educators, holding a position of power and influence over students in their working lives.

Overall, the positionality reviews demonstrate an awareness of the need to consider and address '**blind spots**' and to empathise with lived experiences and situations which are different from one's own. Reflection/reflexion should not be a one-off event, but rather an ongoing and possibly transformative process through which we consider the impact of our actions on the participants in three pilot citizens' assemblies that we are conducting. As such, further reflexive exercises, such as project team de-brief meetings, and surveys will be conducted throughout the evaluation stage of all three pilots (See Section X).

By actively 'designing' for reflection on positionality as a key consideration in incorporating intersectionality into citizens' assemblies, we also hope to provide a pathway for other projects

and citizens' assembly organisers to understand how positionality can influence their own processes and what steps can be taken to mitigate exclusionary impacts. Throughout the pilots, and as explained in the Evaluation Plan in Section X, facilitators, observers, and notetakers, as well as the participants themselves, will be invited to engage in continuous reflection on their positionality and its impact on the process and outcome of the pilot citizens' assemblies.

IV. Context-Based Approach

The adoption of a context-based approach is one of our project's key considerations for incorporating intersectionality into citizens' assemblies. Our contention is that the precise interaction between social groups and structures of marginalisation can only properly be understood in their relevant **context**, whether institutional, historical, economic, social, cultural, or geographical. As McKinzie and Richards put it, 'attention to the historical, political, economic, and social factors that shape power relationships and social structures is critical to conducting robust intersectional analyses that avoid reification of social categories and inequalities' (McKinzie and Richards, 2019, p. 1).

The very concepts of exclusion, marginalisation, or indeed intersectionality itself, can also be dependent on the particular context, including the categorisation—and relationship between—social groups. Moreover, we are testing pilot citizens' assemblies at different levels (local, national, and transnational) which in itself is an important contextual background when evaluating their effectiveness with regard to intersectionality considerations. We have also argued that determining what is meant by relevant social groups (we are interested primarily in sex/gender, age, race/ethnicity, and socio-economic status and their intersections), and who precisely is marginalised within those social groups, requires an understanding of the underlying the local, national, and transnational contexts. The topic of the assembly (in this case, housing) also necessitates an additional layer of contextual understanding.

As explained in Deliverable 3.4, the first step in understanding the wider (structural, societal, and legal) systems of power in relation to a given topic (e.g. housing) is to conduct a **contextual 'power analysis'**. A power analysis allows for the consideration of who holds the power in a particular community. A power analysis serves as a useful **structuring device** for applying our intersectional normative framework to understand intersectional marginalisation in a given context, as well as allowing us to recognise the relevant decision-makers and policy influencers. Moreover, our conceptualisation of intersectionality as an analytical and normative lens is grounded in the notion of 'power' and (structural or institutional) power relations (privilege and marginalisation) at a collective or societal level, rather than individual identities as such. As a recently published UN Guide and Toolkit on Intersectionality put it, '[u]nderstanding the context in which we are located and its power dynamics is vital for practitioners and policymakers

[allowing for] an overview of power dynamics in a specific time and place' (UN Intersectionality Resource Guide and Toolkit n.d.).

For the purposes of conducting a context-based analysis for our three pilots, we focused on the following (overlapping and interrelated) elements:

- (1) The demographic context: Focuses on the make-up of the relevant population (at the local, national, or transnational level respectively);
- (2) The institutional context: Focuses on the question of who holds the power to make decisions on the topic of the assembly;
- (3) The topical context: Focuses on the issues that arise within the context of the topic of the assembly. The topic of all three of our pilot citizens' assemblies is housing..

Figure 3: Elements of a context-based analysis

1. Context-Based Analysis for the Local Pilot

In what follows, we present the findings of the context-based analysis for the **local pilot** in Colchester, Essex, United Kingdom (full details, including sources, can be found in Appendix 4). This serves two purposes. First, to show how the analysis itself **influenced the design of, and was used during, our local pilot**. As part of the preparation for the pilots, this context-based analysis was used to brief the facilitators and the project team prior to the pilot taking place. This was done in response to feedback from the project team that a certain level of understanding of the local context around housing and around the Colchester community is necessary for the facilitators to be able to engage properly with the participants; especially given that most of the project team were not Colchester residents. A synopsis of these findings was presented during the Facilitators Briefing Session held online on 19 February 2026 (see the presentation slides at Appendix 5). Furthermore, a synopsis of the analysis will be presented to the participants of the assembly themselves, during the in-person assembly session that is scheduled to take place on 28 February 2026.

The second purpose of the analysis below is to act as a **template** for how we are going to conduct the context-based analysis for the other two pilots of the project (at national level in Cyprus, and at the EU-level for the transnational pilot). The background information for this analysis for the local pilot in Colchester, Essex, United Kingdom can be found in Appendix 4.

1.1. The Demographic Context

Colchester is a small city located in the East of England in the United Kingdom, approximately 84 kilometres from London. Colchester was awarded city status in 2022 as part of Queen Elizabeth II's Platinum Jubilee celebrations and is often referred to as 'Britain's oldest town' due to its long history, dating back to Roman times. The 2021 census for England and Wales provides a snapshot of the demography of Colchester (also as it relates to the rest of England).

The population of Colchester was recorded as 192,700, which represents an increase of 11.3% since the 2011 census, a faster rate of growth than the regional and England averages. This means that Colchester is a growing and changing community, with increased pressure on local infrastructure including housing and transport. Many residents of Colchester commute to

London for work and there are newer populations who have moved out from London due to better affordability of housing in Essex compared to London. Colchester also includes a large 'short-term' population of students due to the presence of the University of Essex, located on the outskirts of the city, near the village of Wivenhoe.

The median age in Colchester is 39, which means that the population is slightly younger than the English average. 87% of the population was White in 2021, which is down from 92% in 2011, demonstrating a growing diversity in the city. 56.7% of the population were in employment (note that the census was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic). Unemployment in the wider UK context has also increased recently. 6.8% of residents indicated that they had a disability that limited them a lot.

Analysis conducted by the University of Essex shows that the student population is notably more diverse than Colchester as a whole. In Academic Year 2023-2024, 47% of undergraduate students were White, while 21% of postgraduate students were White (50% were Asian). The majority of postgraduate students were also classed as 'international' (as opposed to 'home') students.

1.2. The Institutional Context

At a national (England) level, housing is the responsibility of the Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government. The recently enacted Renters' Rights Act 2025 is an important legislative intervention that seeks to end 'no fault' evictions from May 2026, meaning that landlords will need to provide a good reason for asking tenants to leave. The Act will improve both the flexibility and security of tenants, allowing them to leave their tenancy with two months' notice. The Act prohibits rental bidding, whereby potential renters can outbid each other by offering to pay a higher rate of rent, while also limiting the ability of landlords to increase rent.

At a local level, housing is primarily the responsibility of Colchester City Council. The Council is also the 'landlord' for social housing in Colchester. There is often confusion as to who is responsible for housing as there is an additional layer of local government in Colchester, namely Essex County Council. During the Assembly, we might expect participants to express frustration towards the 'council' generally, without specifying (or being aware of) which body is actually responsible.

For student accommodation, the University of Essex bears primary responsibility for the provision of accommodation services, alongside private management companies for certain accommodation types.

1.3. The Topical Context

The 2021 census showed that 64.6% of Colchester residents were homeowners, 21.5% were private renters, while 13.3% rented social housing. This suggests a need for us to be alert to potential tensions between owners of property and renters (whether social or private), between younger and older residents, and between students and non-student residents. Moreover, there are structural consequences to disparities in tenure, linked for example to security and stability as well as cost (housing costs continue to rise). The average private rent in Colchester now stands at £1,208 per calendar month, while the average price for a new home is £301,000, meaning that Colchester is less affordable than England as a whole, and that many younger residents are priced out of the market and need to wait longer to build a deposit (it is usual for lenders to require a 10% deposit on the purchase price of a home). Some participants in the Assembly may be 'social' renters: social housing is designed to be more affordable to those on a lower income, with rents set based on a formula that takes account of income in the local area.

In addition to the above, we sought to engage in a 'listening exercise' with the relevant communities. Our approach built on years of work that two of the project team members had undertaken in the local community. Since 2018, Rebecca Warren and Samantha Woodward had undertaken various community organising projects and community-led research projects in collaboration with a range of community-based organisations and students, focusing on a range of issues, including housing. Through this work we were able to share with the project team the wider context of listening that they had done in the community across these years, identifying common issues and patterns that had emerged across this longitudinal view. Building out of this approach, for this particular project from September 2025 to January 2026 our team engaged in listening exercises with local stakeholders. We shared the project and the ways that we wanted to work together with the stakeholders in an alliance meeting. The engagement activities included attending the Youth Assembly organised by Citizens Essex, regular attendance at meetings organised by the Citizens Essex Alliance (across this period there were four such

meetings), and holding two co-design workshops, one with local community organisers and one with student representatives from the University of Essex Students' Union. In this 'listening' exercise, a number of issues of concern relating to housing were raised. We collected the issues and grouped them into five categories, namely: affordability and supply, quality and safety, Marginalised groups facing housing instability, planning and infrastructure, and student-community relations.

Under the first category, affordability and supply, there were concerns about the lack of affordable and social housing. The 'right to buy' social housing was raised as a cause of concern in that it has led to a depletion of housing stock, with supply unable to keep pace with demand. There were more general anxieties expressed concerning the cost of living and income insecurity. Under quality and safety, there were concerns about the state of disrepair of rented housing, with landlords often unresponsive to repair requests. Potential accessibility challenges for disabled and neurodivergent renters and buyers were also raised. Finally, the safety and security of the wider neighbourhood and locality were important to those we spoke to.

Marginalised groups facing housing instability that were highlighted throughout the listening exercise include the homeless, families requiring temporary accommodation due to long social housing waiting lists, those who are unable to share housing, and international students. International students (and indeed all new residents from abroad) often face structural barriers to accessing housing in the UK, including guarantor requirements, upfront payment demands, language and other cultural barriers, meaning that they are at a higher risk of exploitation and may suffer from lower levels of power and confidence in navigating the local housing market. During the listening exercise, those participating expressed frustration at the lack of planning and infrastructure, particularly surrounding new housing developments which are often located far from local amenities and public transport and with attendant risks to the environment due to encroachment into greenfield sites and urban sprawl. With regard to student-community relations, there is a risk that a short-term student population can put pressure on the local housing market. This risk has lessened in recent years due to the construction of additional student housing at the University of Essex but also due to a decrease in student numbers across the UK, particularly for international students.

Through the co-design workshops we were able to explore these issues in more depth with key stakeholders and encourage the participants to contribute to forming the approach of the assembly. For the student focused workshops, we were joined by key members of the Students' Union who represent particular groups of students, including the International Students Officer, the Community Officer for Neurodivergent Students, the Students' Union President, the Vice President for Welfare and the Chief Executive for the Students' Union. For the Citizens Essex focused workshop a member and volunteer of a local multi-ethnic church ministry joined, as did an organiser from the local Colchester foodbank, alongside a member of Citizens Essex who works in a local infrastructure charity and the community organiser for Citizens Essex. For both workshops, we ran a structured co-design process to ensure that the citizens' assembly was shaped *with* participants (or with those close to or representing the participants) rather than simply *for* them. The workshop aimed to collaboratively define the purpose, structure, values, and practical elements of the assembly.

The session began by introducing the concept of a citizens' assembly, setting out why it matters and how it fits within the wider project's focus on intersectionality, housing, and lived experience. Participants reflected on their own positionality and took part in introductory rounds centred on belonging and inclusion, helping establish shared ground rules rooted in respect, openness, and collective ownership.

Working together, participants mapped the key issues the assembly should address, identifying why housing mattered, what aspects required attention, and which questions should sit within or outside the assembly's scope. This included a short deliberation on priority areas and consideration of how wider student input might be gathered.

The central part of the workshop focused on designing the assembly itself. Participants explored four core components:

- **Who participates** – identifying who should be invited, how to ensure diversity and representation, and what support would be needed to involve groups who often face barriers to participation;
- **How they participate** – discussing accessibility (language, childcare, transport, digital), emotional and psychological safety, and the information or expertise required to support fair deliberation;

- **How the assembly should run** – shaping facilitation approaches, preferred discussion formats, and how to elevate voices that are not usually heard;
- **How decisions are made** – considering consensus-building, voting methods, transparency, documentation, and how recommendations should be used and communicated.

The participants of the workshops then co-created **a set of core values**, such as fairness, inclusion, respect and transparency, and reflected on where these values needed to be embedded throughout the assembly's design. The workshop closed with a short reflection on what worked well, what required further development, and what commitments or next steps participants felt were needed. Taken together, the co-design process ensured the assembly was grounded in local experience, guided by participants' priorities, and shaped through collective reasoning about inclusion, representation, and impact.

As explained in Deliverable 3.4, the added-value of conducting a context-based approach from an intersectionality perspective is that it allows us to identify those who are most marginalised in a given context, whether geographical, social, economic, etc., but also to identify what issues are particularly prevalent within a particular community on a given topic (in our case, housing). Taken together, this allows us to identify **the particular problems** faced by those in a particularly marginalised position **in the relevant community** and with regard to the **relevant topic**.

The context-based analysis of Colchester fed back into the design process for our local pilot, for example through co-designing with the local communities, through the selection of specific issues for discussion within the broad umbrella of housing, through the communication messages of our recruitment campaign, and through identifying the relevant stakeholders to whom to address our eventual recommendations from the pilot. Moreover, the context-based analysis was used to provide essential training to facilitators and observers to help them to apprehend and engage with the local context, allowing them more effectively to understand the concerns of the participants in the pilot, all of whom were drawn from the local communities.

The analysis that we have conducted for Colchester now provides a **template** for how we will approach the contextual analysis for the national pilot (in Cyprus) and the transnational pilot (across several EU Member States), while remaining mindful of the need to adapt the context-based approach itself to the needs of the relevant context.

V. Recruitment

For the local pilot, based in Colchester, Essex, United Kingdom, we adopted a deliberate and targeted approach to the recruitment of participants. This strategy formed a component of the targeted intervention of ‘co-designing’ which we deployed throughout the local pilot citizens’ assembly. Our first step was to identify the relevant communities that we wanted to engage with throughout the local pilot, namely the University of Essex student community and the wider (permanent) resident population of Colchester, with the overarching objective of bridging the perceived divide between the two communities when it comes to housing in Colchester. As already explained, our context-based analysis, drawing from the census and University of Essex-derived survey data, identified **divergence** in the demographics of the two populations, with the student population being noticeably more diverse on the basis of race and ethnicity.

Our next step was to engage in a listening exercise through the two co-design workshops mentioned above, which we conducted in December 2025 in collaboration with the University of Essex Students’ Union, representing the student community and with Citizens’ Essex, representing the wider Colchester community. Perhaps unsurprisingly, both communities had a variety of distinct concerns and raised a number of diverging but also overlapping issues regarding housing. We further liaised with these two co-design groups to identify effective approaches to reaching out to the relevant communities and to encourage their participation in our pilot assembly. This included a follow-up meeting with members of the University of Essex Students’ Union who provided feedback on our recruitment communication material, as well as some aspects of the pilot assembly including the timing, the duration, the location, and the content of the assembly’s three sessions. Overall, this involved the adoption of a tailored approach to recruitment designed to reach out to the relevant communities and ensure their participation.

For the wider Colchester community, we deployed various members of Citizens Essex, with whom we engaged during the co-design workshops held in December 2025, to reach out to their community contacts to engage with potential participants. At the same time, we adopted a broader media strategy, which included stories in the local press as well as a recruitment campaign conducted with the University of Essex media team on their website and through

social media.⁶ A similar social media strategy was conducted with the students at the University of Essex in addition to an email and social media campaign from the University of Essex Students' Union, and 'on the ground' recruitment of participants with a 2-day gazebo stand at the University's Colchester campus.⁷ In the stand, members of the project team got the opportunity to discuss on a one-to-one basis with students, presenting the upcoming pilot and discussing the benefits of taking part. The below posters were distributed across campus, and University lecturers were invited to present the project during compulsory undergraduate and postgraduate lectures:

⁶ See: <https://www.gazette-news.co.uk/news/25864373.colchester-housing-university-essex-research-issues/> and <https://www.essex.ac.uk/news/2026/02/16/volunteers-needed-for-colchester-housing-discussion>

⁷ See: <https://www.instagram.com/reel/DUndqJhiNYf/>

YOUR CHANCE TO BE PART OF SOMETHING BIGGER!

Join us to discuss housing issues at the University and in Colchester.

 £50 IN AMAZON VOUCHERS
CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

Scan to learn more and register

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YOUR CHANCE TO BE PART OF SOMETHING BIGGER!

24 Feb
Zoom

28 Feb
Campus

10 Mar
Zoom

Join us to discuss housing issues at the University and in Colchester.

**£50 IN AMAZON VOUCHERS
CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION**

Scan to learn more and register

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 EU-CIEMBLY
Democracy for All

YOUR CHANCE TO BE PART OF SOMETHING BIGGER!

COLCHESTER CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY ON HOUSING

 £50 IN AMAZON VOUCHERS
 CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION
 LUNCH FOR THE IN-PERSON SESSION

Scan to learn more and register

euciembly@essex.ac.uk

Join a group of people from different backgrounds and life paths who come together to:

- learn about housing issues that affect everyday life
- discuss in a respectful, supported space
- develop ideas and recommendations together

No specialist knowledge needed!

24/2 Zoom	28/2 Campus	10/3 Zoom
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Figure 4. Local pilot recruitment posters

The QR code found on the poster and across our media campaigns directed potential participants towards the registration survey (Appendix 6) through which they could express their interest in participating in the project while also accessing the relevant Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form.

For the Cyprus pilot, we will conduct a context-based approach similar to what we have done for the local pilot in order to identify and specify the social groups of interest, and the intersections of those social groups. As mentioned in Deliverable 3.4, we will adopt a more intersectionality-oriented approach to the selection of participants to the assembly, meaning we will actively seek to include in our participants' group persons from the intersection of the identified marginalised groups. An attempt will take place to sample and recruit residents from across the five main cities in Cyprus. We are planning to run a Cyprus-wide communications campaign via the social media accounts of the project and of collaborating public authorities (e.g. the Commissioner for the Rights of the Citizen, and the Cyprus Youth Organisation), and social media accounts and email lists of collaborating civil society organisations. This will be complemented by a visibility campaign through events and media appearances (including the project's presentation at the Cyprus Forum (1 October 2025), Vergina TV (20 February 2026), and Alpha TV forthcoming in March 2026). As with the rest of the decisions governing the design of the pilots, we embrace a flexible approach to sampling and recruitment, acknowledging that our efforts in the upcoming months may open up new or different paths for gathering a sampling pool, and that this is the first time that a citizens' assembly of such an extent will take place in Cyprus.

For the transnational pilot, we aim to create an enclave involving those deeply affected by an aspect of the housing crisis in Europe (as explained in Deliverable 3.4). This follows the project's context-based approach: rather than pre-defining which social groups are the most marginalised groups across the EU - since this might diverge from country to country and area to area - and then seeking their intersections to guide recruitment, the process begins by asking three intersectionality-oriented guiding questions: *What is the issue the assembly seeks to address? Who needs to be in the room to deliberate on it, based on the 'deeply affected' principle? And how can they be reached?*

As a result of embedding the 'deeply affected' principle in the transnational pilot, and acknowledging the limited resources available within this project, we treat the issue of country

selection as instrumental rather than normative. That is, the countries we will focus our sampling and recruitment efforts on are practical conduits for reaching people who are deeply affected by the housing issue, not as ends in themselves or as claims about which Member States matter most for that issue.

Given practical constraints on project resources, we will concentrate sampling efforts in five to six countries where there are practical advantages for gathering a large enough sampling pool (e.g. existing national samples and re-contact consents from previous projects, partner networks, CSO access, and consortium language capacity). These countries are currently expected to include Cyprus, Ireland, Germany, Portugal, Spain, and Malta. However, this does not preclude participants residing in other countries from participating.

To operationalise the ‘deeply affected’ principle, we plan to adopt a hybrid recruitment methodology that balances gathering participants with a range of lived experience of the housing issue and intersectional diversity. This approach will be grounded in a contextual analysis of how structural and institutional barriers impact and constrain the public participation of persons belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups in the development of housing policy, and specifically persons belonging to the intersections of our four ‘anchor’ social groups, namely: (1) race or ethnic origin; (2) sex or gender; (3) age or generation; and (4) socio-economic status - while remaining attentive to housing-specific factors such as disability, migration status, and tenure insecurity that compound exclusion. This will be achieved through a short sampling survey which gathers data on each variable for each potential participant, i.e. the same survey-based approach to be adopted for the local and national pilot. To develop the sampling pool for the transnational pilot, we will follow a **two-channel pathway** combining *CSO nomination* and an *open call* to achieve depth of lived experience and diversity of perspective.

1. CSO pathway:

- Partnerships with European CSOs (e.g., Community Action Tenants Union Ireland, Housing First Europe, German Tenants’ Association, migrant and disability housing groups such as Inclusion Ireland) with well-established lived experience networks/members with lived experience of housing issues
- CSOs nominate or invite individuals with direct experience of housing precarity (non-staff) to register (i.e., to enter the sampling pool) for the assembly

2. Open call pathway:

- Draws from nationally representative panels in Ireland and Germany and supplementary outreach on social media targeting underrepresented intersections
- A screening survey attached to the project partner Make.org’s consultation platform deployed y through partner networks and targeted outreach, will identify participants with varying degrees of exposure to housing issues and will ensure our ability to achieve representation across **anchor social categories**: race/ethnicity, gender, age, and socio-economic status.⁸

We will seek to define an **intersectional inclusion matrix** to guide recruitment from this sampling pool. The inclusion matrix will be an analytical tool combining housing-specific vulnerability (e.g. tenure insecurity, income-to-rent ratio) with intersectional marginalisation indicators (race/ethnic origin, sex/gender, age/generation, socio-economic status) to determine the final balance of participants.

Size and demographics of the participant group

This pilot will involve 100 participants, which in addition to the transnational nature of this pilot, brings additional difficulties in recruitment. As such, we have included more details here about our plans to define size and demographics of the participant group, with the continuous caveat that we adopt a flexible and adaptive approach to recruitment throughout this project. The intersectional inclusion matrix will ensure there is diversity across all variables. We will also ensure a diversity of experience and views by developing categories of participants according to their level of exposure to housing issues, which is likely to follow the following structure (to be further refined).

Category	Description
<i>Deeply affected / lived experience</i>	Persons at the intersection of two or more marginalisation axes (via CSO and open-call self-selection)
<i>Moderately affected</i>	Participants facing housing strain but not severe precarity

⁸ For more information on this please see Section IX.

The governance model for the transnational pilot also operationalises the theoretical insights of the Subaltern Counterpublics model by embedding power-sharing, reflexivity, and co-production into the organisational structure of the assembly. In the theoretical framework developed across Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3, intersectional inclusion requires more than representational diversity - rather, it demands a redistribution of epistemic authority and institutional power in order for those deeply affected by structural inequalities to shape both the deliberative content and the conditions of participation. Traditional top-down citizens' assemblies typically centralise decision-making power in a commissioning body or expert secretariat. In contrast, the counterpublic model calls for a pluralist governance architecture, where marginalised groups can influence agenda-setting, design, and outcome validation.

As such, the transnational assembly's governance structure will attempt to follow a **dual accountability model** combining institutional oversight and participatory legitimacy through the development of a Participant Advisory Panel. This will be formed from a subset of the participants recruited via civil-society organisations (CSOs) early in the planning process for the CA, enabling this group to provide lived experience input on inclusion-related matters throughout the design of the CA process, including participant communications, accessibility, and specific design elements of the assembly itself.

Participants from all three pilots will be invited to contribute to the Oral History Exhibition foreseen under WP6 (Task 6.5) e.g. through vox-pop style interviews during the assembly events. This exhibition, developed jointly by the Universities of Essex and Coimbra, will record personal testimonies of assembly participants reflecting on their participatory experience. Including transnational participants in this exhibition will ensure that their lived experiences inform not only policy recommendations but also the project's broader narrative on inclusive democratic participation. Options for sustaining engagement and following-up with assembly members beyond the transnational pilot will also be explored in the context of Task 5.3 EU-CIEMBLY Living Labs.

VI. Facilitation

In our design process, we adopted a wide definition of the term ‘facilitation’, which extends beyond the small-group deliberation moments during an assembly process. Facilitation was seen as a concept that relates to two stages: the frontstage and the backstage. The frontstage refers to the visible and immediate work that facilitators do during deliberation: the moments of interaction, communication management, and collective meaning-making that participants directly experience. In this visible dimension, facilitators are responsible for orchestrating the social dynamics of the group i.e., reading communication patterns, ensuring equal speaking opportunities, managing tension and conflict, and encouraging dialogue across social, cultural, and political divides (Escobar, 2019).

Frontstage facilitation aims to ensure that all participants – regardless of their background, confidence, or communicative ability – can engage meaningfully in the deliberation. Facilitators draw upon what Escobar (2019) calls a toolbox: conversational guidelines and engagement rules co-designed with participants; discursive strategies such as questioning, paraphrasing, summarising, and reframing; and participatory devices like post-its, clustering exercises, or visual mapping. These tools create a structure to the deliberation that fosters respectful dialogue while allowing space for emotional, narrative, or creative expressions. According to Deliverable 2.3, ensuring internal inclusion within the deliberative process is central to intersectional facilitation. Facilitators are expected to prevent what Young (2000) calls ‘internal exclusion’ i.e., the reproduction of broader social inequalities within the deliberative setting. This involves continuously monitoring group dynamics to prevent dominance by participants with higher levels of education, confidence, or linguistic fluency, while actively encouraging the participation of those whose voices are typically marginalised. In this context, humour can help break tension and rebalance power relations (Hewer et al., 2019).

Similarly, creative, but widely established, facilitation methods—such as storytelling, metaphors, or role-playing—can allow participants from marginalised groups to express perspectives that might otherwise remain unheard. This should also be linked to, and organised through, the way in which citizens interact, and the criteria used to bring them to deliberate together. As emphasised in Deliverables 2.2 and 2.3, dialogue should not be limited to ‘reasoned argument’

but should include emotional and experiential modes of expression that enrich collective understanding.

Although the frontstage is where deliberation unfolds in practice, much of the facilitator's work occurs **backstage**: in the design, preparation, and post-deliberative documentation of the deliberative process. Drawing on Escobar (2015, 2019), this dimension includes three interrelated functions: public-making, scripting, and inscribing. *Public-making* refers to the transformation of a group of strangers into a deliberative public. Before the assembly begins, organisers must establish trust, ensure accessibility, and create a sense of shared purpose. This process involves **logistical as well as relational decisions**: choosing inclusive venues and seating arrangements, adapting language and materials, and setting ground rules collaboratively with participants. As highlighted in the UK Innovation in Democracy Programme (2020), collective rule-setting and/or the agreement over key rules of democratic deliberation and early framing of deliberative values are key to building ownership and legitimacy.

Scripting involves defining the framework within which deliberation will occur: 'the orchestration of people, language, and artefacts within purposeful assemblages' (Escobar, 2015). Here, facilitators, often working with organisers and chairs, shape the structure of interaction: how sessions are sequenced, when small-group discussions alternate with plenary sessions, and how diverse forms of expertise (academic, experiential, civic) are introduced. The script should remain flexible, allowing facilitators to adapt to group dynamics or emerging tensions without making interactions feel artificial.

Finally, *inscribing* refers to the documentation of deliberation: recording key arguments, capturing different perspectives, and ensuring that minority voices are reflected in the outputs. As stressed in Deliverable 2.3, documenting dissent and alternative perspectives is a central feature of inclusive deliberation. Facilitators act as the translators of the experiential language of participants into the formal language of policy-making. In this sense, note-taking and visualisation tools (e.g., post-it clustering, flipchart synthesis, or digital capture platforms) are not neutral artefacts: they determine which ideas become visible and how deliberation is later represented.

In our project, therefore, backstage facilitation is seen as the hidden infrastructure of intersectional inclusion. It is through careful orchestration of the entire citizens' assembly

process that facilitators seek to prevent procedural bias, maintain transparency, and transform deliberative talk into legitimate and recognisable outcomes.

We see the distinction between frontstage and backstage as analytical rather than absolute. In practice, facilitation is a continuous movement between the two spaces, requiring **adaptability** and **reflexivity**. Facilitation ‘is a contingent, pragmatic, and bodily endeavour that resists standardisation’ (Escobar, 2019, p. 181). Both adaptiveness and reflexivity are central to designing intersectionality-oriented citizens’ assemblies and thus to our pilots’ design.

Adaptability is particularly relevant for citizens’ assemblies, such as ours, that are seeking to follow an intersectional approach as facilitators must respond to the lived realities and power asymmetries among participants. For the purposes of our pilots, it was necessary to establish a **general protocol** that ensures a common approach among the different facilitators involved in the citizens’ assemblies. Since facilitation is a cross-cutting intervention of this project, a general protocol was also necessary to allow for a common approach in the deliberation taking place in the three pilots as well as in the training that is developed for the pilots’ facilitators. However, the protocol must also allow facilitators the freedom to adjust communication patterns, group configurations, and timing as the deliberation unfolds.

This general protocol took the form of an **EU-CIEMBLY Handbook for Intersectional Deliberation**, which was drafted by the team for our project pilots and operates as a training tool for everyone involved in the organisation and the facilitation of the three pilots. The Handbook establishes a common approach towards the attitude, skills, and methods that organisers and facilitators must use during the pilot assemblies. The Handbook was written by the Make.org team with contributions from the UE and the UniBg teams. It was presented during the Facilitators’ Training workshop on 19 January 2026 and can be found in the appendices to Deliverable 4.2.

A number of additional actions and activities have been designed and organised by the UE team, in collaboration with other project teams, to ensure a **common understanding** among the team members involved in the implementation of the pilots. This included the Facilitators’ Training workshop (see Deliverable 4.2), as well as dedicated briefing and de-briefing meetings

prior to, and after each, assembly session.⁹ All the material and training provided to facilitators were recorded and are available in the project's Google Drive folder.

Reflexivity was also seen as central to the process of citizens' assembly facilitation. Facilitators must continuously examine how their own intersectional characteristics – such as those relating to sex/gender, and race/ethnicity, as well as markers of (relative) privilege, such as their professional background or institutional affiliation – influence interactions. Facilitators should be encouraged to make their standpoint visible where appropriate, acknowledging that total neutrality is neither possible nor desirable. It is our contention that transparency surrounding positionality can increase trust and authenticity in the deliberative process. To enable reflexivity in the process of our pilots' design and implementation, both the project team and the facilitators were asked to complete the Positionality reviews mentioned above in Section III and attached in Appendices 3 and 4.

The above considerations echo our project's overall vision for an intersectionality-informed approach to deliberation as set out in Deliverable 3.4, which sees facilitation as a relational practice embedded in power rather than a purely technical function. Against this background, we sought to turn the intersectionality activators into concrete action across the frontstage and the backstage of the facilitators' work. Previous work that has taken place in the project identified three potential 'intersectionality activators' that could foster intersectional deliberation across all three pilots.¹⁰ These are pictured below, in Figure 5.

⁹ E.g. for the Colchester pilot, the team held a briefing meeting before each assembly session, and a de-briefing meeting after each assembly session.

¹⁰ See Deliverable 3.4 Section V.

Figure 5: Activators of intersectionality-informed facilitation

These activators are seen as transversal, applying regardless of whether the citizens’ assembly process is conducted at the local, national, or transnational level. Throughout our pilot citizens’ assemblies, we will attempt to turn these intersectionality activators into tangible actions, as described below:

Activator 1: Value diverse communication modes

Summary:

Intersectionality-driven facilitation values multiple communicative modes, such as storytelling, emotional expression, humour, and embodied knowledge, as legitimate contributions to collective reasoning. The aim here is to encourage more equitable collective outcomes by fostering open dialogue, and the sharing of personal experiences, stories, and testimonies.

Actions:

1.1 Facilitators were trained in specific, observable techniques that encourage the use of diverse communicative modes. These techniques involve:

- (a) explicitly inviting means of sharing lived experiences, such as storytelling and personal testimony, as valid forms of evidence to be taken into consideration by the group;
- (b) implementing a 'listen-reflect-speak' rule, allowing for structured silent reflection before deliberation to help participants who are less comfortable with a rational traditional deliberative debate approach.

1.2 Allow space within the assembly for people to express in ways that makes them feel most comfortable and which may not always be speaking up:

- (a) Create activities that allow for ways of participating and interacting that goes beyond rational or ordered argumentation;
- (b) Enable participants to use multiple means of expressing themselves during the in-person assembly (e.g. by providing pens and paper, and encouraging participants to express themselves via drawing, song lyrics, personal stories or stories of those close to them).

Activator 2: Understand how power operates in deliberative settings

Summary:

Power dynamics manifest in subtle ways during the deliberative process. They relate to who speaks first, who is interrupted, whose emotions are validated, and whose arguments are perceived as credible. A key task of the facilitators is to identify and mitigate these power dynamics, allowing participants to safely engage with each other and with the discussion across their differences.

Actions:

2.1. Facilitators were trained in key intersectionality concepts, including relational power and an understanding that individuals may occupy positions of relative privilege in one context while experiencing marginalisation in another. The training includes material on the qualities of intersectional inclusion, equality, and deliberation that form the foundation of the EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly.

2.2. Facilitators were trained in techniques that encourage deliberation as an inclusive process of collective reasoning rather than an adversarial contest.

Activator 3: Practise reflexivity

Summary:

Reflexivity is a particularly crucial aspect of the facilitators' role in this project and – arguably – in any project that deals with intersectionality. It requires that practitioners reflect how their own background and identities shape the process, uncover and interrupt their own unconscious biases and proactively seek feedback from those experiencing intersectional discrimination; remain conscious of how their position and status might prevent others from speaking up, and reflect at various points of the process how their own background identities shape the process.

Actions:

3.1. Facilitators engaged in positionality and privilege training and positionality exercises.

- (a) Facilitators engaged in positionality and privilege training during the session with Karen Bowlby.
- (b) Facilitators received training on positionality and privilege and acting reflexively in the context of small group deliberation at a training session delivered by Kathryn McCabe.
- (c) Facilitators engaged in a reflective and reflexive positionality exercise in advance of the pilot assemblies taking place (Appendix 3).

3.4. Assembly participants will engage in a positionality-related icebreaking activity using the 'Whiteboard' function on Zoom, during the first session of the local pilot citizens' assembly (Appendix 8). There was a three-fold purpose to designing this activity. The first was to create a connection between participants in a creative and informal way, allowing participants to feel comfortable with each other from the outset of the citizens' assembly. The second purpose was to invite reflection from participants on their positionality, allowing them and us to reveal diverse (or similar) backgrounds and identities in relation to intersectionality, at both the individual and group level. The final purpose was to allow participants to understand how privilege and power can affect deliberation and decision-making.

3.5. During the first session of the local pilot citizens' assembly participants will develop and prioritise ground rules for their participation in the Assembly, using the Whiteboard function on Zoom (Appendix 10). This approach furthers our emphasis on 'codesigning' the local pilot citizens' assembly alongside participants.

3.6 We have designed assembly activities in a way that brings out, and allows participants to engage with, the concept of intersectional discrimination. For example, during the second session of the local pilot citizens' assembly, participants will engage in an 'Mapping Activity' where they will reflect on the obstacles and difficulties that persons belonging to the intersection of marginalised groups may be facing in the community regarding housing issues (Appendix 11).

Further detail on various aspects of facilitator training can be found in Deliverable 4.2.

VII. Language

One of the key decisions that we have had to make in the design of the pilots was on the topic of language and **the potential to cater for multilingualism** in the three pilots. Our starting point in thinking about language was an acknowledgment that, as a result of EU integration and inter-EU migration waves, many EU residents' linguistic profile diverges from the old 'one nation, one language' model that was instrumental in national-building on the continent. To complicate matters, democratic participation at the national level in EU member states is mostly tied to citizenship, but increasingly more and more EU citizens reside in countries other than their country of origin - and by extension are not proficient in the national language(s). The EU has been facing charges of democratic deficit from its own citizens, and this issue is exacerbated significantly in the case of non-citizens. According to Eurostat 2024 statistics, nine percent of the EU's population (about 41 million people) are citizens of another country than the one where they reside - with three per cent being from another EU Member State and six percent from a non-EU country. The distribution between residents and non-residents is more unbalanced in larger metropolitan areas, such as the Austrian capital, Vienna. There, for example, 35% of the population are not Austrian citizens and are hence barred from voting in national and state elections. Zooming in on this cohort, over 33% of non-Austrians residing in Vienna are at risk of poverty, and as many as 70% of non-Austrian young men are at risk of poverty (Zur Lage der Nichtösterreicher*innen in Wien (2024)). These examples help to illustrate how layers of intersectionality overlap with language and citizenship matters.

This discussion on language is divided into four parts, as follows. First, we outline the theoretical implications of language-related questions for our debate on intersectional deliberation. Next, we outline the project's language-related research questions and hypotheses. Next, the discussion will be devoted to the lessons we learned in Work Package 3 about language-related concerns in previous citizens' assemblies, including a list of objectives inspired in lessons learned from these earlier assemblies. Finally, we will highlight the language-related approaches tied to each pilot citizens' assembly, while also linking each pilot to the respective set of objectives and hypotheses noted in the earlier discussion.

1. Theoretical Implications

There is no model of democracy or language policy deemed universally adequate and sufficient. Many traditional democracy theories (e.g., by Habermas and Dahl) are predicated on the

quintessentially European model of ‘one nation, one language’, in the sense that they require a single shared language to create a public sphere (Habermas) and to fulfil democratic criteria of access to information and active participation (Dahl). As for language policy, while many scholars will stress the expressive role of language and defend the need for multilingual language policies in democratic participation (e.g., Kraus, Grin, Shohamy), others will focus on the instrumental value of language instead, arguing for the use of *linguae francae* (today increasingly English) (e.g., van Parijs, Modiano).

Looking beyond the literature on language policy and turning to empirical data from the Special Eurobarometer 540 of 2024, 47% of respondents claimed to be able to have a conversation in English, while 27% of them rated their competence as ‘very good’. This means that roughly just under 13% of respondents could speak English well - though we must view these figures conservatively because they are self-reported. Out of these 13% of respondents, most were male, younger, well-educated individuals holding managerial positions and placed higher on the social ladder (Eurobarometer, 2024).

This means that, regardless of our project's theoretical affiliations, relying on **English as a lingua franca** of sorts in our citizens’ assemblies will privilege the cohort described above - the 13% who claim to speak English well. While designing the assemblies, practical considerations also influenced our understanding and our approach to the language policy that we applied. For instance, while an English-only pilot might be more easily workable in the context of the Colchester pilot, even though our sample from the University student community is predominantly multicultural,¹¹ we agreed as a group that it will be very challenging to recruit participants to an English-only Assembly in Cyprus, where the spoken day-to-day language is Greek. The challenge is naturally exacerbated for the transnational pilot, where we are not only looking to recruit persons residing across the EU, but also those that are deeply affected by housing issues, potentially including marginalised persons who are not proficient or confident in speaking in a language other than their native one. While acknowledging these challenges, normatively and theoretically, we adopt a more expressive notion of language in our project, valuing multilingualism and recognising the importance of language in democratic participation (in line with, e.g., Cordier 2025 and Verhasselt 2025). We also hope to illuminate classic democracy models from more contemporary angles, which today in Europe are inevitably multilingual.

¹¹ For more details see the discussion on the local pilot, below.

The following are the research questions on language that we will explore throughout the three pilots.

2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

In this context, our key research questions are as follows:

- a. How important is language in citizens' assemblies - and democratic participation more broadly?
- b. How are the participants' willingness to participate and engagement with the topic affected by the language policy of the citizens' assembly?
- c. How well can participants cope with an English-only language policy?

The two main hypotheses that will be tested in our pilots are as follows:

- a. Whether English as the EU's second first language suffices to accomplish intersectional deliberation.
- b. Whether to be intersectionally inclusive, democratic debate in the citizens' assemblies must accommodate the participants' multilingualism.

3. Lessons from Work Package 3

Data gathered within Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, and reported in Deliverable 3.3, helped us gain insights into language-related questions in past citizens' assemblies. One important - albeit unsurprising - conclusion is that assemblies taking place in officially monolingual nations (i.e., countries with a single official language, the majority of EU member states) rarely offer language services. In contrast, citizens' assemblies conducted in multilingual countries tend to offer language services in those languages, even though a strict territoriality principle is often observed - rather than a personality principle, whereby participants are accommodated in their language preferences regardless of the language or languages tied to the territory of the assembly.

Additional insights derived from Task 3.1 and Task 3.2 include the following. On the input stage, and specifically on recruitment, sampling and sortition, some past assemblies chose to recruit additional participants to double as interpreters. Some interviewees noted that accommodating language needs is difficult when there is a lack of information on potential participants' languages, making organisers have to guess based on potential participants' names. Some

assemblies used people from a certain linguistic community to recruit from that community, whereas others looked at a country's linguistic profile (statistics) to target those communities. Another important factor reported by some interviewees is that official invitation letters are often ignored, so targeting language communities by phoning some people who have not responded to the letter is a fruitful route. Further, adding a QR code to official invitation letters leading to a website / videos in the respective languages is another viable tool to include speakers of different languages to the national language. For some communities, childcare / financial compensation / having an accompanying person (i.e., someone there for support who is *not* participating) are also important.

Concerning the throughput stage, some assemblies reported the full use of artificial intelligence tools (AI) to translate materials with varying degrees of success. Some also worked with videos with subtitles, while others opted to have plenary sessions interpreted simultaneously (booths or on-stage) – but preferably making interpreters visible, to destigmatise any language-related issues. Some assemblies featured lectures in a given language with pre-prepared subtitles made available on tablets handed to the audience.

Notably, our interviewees reported that during the deliberation phase, whispering interpreting made some participants uncomfortable. Some assemblies chose to offer ad hoc language solutions on a case by case basis, whereas others used facilitators as interpreters. Some facilitators reported that collecting ideas in more than two or three languages is challenging, and others noted that it is difficult to implement simultaneous interpreting in small groups.

Some general insights from previous assemblies include the link between language, culture and catering. Often, during pre-assembly events or socialising events, there is a strong connection between the languages of the assembly and those of the participants, the cultural values upon which the assembly rests and the food offered at these events. Another important insight that transpired from our project interviews is a notion of **multilingualism as a barrier** and the **idealisation of monolingualism** as the optimal communication model (see Deliverable 3.3). Closely linked with this, some of the interviewees also reported feeling that language services (translation and interpreting) are a nuisance to be avoided.

What is more, evidence from our secondary evaluation data analysis showed that there were no stark divisions in participant experience based on language, which could suggest that the language support provided was largely successful. However, the results do show a small

variation in satisfaction and critical perception between the group of native and non-native speakers in that assembly.¹²

These insights helped us design our research questions and hypotheses outlined above. We have kept them in mind when determining the design elements of each of our pilot assemblies. While the pilot citizens' assemblies will help answer the research questions and test our hypotheses, we align ourselves with an expressive notion of language and have the following **considerations** in mind:

(1). There are significant gaps in research on multilingualism in citizens' assemblies. We intend to collect information - in the form of surveys, interviews and observers' notes - on this and publish our results. As such, specific questions on language accessibility were included both in our template recruitment survey (see Appendix 7), as well as in the surveys for the data collection on participants' experiences (see Section IX for the Evaluation Plan).

(2). Where relevant, we intend to normalise multilingualism and language services, as well as to make them visible. Any democratic initiative committed to intersectionality must consider the role of language and, in any case, individual multilingualism and complex language repertoires are increasingly common in the EU. Where possible, we will slow matters down in our pilots to prioritise multilingualism and quality over facile, superficial 'understanding' with suboptimal language practices that favour privileged participants. Where this is not possible or not done, we hope to gather important conclusions as to the importance of language in democratic debate.

(3). To the extent that it is possible, we intend to invest in language services and test less costly options - such as AI-generated tools. This serves a twofold purpose. On the one hand, assessing the effectiveness of these emerging tools in the area of language is an urgent task, particularly given our commitment to intersectional deliberation. On the other hand, finding effective, accessible and viable tools that keep data private and secure, but are less cost-intensive could be a game-changer in making citizens' assemblies more accessible and multilingual.

4. Overview of Language Policy in our Pilot Citizens' Assemblies

¹² See Deliverable 3.3 pp. 121-122.

Just as our pilot citizens' assemblies test different design choices and deliberation models, they will also adopt different approaches to language and language services, aiming to answer the above research questions, meet our objectives, and contribute to future citizens' assemblies and debates on democratic participation more broadly.

The local pilot followed an 'English as a lingua franca' approach and will hence test our first hypothesis above, namely 'English is the EU's second first language and suffices to accomplish intersectional deliberation'. In practice, this means that no translators or interpreters have been engaged for this pilot, nor will any materials or informative documents be made widely available in languages other than English, although some recruitment emails were sent in other languages e.g. to the Greek and French Student Societies/ student cohorts. In the same vein, our plan was that participation would only be possible in English, unless prospective participants explicitly request language services at the recruitment stage - in which case ad hoc measures would be put in place for that particular participant. At the recruitment stage, no participant requested language services to be able to participate in the assembly. Given the anticipated cohort of participants in the local pilot - namely students currently taking their programmes in English but stemming from many different linguacultural backgrounds - we expect the 'English-only' policy to potentially pose a hurdle for some. Objective (1) above will be pursued in this pilot to collect participants' perceptions in relation to language.

The national pilot will aim at testing the second hypothesis, namely that 'to be intersectionally inclusive, democratic debate in the citizens' assemblies must accommodate the participants' multilingualism'. Our plan is to achieve that by offering materials and informative documents in two languages: Greek and English, as well as by using AI generated tools complemented by the hiring interpreters to assist live during the events, mostly the on site session. By highlighting the role of multilingualism as per objectives (2) and (3) above, we hope to test a range of multilingual elements, from translated materials and translated subtitles and captions to live interpreting and multilingual deliberation.

The translational pilot, which is by nature our most linguistically complex one, will rely on online and AI-generated tools to enable multilingualism - in line with Objective 4 above. Because it is transnational and will take place solely online, this pilot offers a suitable ground for testing online tools that, at least in theory, preclude the need for human translations and interpreters. Testing these tools is important for the reasons noted earlier, namely because we need to appraise the

effectiveness of these tools as far as intersectional deliberation is concerned, and because we need less costly solutions for multilingual citizens' assemblies. In line with the national pilot, this pilot will primarily test the second hypothesis outlined above in that it will aim to adopt a multilingual modus operandi - albeit without necessarily relying on human translators and interpreters.

The numbers of translators and interpreters, the nature of their work and language combinations, as well as the number and type of online (including AI-generated) tools employed are currently under discussion and are predicated on the numbers and language profiles of participants. More details on this will follow in the subsequent Deliverables 4.3 and 4.4, which will report on the evaluation of the three pilots.

VIII. Online Deliberation

One of the areas of particular interest for our project is the way in which digital tools could enhance intersectional inclusion in transnational democratic processes. This section focuses on the role and use of online tools for the pilot assemblies, explaining the project's general approach towards online deliberation within the assembly.

1. An Assessment of Existing Practices Relating to Online Dimensions of Citizens' Assemblies

As citizens' assemblies increasingly incorporate digital elements, understanding the empirical evidence for designing online and hybrid formats has become essential for practitioners and policymakers. While deliberative democracy is spreading steadily across various levels of government in the last two decades (OECD 2020b, Paulis et al. 2020; Paulis et al. 2025; Eggers & Magni Berton 2026), the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of online deliberation methods for citizens' assemblies, forcing practitioners to adapt traditional face-to-face deliberative processes to digital environments (Verhasselt & Paulis 2025). This transition has generated substantial evidence on the effectiveness, challenges, and best practices of online deliberation (Curato et al. 2021; Paulis et al. 2025). According to OECD's data, online deliberation became the most frequently used medium for conducting deliberative processes in 2021, with 85% of OECD countries implementing government-wide online consultations (OECD 2022). Several of the interviewees, as well as the two assemblies that we examined for the secondary data analysis, in Deliverable 3.3 also operated with an online element in their assembly events.

Our project places special attention on the question of how information and communication technology (digitalisation) is used in the assemblies, particularly regarding the potential of online tools to enhance intersectional inclusion, equality, and deliberation in online and hybrid assemblies. We had deliberately chosen to exclude from our assemblies' design the fully in-person mode because we considered that the requirement for in-person presence over a sustained period raises barriers to participation, especially for those citizens that are already marginalised and likely to face exclusion from democratic processes. It was key, therefore,

during the micro-design phase to decide how to plan and organise the online aspect of the pilot in ways that catered to intersectionality considerations.

It was key, during the micro-design phase, to decide how to plan and organise the online aspect of the pilot in ways that catered to intersectionality considerations.

The shift to online formats revealed both opportunities and limitations. Research from the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission examining the Conference on the Future of Europe's digital platform emphasises that while online platforms can extend participatory processes to wider publics and offer new forms of participation, they work best when integrated into a broader citizen engagement strategy alongside in-person activities (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira 2025). While deliberative processes can be enhanced by the use of online affordances, other studies show that the use of digital platforms can be simply instrumental to the process of 'citizenwashing' policy-making (Petit & Oleari 2026).

In terms of positive externalities of the use of online platforms in deliberation, this **hybrid** approach¹³ ensures complementarity, continuity, and effective follow-up, addressing concerns about **digital exclusion** while maximising reach (Paulis et al. 2025). Research shows that digital platforms can potentially enhance deliberative quality, with early optimism suggesting online debates could improve civic engagement and discussion standards (Min 2007), though success depends heavily on **careful platform design** matched to deliberative tasks. Negative arguments highlight **persistent barriers** including unequal technology access, lack of participant representativeness, dominance by vocal individuals creating power imbalances, and prevalence of incivility leading to polarisation and unproductive discussions (Hofstra et al. 2023; Verhasselt & Paulis 2025).

Overall, empirical research shows mixed results, with deliberation quality highly dependent on contextual and platform-specific factors rather than any inherent superiority of digital spaces.

In more practical terms, Go Vocal's research on digital deliberation (2024) found that synchronous video discussions via platforms like Jitsi or Zoom can effectively mimic offline town

¹³ We use the word 'hybrid' throughout the deliverable to refer to a combination of online and in-person sessions, rather than giving participants the possibility to attend the same session either online or in person.

halls when complemented with **interactive methods** such as breakout sessions and voting tools. However, evaluations of online discussion forums have shown mixed results. Strandberg and Grönlund (2013) found that online deliberative experiments produced meaningful outcomes, while other studies reported lower deliberation quality in some contexts (Friess & Eilders 2015; Meylan-Stevenson et al. 2024).

A systematic analysis of 116 digital participatory tools revealed that while these platforms enhance information flow from citizens to government, they suffer from significant deficiencies in **disseminating accountability information back to citizens** (Shin et al., 2024). This represents a critical gap in the digital tool ecosystem that undermines the full potential of online assemblies. **Selection bias** presents another challenge. Only citizens with appropriate technology and digital literacy can participate in fully online assemblies, potentially excluding segments of the population without reliable internet access or technical expertise (Bürgerrat, 2021). This creates what researchers call ‘systemic bias in participation’ that hybrid meetings alone cannot fully address (National League of Cities, 2022).

Moreover, recent research has shown that AI can expand these participatory opportunities in multiple ways. One straightforward application involves AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants, which can guide citizens through formal participation procedures, answer policy-related queries, or adapt official documents to different linguistic and accessibility needs (Shin et al. 2022). By streamlining these interactions, AI tools may help reach underserved communities, thereby lowering the threshold for civic engagement (Androutsopoulou et al. 2019). At the same time, **automated systems** that assemble or summarise policy information can empower citizens to make more informed contributions to deliberations and consultations (Landemore 2024; Argyle et al. 2023).

More specifically, online deliberative citizens’ assemblies have recently seen the progressive introduction of automated moderation systems using advanced natural language processing (NLP) algorithms (Behrent et al. 2025). Such systems enable the identification of argumentative patterns, the classification of interventions, and the automatic filtering of offensive or irrelevant messages (Guridi et al. 2025). Similarly, topic modelling and semantic clustering algorithms can process thousands of textual contributions, identifying patterns of convergence and divergence, and generating coherent summaries that reflect the diversity of opinions expressed by participants (Hadfi et al. 2023; Novelli et al. 2025). AI tools bring to online deliberative processes the capacity to recognise latent consensus and areas of conflict in the discussions, allowing to

assess which issues generate the greatest interest, support, or debate among participants, without the need for direct intervention from facilitators. Furthermore, research shows that AI tools are less likely than human moderators to marginalise minority positions in processes dominated by vocal majorities or internal hierarchies (McKinney 2024).

Additionally, recommendation systems can facilitate connections between participants with shared interests, creating micro-spaces for interaction which, when networked together, enhance processes of broader consensus-building and the formation of internal majorities (Novelli et al. 2025). This does not imply that AI would replace human deliberation, but rather foster it by providing a more precise mapping of the argumentative landscape and generating processes that reflect more faithfully the concerns of the citizens' assembly participants (Tessler et al. 2024). Moreover, if automatic fact-checking systems powered by NLP techniques are implemented within online deliberative fora, factual claims made during debates or digital consultations can be verified in real time by comparing them against databases of verified information, while flagging potential misinformation or inaccuracies (Novelli et al. 2024).

Overall, harnessing AI to facilitate user-friendly, inclusive communication channels has the potential to strengthen democratic legitimacy by enhancing both the breadth and depth of public participation (McKinney 2024). Thus, AI is increasingly expected to be a catalyst for democratic innovation, particularly in the context of deliberative procedures (Small et al. 2024). By harnessing advanced techniques in text analysis, summarisation, and generation, AI-powered platforms can help synthesise large volumes of information, support fact-checking, and encourage civility and mutual understanding among diverse participants (Tessler 2024). These tools can also map and aggregate different viewpoints in real time, thereby identifying areas of consensus or disagreement more efficiently (Tsai et al. 2024). As a result, AI not only streamlines the deliberation process, thus making it more inclusive and accessible, but also enhances the quality of collective decision-making by offering data-driven insights and personalised feedback to participants (Ma et al. 2025; Fishkin et al. 2025).

Recent work, however, flagged **risks around bias and transparency** in using AI in citizens' assemblies (for briefings, drafting, facilitation), and recent evidence of an 'AI penalty' finds that participants rate AI-facilitated deliberation lower than human-led formats and that they are less willing to take part, suggesting public scepticism that designers must address (Jungherr & Rauchfleisch 2025).

It is against the above background that we have considered the use and potential of online spaces in our pilots' design, especially when it comes to the input (i.e. how to utilise online spaces for deliberation to make for a more inclusive assembly) and the throughput stage (i.e. how reduce barriers to the online deliberation environment of an assembly). Our choice to combine online with in-person elements for the local and national pilot, and to try an online-only version for the transnational pilot was intentional. As seen from the literature above, the integration of online and offline elements represents a critical design consideration for inclusive deliberation.

1.1. Best practices for integrating online and offline citizens' assemblies

Research on hybrid participation models during the pandemic period provides valuable insights on integrating online and offline elements in an assembly. A recent study examined five cases in the Netherlands and found that forms of participation that were conducted simultaneously online and offline often fell short in providing opportunities for inclusive interaction. The study recommends **sequential use** of different media types: use media such as webinars for enhancing access to participation, followed by richer interactive platforms and in-person meetings for deeper citizen interactions (Meijer et al., 2023).

The DemocracyNext Assembly Guide, based on OECD Good Practice Principles developed from analysing over 700 citizens' assemblies worldwide, emphasises that the essential principles making assemblies effective remain constant across formats: representative sortition-based selection and adequate time for learning and deliberation. For hybrid formats, the guide stresses the importance of maintaining these core elements while thoughtfully adapting facilitation methods (DemocracyNext 2024).

Evidence from assemblies that transitioned online mid-process, such as the French and UK Climate Citizens' Assemblies, demonstrates that prior face-to-face meetings significantly facilitate online collaboration. Participants who met in person first before shifting online reported more comfortable and productive virtual interactions (Bürgerrat 2021).

Research on hybrid citizens' assemblies reveals nuanced insights about combining digital and physical formats. The German Bürgerrat's evaluation of online deliberative assemblies (2021) found that **participants valued having an initial face-to-face session** to establish relationships before transitioning online. **Conversely**, some participants found benefits in the

online format. One member reported: 'More people spoke in my online discussions and they may not have been as afraid of negative reactions from other participants as they are in a face-to-face meeting' (Bürgerrat, 2021). This suggests that digital formats may reduce certain social barriers to participation.

1.2. Existing suggestions for effective online deliberation via Zoom and similar platforms

Platform-specific best practices have emerged from extensive experimentation with video conferencing tools during the pandemic. Gerwin's practitioner perspective on designing online citizens' assemblies emphasises several critical factors (Gerwin 2018). First, online sessions should be relatively short, maximum 1.5 hours per session, to maintain engagement and prevent digital fatigue. Sessions can be organised 3-4 times per week, spread over approximately two months depending on issue complexity (Gerwin 2021). Of course, such an approach involves inherent trade offs that may limit the ability of certain social groups to participate, thereby potentially leading to (unintended) exclusionary effects.

In terms of practical recommendations, the literature suggests that if more time is needed for complex deliberation, multiple shorter sessions could be scheduled rather than extending single sessions beyond the recommended duration (OECD 2020b). It is also crucial to build in substantially more time for coordination and synchronisation than would be required in-person. Technical issues, platform navigation difficulties, and the need for explicit instructions on what might be intuitive in face-to-face settings all require additional time allocation. It is thus crucial to plan for at least 15-20% more time than the same activity would require offline (mySociety 2020).

Synchronous, facilitated small-group video deliberation is the closest online analogue to in-person deliberation: experimental comparisons indicate that organised online deliberation can produce many of the same 'core' outcomes as face-to-face formats (e.g., knowledge gains, efficacy, willingness to participate), provided the process is structured and moderated (Min 2007). Evidence from a controlled comparison of face-to-face vs online citizen deliberation finds that online deliberation is feasible, but **more sensitive to design features** such as moderation, turn-taking rules, and technical reliability (Grönlund et al. 2009).

Breakout room functionality has proven essential for quality deliberation. Guidelines on online facilitation practices consistently recommends groups of 7-8 participants per breakout room,

with both a lead facilitator and co-facilitator present (Go Vocal. 2024). These small groups should follow the same good practices used in person: **clear instructions** provided both verbally and in written form (via chat or collaborative documents), assigned roles to ensure equal participation, and adequate time allocation of 5-15 minutes depending on task complexity.¹⁴

The facilitation literature emphasises the importance of **technical preparation and support** (DemocracyNext 2024). **Facilitators** should practice with all platform features before the actual assembly, create **clear technical guides** for participants, and designate **technical support staff** to handle connectivity issues and platform navigation questions. The broadcast message feature should be used strategically to provide time warnings and additional instructions to breakout groups (OECD 2022)¹⁵.

The literature underlines that the facilitation team for online sessions requires different roles and preparation than traditional assemblies. Designate a lead facilitator for plenary sessions, but ensure each breakout room has both a facilitator and an observer. The co-facilitator can focus on note-taking, monitoring participation equity, managing the chat function, and troubleshooting technical issues, allowing the lead facilitator to concentrate on guiding the substantive discussion (mySociety 2020; Go Vocal. 2024).

Complementary tools enhance online deliberation quality. Collaborative documents (Google Docs, Google Slides, Zoom Whiteboard) allow real-time co-creation and provide facilitators with visibility into group progress. Visual collaboration platforms like MURAL, MIRO or SLIDO support complex group work and help participants feel more connected despite physical distance. These tools should be introduced and tested before substantive deliberation sessions begin (Meylan-Stevenson et al. 2024).¹⁶

In addition, a key empirical finding from online forum experiments is that **information architecture** is key for online deliberation sessions to succeed. In online settings, deliberative principles (clear norms, justification requirements, balanced information, and facilitation) outperform generic ‘comment thread’ conditions on deliberative outputs (Strandberg 2015). This entails that deliberative quality improves when platforms and rules are explicitly ‘designed for

¹⁴ See:

<https://teaching.cornell.edu/teaching-resources/online-teaching/making-zoom-sessions-inclusive/zoom-breakout-room-tips>

¹⁵ https://www.trainingforchange.org/training_tools/zoom-breakouts/

¹⁶ <https://voltagecontrol.com/blog/get-the-most-out-of-zoom-for-virtual-facilitation/>

deliberation', not just for discussion. This seems to confirm previous research showing that **institutional design** (selection, briefing materials, moderation, and decision rules) is a **main driver of quality** online, just as offline (Caluwaerts et al. 2023).

Moreover, online settings seem to increase risks of cognitive overload and unequal comprehension because participants cannot as easily rely on informal peer-to-peer clarification (Hofstra et al. 2023). Practitioner-evaluations and methodological reviews show that it is crucial to maintain **staged agendas** (first learn about the topic, then deliberate, then decide), **frequent recaps**, and **accessible handouts** on both the process and the core topic to sustain the discussion and group interaction (National Centre for Social Research (NatCen) 2021).

Regarding input from experts during online deliberative sessions, a recent study of an online mini-public examining expert hearings finds that expert input can shift perceptions and views, but the effects depend on how hearings are structured and how Q&A is facilitated (Leino et al. 2022). The implication for online citizens' assemblies is that experts should be briefed for clarity, Q&A should be curated to protect diversity of views (not only the most confident speakers), and moderators should enforce symmetry across viewpoints.

1.3. Addressing the digital divide and accessibility challenges

The **digital divide** remains a fundamental challenge for inclusive online deliberation (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025). Literature emphasises that digital inclusion encompasses more than basic internet access, it requires affordable data, appropriate devices, and sufficient digital literacy skills as demonstrated by studies on second-level digital divide (Hargittai 2003; Pérez-Escolar & Canet 2023; Lythreitis et al. 2022). The gap disproportionately affects older persons, persons with disabilities, rural populations, and economically marginalised communities (Tsatsou 2022).

Recent research on digital democratic innovations shows that while scaling up participation through digital means offers opportunities for increasing inclusiveness, it simultaneously risks exacerbating exclusion due to factors such as the digital divides, varying familiarity levels with technology, power imbalances and accessibility barriers (Jimenez-Pernett et al. 2023; Mikhaylovskaya 2024, Lironi & Demofonti 2024). Studies emphasise that equality, understood

as freedom from domination, and equity of diverse perspectives, must be central to deliberative digital democratic innovations design (Beauvais & Baechtiger 2016, Allegretti 2021).

Potential practical mitigation strategies include providing **asynchronous participation options** for those with unreliable internet connections, offering pre-session technical training, using a single consistent platform throughout the process to build familiarity, and ensuring human technical support is available during all sessions (Birchall & Coleman 2023; Mikhaylovskaya 2024). The recent Go Vocal guide on facilitating digital deliberation recommends these approaches specifically for projects seeking to engage citizens consciously despite the digital divide.¹⁷

There are several examples of digital platforms designed for or assisting citizens' deliberation, but the Future of Europe digital platform represents one of the most studied and most effective cases, particularly notable for its success in facilitating transnational dialogue across the European Union's diverse linguistic and cultural landscape (Ballangé 2023; Oleart 2023; Cordier 2025). The 'Future of Europe digital platform' refers to the multilingual hub for the Conference on the Future of Europe (2021-2022), a major EU initiative allowing citizens to share ideas on shaping Europe's future, covering topics like climate, digital transformation, and democracy, leading to concrete recommendations for EU institutions (Galende-Sánchez 2025; Lironi & Demofonti 2024).

The European Commission's Joint Research Centre report on the Conference on the Future of Europe digital platform provides several key takeaways directly relevant to EU-CIEMBLY. First, **multilingualism** is essential when engaging citizens across Europe, requiring **robust translation** systems and careful attention to linguistic equity. Second, transparency, accessibility, and inclusivity must be prioritised in **platform design**, with particular attention to creating safe spaces where participants feel protected from those who might undermine constructive dialogue. Moderation is fundamental to promoting fruitful debates (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025).

The report emphasises that **diverse interaction mechanisms**, such as submitting proposals, commenting, and voting, help engage a diverse and extensive range of participants. Effective and robust analysis systems, potentially AI-driven, are crucial for inferring the most salient contributions, providing insights into citizens' concerns, and helping policymakers identify areas

¹⁷ See: <https://www.govocal.com/blog/how-to-facilitate-digital-deliberation>

of agreement and disagreement on complex issues. These findings underscore the importance of both technical infrastructure and deliberate process design (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025).

Recent deliberative initiatives have begun integrating AI to enhance deliberation processes, especially at EU level. Platforms like those of make.org employ AI-powered tools to analyse citizen contributions and identify common ground. National and EU institutions have experimented with AI-assisted deliberation in (European) Citizen panels to process large volumes of citizen input and synthesise policy recommendations. Examples include the 2023 European Citizens' Panel on Virtual Worlds, organised by the European Commission, the 2024 Citizen Panel on Artificial Intelligence organised by the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU, and the 2025 Multi-Financial Framework or Intergenerational Fairness Citizens' Panels, (Petit & Olear 2026).¹⁸

Overall, previous studies show that **technical access and reliability** repeatedly appear as binding constraints: poor connectivity, weak devices, and lack of digital confidence can depress participation and skew who speaks (Sandover et al. 2020). OECD guidance therefore recommends selecting digital tools with attention to digital divides and resourcing the human support required to run them (OECD 2021). Equity requires 'full-stack' inclusion: devices, connectivity, training, and real-time tech support.

Based on the abovementioned review of the scientific and grey literature, empirical research also suggests that some actions or methods do not work well in online deliberation. Systematic reviews of online deliberation research consistently emphasise that civility, reciprocity, and reason-giving are not automatic online; they require rules and facilitation (Caluwaert et al. 2023). In practice, online spaces without strong facilitation often over-represent the most digitally fluent and verbally dominant participants.

What is more, over-reliance on large plenaries online increases fatigue and reduces genuine deliberation. Long plenaries are a known online anti-pattern: they increase passivity and 'Zoom fatigue' and make it harder for moderators to manage equitable participation. Evaluations of online deliberative methods recommend pushing substantive deliberation into small rooms and using plenaries mainly for orientation, expert sessions, and synthesis (National Centre for Social Research (NatCen) 2021).

¹⁸ https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/european-citizens-panels_en

1.4. Summary of best practices for integrating online and in-person sessions of citizens' assemblies

Most importantly, It would appear from the above literature review that a robust 'hybrid' design is typically sequenced, not fully simultaneous. A hybrid citizens' assembly could thus be structured in three different, sequential phases:

Phase 1 – *Online onboarding and learning sessions* (asynchronous and short synchronous). Online tools can be used for recruitment communications, consent, accessibility checks, and pre-reading of relevant materials. Learning modules should be kept short, based multimedia tools, and repeated (brief video explainers and written summaries). OECD principles emphasise matching tools to participation methods and resourcing inclusion (OECD 2020a, 2022).

Phase 2 – *In-person deliberation*. Evidence and practice-oriented reviews suggest that the most effective deliberation experiences benefit from in-person time, where social cues and informal interaction improve trust and reduce misinterpretation (Willis et al. 2022). An in-person session should therefore be organised after the online onboarding sessions.

Phase 3 – *Online deliberation for continuity and iteration*. After the in-person sessions, online sessions can sustain momentum, by iterating on draft recommendations, testing wording, and preparing final voting or decisions (OECD 2022).

It is crucial to ensure strong continuity mechanisms between online and offline elements. Therefore, consistent visual materials, facilitation teams, and collaborative platforms across both formats should be used. Organisers should brief participants explicitly on what will remain the same and what will change as formats shift, thereby reducing uncertainty and maintaining momentum in the deliberative process.

2. Facilitating Intersectional Online Citizens' Assembly Pilots

Having reviewed existing practices concerning online aspects of citizens' assemblies, this section now provides practical, actionable recommendations based on existing evidence and practical guidelines for facilitators leading online sessions of the EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies. Each recommendation addresses a specific challenge of online facilitation with concrete solutions that have been or can be implemented in preparation of and during the EU-CIEMBLY pilots. We have pointed out those recommendations that we have implemented for the Colchester pilot and we plan to implement for the Cyprus pilot, both of which follow the format of online - in person - online. It should also be noted here that the choice to sequence the sessions in an **online - in person - online format** was intentional, as we predicted that having the first meeting online would reduce barriers to participation for those participants that may not be used to taking part in such events, may be more hesitant to speak up in front of strangers, and may have difficulties with available time or transport means.

The institutional design of online spaces is also particularly relevant for the transnational pilot, which will be held entirely online to best enable transnational participation. This format was selected to maximise accessibility and feasibility given the potentially very different places of residence of the participants, while maintaining methodological coherence with the project's broader objectives of intersectional inclusion and experimentation with deliberative formats.

Holding the assembly online offers several advantages, including removing the need for travel and reducing the logistical and financial burden on participants (and the project, given travel and accommodation expenses would need to be covered for an inclusive approach) - particularly those with caring responsibilities, disabilities, or insecure employment situations. It is also an environmentally friendly option considering the travelling requirements that a transnational face-to-face assembly would require. The online format will also hold comparative value to the other pilots, which will be in hybrid formats, and provide an opportunity to experiment with intersectional facilitation in digital spaces, enabling the project to explore how format mediates intersectional inclusion and deliberative outcomes.

Conducting the transnational pilot entirely online also comes with limitations and challenges. Most significantly, those with lower levels of digital competence, internet access, or inappropriate devices will face increased barriers to participation. These barriers are likely to

disproportionately affect participants who are already structurally marginalised, such as those on low incomes. In addition, extended online engagement can lead to fatigue, especially amongst participants not accustomed to sustained virtual discussion. Unlike in-person processes, where social energy and non-verbal cues can sustain interaction and build momentum, there is a risk that online environments may hinder informal connection and reduce assembly cohesion.

To address these challenges, several strategic design choices have been taken. During the recruitment phase, participants will be screened for digital access and ability (see the participant registration survey in Appendix 6). Those identified as requiring assistance will receive tailored support in the lead up to the assembly. The assembly will be held across a maximum of four sessions, each limited to a maximum of three hours, with frequent breaks and ongoing technical support lines. Facilitators will receive specialised training on online intersectional facilitation, including how to recognise and address signs of disengagement in online settings.

What follows is a short summary of best practices identified by the literature for guaranteeing the effective and smooth running of hybrid citizens' assemblies regarding various stages of the process.

2.1. Pre-session technical preparation and familiarisation

It might seem trivial, but it is crucial that all facilitators are familiar with online tools to avoid undermining participant confidence and wasting valuable deliberation time with troubleshooting during sessions (OECD 2022; mySociety 2020). To ensure that all facilitators are familiar with chosen online tools and that technical issues do not disrupt online activities, existing guides and literature suggest practical recommendations (Ercan et al. 2025). We implemented these together with the following actions, during the design and preparation for the Colchester pilot:

- Conduct at least two full technical rehearsals and onboarding with the organising team and the complete facilitation team before the first pilot session. Simulate the entire session including breakout rooms, screen sharing, collaborative documents, and interpretation channels.
- Have a designated person to create breakout rooms, run online activities e.g. on Whiteboard, broadcast messages, manage waiting rooms, share screens, use polls, and help with emergency troubleshooting.

- Assign one person as ‘technical lead’ who becomes the platform expert and can guide other facilitators. This person should join sessions 30 minutes early to test all functions.
 - Provide simple, user-friendly instructions to participants on how to use zoom and the various functionalities, in the format of a Participants’ Booklet circulated in advance of the first pilot session (Appendix 7).

2.2. Recreating social connection and informal interaction

Online sessions eliminate the informal ‘hallway conversations’, pre-session mingling, and spontaneous social bonding that naturally occur in face-to-face assemblies. This might reduce trust-building and make discussion and deliberation feel transactional (García 2023). To ensure that social connections are maintained to a sufficient extent even during online sessions of citizens’ assembly pilots, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (OECD 2022):

- Open the virtual room 15 minutes before the official start time with a clear message: ‘join early for informal chat!’ Have facilitators present to welcome arrivals and encourage casual conversation. Play background music if culturally appropriate.
- Create ‘Coffee Break Rooms’, during 10-15 minute breaks, divide participants into random groups of 4-5 in breakout rooms with no agenda except socialising. Announce: ‘these are informal spaces, chat about anything!’. Facilitators should not join these rooms.
- End each session five minutes early and invite participants to stay for ‘optional social time’ where anyone who wishes can remain and chat informally. Explicitly state this is optional to avoid pressuring those with tight schedules.

2.3. Effective online icebreakers and community building

Standard in-person icebreakers often fail online (Go Vocal 2024). Activities requiring movement do not work, and going around a large group verbally takes too long and becomes tedious on video. To accommodate the limitations of online platforms affordances, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (mySociety 2020):

- Use ‘Speed Meeting Rounds’ in the first session: pairs of participants spend three minutes in breakout rooms introducing themselves using a structured prompt (‘share

- your name, where you are from, and one hope you have for this assembly'). After three minutes, randomly reassign pairs for another round. Do 3-4 rounds so each person meets multiple others.
- Try 'visual introductions': ask participants to share one object from their immediate surroundings that represents something about them or their connection to the assembly topic. This is quick, engaging, and creates memorable connections.
 - Use Zoom annotations/reactions creatively: 'Put a 👍 if you have participated in a public consultation before, a ❤️ if this is your first time'. This creates quick engagement without requiring everyone to speak.
 - Create a shared collaborative slide deck, MIRO board or SLIDO page where participants add their names, locations, and one word describing how they are feeling. Leave this visible periodically throughout sessions to reinforce community.

In order to strengthen the pilots' intersectionality focus, we intentionally included an icebreaker acknowledging diverse experiences and inviting reflexivity. As explained above, and also found in Appendix 8, such an online icebreaking activity with a focus on positionality/privilege has been designed by our team for testing in the local pilot citizens' assembly, with lessons to be drawn on the effectiveness of this exercise for the subsequent pilots.

2.4. Managing camera usage inclusively

Requiring cameras-on creates barriers for participants with poor internet, privacy concerns, self-consciousness about home environments, or accessibility needs (OECD 2022). However, allowing cameras-off can reduce engagement and make facilitation difficult. To balance these two conflicting needs and guaranteeing effective communication, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (García 2023):

- Establish a flexible camera policy: 'please keep cameras on during small group discussions and when you are speaking in plenary; cameras are optional during presentations and your own thinking time'. Explain the reasoning: seeing faces helps connection but video can be exhausting.
- Explicitly normalise camera breaks: 'it is fine to turn your camera off if you need a visual break, just let us know you are still here via chat or thumbs up reaction'. Model this by occasionally turning off your own camera during presentations.

- Address privacy concerns proactively, for instance by demonstrating how virtual backgrounds work, by explaining how to blur backgrounds, and by ensuring participants know that these features exist. Offer technical support to set these up.
- If the pilot design allows it, for those who cannot or prefer not to use cameras, encourage use of profile pictures and active chat/reaction participation. Explicitly validate: ‘we value your voice and participation regardless of camera use’.
- If during breakout rooms someone switches their camera off, the facilitator should check in verbally (‘can you hear us okay? want to share your thoughts on this?’) to ensure they are engaged and feel included.

2.5. Online voting and decision-making mechanisms

Physical voting methods (raising hands, moving around the room, sticky dots) do not necessarily translate well online (García 2023). Digital voting can feel impersonal and lacks the visibility of collective decision-making. To guarantee the effectiveness and transparency of online voting processes, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (Ercan et al. 2025; OECD 2022):

- Use SLIDO or Zoom’s native polling feature for quick vibe/sentiment poll during group discussions and non-binding votes on selected topics. Create polls in advance with clear questions and options. Share results immediately to foster collective awareness.
- For more complex prioritisation or ranking, use collaborative tools like Mentimeter, MIRO, or SLIDO that show results visually in real-time. This creates the collective experience of seeing preferences emerge together.
- Make voting visible and deliberative. After votes are cast, discuss the distribution and first results: ‘we see 60% support this option, let’s hear from those who voted differently. What are your concerns?’. This mimics the discussion that happens when people see physical distributions in in-person settings.
- For consensus-building, allow for the use of a ‘thumbs’ system via reactions (👍 strong support, 🤔 can live with it, 🙄 serious concerns). Ask those with concerns to speak. This is faster than individual verbal responses, but still creates dialogue.
- Ensure voting accessibility by announcing votes verbally, by showing them in chat, and by giving adequate time to process instructions and cast the vote. Ask: ‘has

everyone who wants to vote had a chance to do so?'. Accommodate those needing assistance from facilitators or administrative/technical support.

For the local pilot citizens' assembly, we will use online voting at two stages, namely to prioritise the ground rules during the first session and to select the final recommendations during the third session. Our intention is to make use of the Zoom Whiteboard for voting purposes as this allows for prioritisation and for participants to cast more than one vote for a single option, allowing for an assessment of the 'strength' of their views on a particular recommendation for example. Using a single platform also has the advantage of avoiding unnecessary complexity and confusion during the session.

2.6. Technical setup and support infrastructure

Technical issues disproportionately affect participants with limited digital literacy, older devices, or unreliable internet, often those from marginalised communities (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025; Verhasselt & Paulis 2025). Without proactive support, these participants may drop out. To sustain engagement from participants with different backgrounds, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (Go Vocal 2024):

- Create a simple, visual 'how to join' guide with screenshots and circulate this at least 3 days before the first online session. Include information on how to download/access Zoom and any other platform used in the session, how to test audio/video, how to join via web browser if the app does not work, and a phone number to call for help. We integrated this into a participant's booklet for distribution in advance of each pilot citizens' assembly (see Appendix 7).
- Establish a dedicated technical support hotline (phone and WhatsApp/Signal) available from 30 minutes before each session until 15 minutes after it ends. Staff this with patience, (if possible multilingual) support people, and not the facilitators.
- Assign one facilitator/person as 'tech monitor'/'technical lead' during sessions whose only job is watching for technical issues: frozen screens, people stuck in waiting rooms, audio problems, chat messages saying 'I can't hear'. They handle these immediately while others facilitate content.
- Provide device/data support if budget allows, as for instance offer to lend tablets or provide mobile data stipends to participants who need them. Make this available discreetly through individual outreach, not public announcements that might cause

embarrassment. We integrated a question in our recruitment survey for the Colchester pilot, asking interested participants if they had any difficulty participating online, such as lack of a suitable device, data plan etc. This would have allowed us to deal with any difficulties on a case-by-case basis. No participant reported such difficulties.

- Have a 'Plan B' for connectivity issues: if someone repeatedly has problems, arrange for them to join by phone for audio only while viewing shared materials sent via email/WhatsApp. Ensure they can still participate meaningfully.

2.7. Combating Zoom fatigue and maintaining engagement

Video conferencing is cognitively and physically exhausting (Li & Yee 2023). Participants experience eye strain, difficulty concentrating, and mental fatigue much faster than during in-person sessions. Sessions longer than 90 minutes often see dramatic engagement drop-off (García 2023). To prevent and/or counterbalance this, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations:

- If possible, limit session length to 90 minutes maximum. Structure as: 10 min arrival/settling, 30 min content block, 10 min break, 30 min content block, 10 min wrap-up. Never run over time, respect participants' schedules and energy.
- Vary activity types every 15-20 minutes: presentation → small group discussion → individual reflection → plenary conversation. This variation prevents monotony and engages different cognitive processes.
- Build in 'screen-break moments': invite participants to stand, stretch, look out a window, or close their eyes for 60 seconds during transitions. Say: 'look away from your screen and stretch, we will resume in one minute'. This acknowledges physical needs.
- Use 'gallery view' strategically: during small group discussions, ask participants to switch to gallery view so they see everyone. During presentations, suggest 'speaker view' to reduce visual complexity. Explicitly guide these switches.
- Schedule breaks generously, meaning that a 10-minute break means 10 full minutes, not '5 minutes to return'. Use countdown timers visible on screen, and start the second half only when most participants have returned, rather than penalising those who took the full break.

2.8. Ensuring equitable voice and preventing domination

Online formats can amplify existing power dynamics. Those comfortable with technology, those with higher educational attainment levels and or/ political sophistication levels, confident speakers, and native language speakers may dominate the discussion (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025). Those less comfortable may become invisible, and less prone to participate in the discussion, especially without cameras. To try to compensate for these underlying dynamics, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (Ercan et al. 2025):

- Use structured turn-taking in plenary by requiring the use of the ‘raised hand’ feature, or a typed list in chat of who wants to speak. Facilitators should call on people in order, explicitly: ‘next we will hear from Maria, then Thomas, then Aisha’. This prevents interruptions and ensures quieter voices are heard. Based on previous experience, we will advise facilitators to keep an eye out for those raising their hand ‘physically’ as participants may be unable to find the ‘raise hand’ function on Zoom.
- In breakout rooms, assign within the group an ‘equity monitor’ role whose job is ensuring everyone contributes, and try to trigger contributions by inviting participants to speak: ‘let’s hear from people we have not heard from yet, for example [name], what is your perspective?’.
- Offer multiple modes of contribution: speaking in plenary, speaking in small groups, writing in chat, writing in collaborative documents, or private messages to facilitators. Explicitly say: ‘you can contribute in whatever way feels comfortable, all forms of participation are valued’. The presenter should make an active effort to “bring the chat inputs / conversation into the plenary room” e.g. by repeating or integrating the chat input into the discussion.
- Use ‘silent brainstorming’ before discussions: give everyone two minutes to write their thoughts in a shared document or private notes before opening discussion. This prevents the first speaker from anchoring everyone’s thinking and gives less confident speakers time to formulate ideas.

2.9. Managing collaborative documents and asynchronous work

Synchronous video sessions are just one part of online deliberation, and without careful management of shared documents and asynchronous spaces for contributing, collective work could fragment and some participants may end up being left behind (mySociety 2020). To allow

access to asynchronous spaces for collaboration, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (OECD 2022; Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025):

- Create clear, consistent document structure: one folder with clearly labelled files for each session ('Session 1 - Background Materials', 'Session 2 - Breakout Notes', etc.). Share access at the start and do not change the organisation mid-process.
- Use templates for collaborative work: create Google Doc or Zoom Whiteboard or MIRO templates with clear prompts, space for each person to contribute, and instructions at the top. This structures participation and prevents blank-page paralysis.
- Establish clear norms for asynchronous work: 'between sessions, please review the shared notes from your breakout group and add any reflections in the text. This should take 15-20 minutes'. Give specific time expectations and deadlines.
- Monitor the contribution, but do not pressure: check who has accessed documents between sessions. For those who have not accessed the documents, send a friendly individual reminder: 'we would value your input on [document], can we help you access it or answer questions?'. Address barriers rather than assuming disinterest.
- Synthesise and report back: at each session's start, briefly summarise asynchronous contributions: 'Between sessions, several people added ideas about [topic], let me highlight a few themes we are seeing'. This validates asynchronous work and keeps everyone informed.

2.10. Adapting deliberative methods for online environments

Traditional deliberative techniques (think-pair-share, world café, fishbowl discussions) require adaptation for online formats, as direct translation often fails (Rosa & Guimaraes Pereira, 2025). To effectively adapt deliberation processes to online settings, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations (OECD 2022):

- Adapt 'World Café' digitally: participants rotate through 3-4 different breakout room 'stations', each addressing a different question. Assign a 'table host' who stays at each station to welcome new groups and summarise previous discussions. Use 15-minute rotations.
- For consensus-building processes, use a visual tool (MIRO, SLIDO, Whiteboard etc.) where participants place sticky notes along a spectrum (strongly agree →

strongly disagree). Make this collaborative and visible. Then discuss clusters and outliers.

- Create ‘silent reflection’ periods: after a discussion or presentation, give 3-5 minutes of true silence where everyone mutes and reflects individually, perhaps writing notes. This intentional pause mimics the natural processing time that happens informally in-person.
- Use the chat strategically: for brainstorming, ask everyone to simultaneously type ideas in chat on a signal (‘in two minutes, post one idea for [topic], ready, go!’). This creates rapid collective input without turn-taking constraints. Save the chat log for later synthesis.

2.11. Supporting facilitators’ wellbeing and collaboration

Online facilitation is mentally demanding. Facilitators must manage technology, read non-verbal cues through small video squares, monitor multiple communication channels simultaneously, and maintain energy, all while focusing on content and group dynamics (mySociety 2020). To guarantee the wellbeing of facilitators, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations:

- Have co-facilitators so you can trade off leading discussions, managing technology, monitoring chat, and handling unexpected issues. Even short sessions need a minimum of two facilitators. We intend to adopt this approach insofar as possible, but due to the size of the team and the need for observers, there will be one facilitator in small break out rooms, for example.
- Establish a clear role division: before each session, decide who leads the plenary, who manages breakout rooms, who monitors technical issues, who handles timekeeping. Write this down and keep it visible during the session. Rotate roles across sessions to prevent burnout. We have done this in a detailed “Roll-out Plan” that was made available to all team members involved prior to the first assembly session
- Schedule facilitator de-briefs: after each session, take some time with the facilitation team to discuss what worked, what did not work, who seemed disengaged, and what needs adjustment. Keep brief written notes. In order to allow for a deeper reflection, we held de-brief meetings the morning after each session.

- Build in facilitator breaks: if sessions run longer than 60 minutes, switch lead facilitators midway. The person stepping back can turn off their camera, step away from the screen for a few minutes, and return refreshed.
- Create a facilitator support system: establish a private chat or WhatsApp group for the facilitation team where you can quickly ask questions, request backup, or share concerns during sessions without disrupting the participant experience.

2.12. Awareness of overlapping barriers in online facilitation

Online participation barriers often overlap, which has consequences for intersectionality: older participants may have less digital literacy and more accessibility needs; migrants may face language barriers and unreliable housing situations affecting connectivity; women with care responsibilities may need more schedule flexibility (Ercan et al. 2025). To take intersectionality into account during online sessions, existing guides and literature suggest these practical recommendations that should, naturally be adjusted to each specific situation, if required:

- If possible/budget allows, conduct individualised participant needs assessments: before the first session, contact each participant asking about: access to devices/internet, accessibility requirements, care responsibilities affecting schedule, and any concerns about participating online. Adapt accordingly. We have included these aspects in the registration survey so that participants are supported from an early stage. Where participants expressed concern about participating, the organisers would contact them individually and ask how we could support them in taking part effectively in the sessions.
- Address accessibility comprehensively: ensure materials are screen-reader compatible, offer captions/transcripts, use plain language, provide materials in advance for those who need processing time, and explicitly ask throughout: ‘what would make this more accessible for you?’. Then implement suggestions. We run all documents and communications through an accessibility check prior to circulating.
- Create explicit anti-discrimination norms: establish clear community guidelines about respectful interaction that specifically name intersectional identities (race, gender, disability, language, class, age, etc.). Empower all participants to call out exclusionary behaviour using a clear and previously communicated process. We established the role of “**Inclusion Supporter**” - a member of our team that was introduced to the participants as the go-to person in case they wanted to share a

concern privately, or they wanted specific assistance or even if there was something troubling them about the process, their participation, their role etc. In addition, we set up a dedicated **Inclusion Support team**, consisting of project team members who were monitoring an inbox where participants could email with any complaints regarding the process. Information about both of these Inclusion roles were given to participants in the Participants' Booklet (Appendix 7), as well as at the beginning of each assembly session.

- If possible, ensure a diverse facilitation team: facilitators should reflect the diversity of participants in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, and lived experience. This creates multiple entry points for connection and trust and ensures diverse perspectives shape the process itself. During the in-person assembly session for Colchester, the entire project team introduced themselves and said where they come from, explicitly showing the diversity in our places of origin, languages, roles, and backstories.

2.13. EU-CIEMBLY suggestions to participants for online participation

Drawing from the above discussion, we have advised participants at the local citizens' assembly pilots, in a tailored Participants' Booklet (Appendix 7) and at the start of the first assembly session of the following suggestions for online participation:

- Try to be on time for all sessions (we know that life can get in the way).
- Dress however you feel comfortable.
- Try to keep your camera on if you can. We want to get to know each other and have an open conversation, especially in small group discussions. Try to use a photo instead of a blank screen if your camera isn't working.
- Feel free to turn your camera off if you need a break, whether to grab a cup of tea, eat your dinner, feed your pet, or put the kids to bed! Just let us know you are still here via chat or thumbs up reaction.
- Please keep your microphone muted unless speaking so we all avoid talking over each other.
- Raise your hand if you would like to say something, unless the conversation is already in full flow, then feel free to interact as you normally would, being mindful of allowing others a chance to speak.

- You are inviting us into your homes, so please find a space that you are comfortable in. Be sure there is nothing inappropriate or that you would not like to be visible behind you (feel free to use a blur filter if you prefer).
- Try to give your complete attention to the discussion and activities (again, we know life gets in the way). Feel free to bring your food / coffee/ water to the meeting, we will all be hungry.
- Always be polite and respectful to others. We can disagree, as long as we treat each other with respect.

IX. The use of Civic Tech Platforms

One of the areas of particular interest for our project is the way in which digital tools could enhance intersectional inclusion in transnational democratic processes. While the section above explained our general approach towards online deliberation *within* the assembly, this section focuses on another dimension of online participation, namely the use of digital tools that aim to expand the range of voices feeding into the assembly and support informed, inclusive deliberation. In what follows, we present the digital strategy that supports the EU-CIEMBLY project's transnational citizens' assembly and that pilot's goal to strengthen intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly design.

1. Objectives

As explained above, the transnational pilot aims to bring together people experiencing, or at risk of experiencing housing precarity in the EU to deliberate on the question of 'How can the EU help deal with housing problems across Europe?' One of the design aspects of this pilot focuses on the use of digital tools. We are interested in examining how a set of civic tech tools can support the design and implementation of an intersectionality-oriented assembly across borders. Through experimenting with types and formats of digital facilitation, we seek to understand how technology might reduce barriers, create new modes of engagement, and amplify voices that remain underrepresented in traditional deliberative settings.

The transnational pilot will follow the Subaltern Counterpublics model (Deliverable 2.3), which frames subaltern counterpublics as discursive spaces where marginalised groups can deliberate free from dominant pressures, then re-enter the public sphere with strengthened viewpoints. The model outlines how counterpublics can be formed and organised by identity or interest, and before, during, or after the main assembly. It highlights the potential of integrating pre-existing counterpublics into assembly stages, such as the information-providing throughput phase. Deliverable 3.4 explains the details of how this model is operationalised for the transnational pilot.

Our aim is to accompany this model, which is developed in a primarily synchronous setting, with digital components that are (mainly) asynchronously used and allow for participation beyond the selected participants of the pilot assemblies.

For the above objective, the project is utilising Make.org's digital participation ecosystem, which strives to provide a concrete mechanism for operationalising intersectionality in practice in a purely digital environment. The current design of the transnational pilot seeks to support intersectional inclusion by creating safe spaces that amplify minority voices, encouraging the sharing of experiences and perspectives unique to PMIMG. This aligns with the 'enclave deliberations' (see Deliverables 2.3 and 3.4) approach within groups connected by shared experiences or identity. Enclaves can help marginalised participants clarify common goals, strengthen arguments, and develop recommendations. When linked to broader deliberative processes, they function as counterpublics, enhancing the intersectional character of the assembly.

The EU-CIEMBLy transnational assembly is framed as one such enclave deliberation: a dedicated space for those deeply affected by housing precarity to deliberate collectively, generating recommendations for the wider European deliberative system. Inspired by the 'most-deeply affected' principle (Afsahi, 2020b), this approach prioritises those facing the greatest barriers and are often excluded from traditional policy frameworks. With regard to housing, which is the topic of the transnational pilot assembly, those groups might include people experiencing or at risk of homelessness, low-income renters, migrants, and single-parent households.

The use of make.org's digital tools aims to strengthen the transnational pilot's attempt to add to the participation of PMIMG voices in the EU landscape of citizens' participation through an enclave-style assembly. The digital tools that we will apply for the transnational pilot seek to complement the deliberative setting of the pilot thus enhancing the pilot's potential for intersectional inclusion. This approach is linked with the following four dimensions:

- **Diversity**

Academic research emphasises the importance of **widening access** to assemblies so that deliberations and recommendations reflect a diverse set of actors. For instance,

Landemore and Fourniau (2023, p. 21) argue that ‘the widening of the boundaries of the citizens’ assemblies (...) give(s) it both a reality and a growing legitimacy in its role of representation’.

To this purpose, the digital tools that we have decided to embed in the transnational pilot aim to broaden engagement beyond those 100 that will be chosen to participate in the transnational assembly pilot.

- **Openness**

Practical and methodological constraints, as well as structural, institutional, and social barriers, mean that participation is not fully or equally open to everyone, not least due to the practical need to limit the number of participants in a citizens’ assembly. Concepts such as the ‘mini–maxi link’ underline the democratic value of connecting mini-publics more closely with the broader public sphere. As Setälä and Smith (2018) argue, mini-publics only realise their democratic potential when they are effectively embedded in wider political and deliberative processes.

The use of civic tech tools in the project has the potential to make access to the assembly more universal.

- **External perspectives**

The pilot assembly will primarily capture the views of its selected participants. However, additional voices external to the main pilot, including marginalised groups, thematic experts or international actors, could enrich the deliberation. Scholars repeatedly confirm the benefit of integrating a broad range of viewpoints into assemblies, noting that greater diversity in perspectives leads to more robust deliberation. As Mansbridge et al. (2012) argue, the deliberative capacity of a system is enhanced when it incorporates a plurality of viewpoints and discourses, since this broadens the range of arguments and forms of reasoning considered.

Civic tech tools aim to provide ways to gather such additional, external voices.

- **Information accessibility**

Participants currently rely largely on their own experience and the curated inputs provided. Literature stresses that high-quality, accessible expertise and data are crucial for informed decision-making—an area where digital tools, in particular, show great promise in helping participants understand, navigate, and synthesise complex information. Aichholzer and Rose (2019) argue that digital platforms can broaden access to information, diversify the types of data available, and facilitate participants' engagement with complex material.

Increasing access to broader datasets, expert knowledge, and well-structured information materials could strengthen the depth and quality of deliberation.

The above considerations have led the project team to choose to integrate the use of two of the project partner Make.org's civic tech tools in the transnational pilot.¹⁹ These tools are: a Consultation Platform and a Panoramic Platform. The following section outlines, step by step, how these two civic tech solutions will function in the context of the transnational pilot with the objective to enhance the intersectionality-oriented character of the pilot.

2. Digital tools to boost an intersectional approach

2.1. Consultation Platform: A large-scale participation platform

A **large-scale participation platform** makes it possible to reach and engage a far more diverse set of actors than a traditional panel alone. Citizens from different backgrounds, life paths, social groups, and the intersection of social groups can contribute their experiences and ideas directly through the digital platform. While no citizens' assembly can fully accommodate this breadth of participation on its own, the civic tech solution significantly expands the range of voices feeding into the process and strengthens the intersectionality-orientation of the pilot assembly.

As previously outlined, citizens' assemblies by design, involve a selected group of participants, no matter how representative the sampling may be. In contrast, an online participation platform is open to anyone who wishes to take part. By enabling broad public access, the platform complements the closed nature of the assembly with a much more inclusive channel for input. This openness allows the project to gather perspectives from individuals who may not have been selected for the pilot but still have a legitimate stake or interest in the topic.

¹⁹ Make.org is the civic tech partner of the project. This part builds on their extensive experience with large-scale citizen participation and digital engagement.

What is more, group discussions within an assembly naturally develop their own internal dynamics, which is both valuable and essential to the deliberative process. Nevertheless, these dynamics can also limit exposure to certain viewpoints. A large-scale participation platform provides an effective remedy by introducing external perspectives that the participants to the pilot assembly may not have encountered otherwise. Inputs derived from online consultations—whether new arguments, lived experiences, or minority viewpoints—can offer rich, complementary insights that help ground offline discussions in a broader societal context and enhance the depth of deliberation. Here, the asynchronous (via the platform) and the synchronous (via the online assembly sessions) approaches of the transnational pilot are complementary, allowing for external perspectives to be considered within an enclosed, safe space.

In light of the above considerations, we are embedding into the transnational assembly the **Consultation Platform** developed by Make.org. This is a digital platform that enables large-scale engagement on a given topic, helping to identify the main consensus amongst participants, as well as controversial topics. In practice, participants to the platform are invited to contribute with ideas related to the topic and to vote on those shared by others on the digital consultation platform. The platform offers every user the opportunity to speak up, be heard, and share the ideas that matter the most to them. Previous use cases of the platform include [EurHope](#)²⁰, [Compulsory service in Switzerland](#)²¹, and [Czech-German Consultation](#)²².

In addition, the consultation platform will be used to support the recruitment of participants for the transnational pilot assembly. Because participation on the online platform is open, it can serve as a means to open up the sample of potential participants. This approach is being explored for the first time within the scope of the EU-CIEMBLY project and will be closely monitored and evaluated.

2.3. Panoramic Platform: Rich verified database for information

The panoramic platform provides a smooth, integrated way to introduce perspectives that may not necessarily be represented among the pilot assembly participants. By offering a dedicated

²⁰ <https://about.make.org/articles-en/discover-the-final-report-of-the-eurhope-initiative>

²¹

<https://about.make.org/articles-en/a-broad-national-consultation-to-rethink-mandatory-service-in-switzerland>

²²

<https://about.make.org/articles-en/youth-together-for-europe-the-priorities-of-young-people-in-germany-and-czech-republic-for-a-stronger-and-more-sustainable-europe>

space where participants can access viewpoints that neither the pilot assembly composition nor the EU's public consultation on Housing²³ has captured, the platform significantly broadens the deliberative horizon. This exposure to additional experiences, arguments, and standpoints enhances the inclusiveness of the process and ensures that the pilot assemblies' discussions are informed by a wider societal landscape that complements the discussion in the room with new perspectives

A core requirement of any citizens' assembly is that participants have access to high-quality, impartial expert information (see Deliverable 2.2). Briefings must be comprehensive enough to support informed deliberation, yet selective and accessible enough not to overwhelm participants. A digital information-access platform addresses this challenge by providing a large, well-organised repository of verified materials. It can host a far greater volume of documents, expert contributions, and evidence than traditional briefing methods allow. With AI-assisted navigation, participants can easily retrieve, explore, and understand complex information with low barriers to entry (e.g. intuitive use, mobile ready, easy language). This approach strengthens the informational foundations of the pilot assembly while maintaining neutrality and safeguarding against bias, given the safeguards embedded into the make.org platform

Finally, by integrating the results of the online consultation into the digital information platform, participants gain an additional, intuitive way to access the public's input. This ensures that openness is not limited to the consultation phase but extends into the deliberative process itself, allowing pilot assembly members to revisit and reflect on the wider public's contributions whenever needed.

In light of this set of considerations, we are embedding into the transnational pilot Make.org's **Panoramic Platform**: generative-AI platform designed to make complex institutional or strategic content easier to understand and engage with. It transforms large volumes of material—from documents to debates and transcripts—into clear explanations, thematic overviews, and sourced answers to user questions. The platform works through natural-language interaction, allowing people to explore topics freely or follow curated pathways suggested by the system.

Its purpose is to widen access to information and strengthen participation by giving everyone, regardless of background, a shared and comprehensible knowledge base. Concretely, it means

²³ On the EU's public consultation on housing, see https://housing.ec.europa.eu/european-affordable-housing-plan_en and for a discussion on the link between this and the transnational pilot see Deliverable 3.4.

that information is retrieved through the platform and its AI generated, accessible answers - always with direct links to the in-depth documentation that constituted the database of the whole exercise (pdfs, videos, websites). Built with strong privacy safeguards and powered by a European AI model, it has already supported major national and European democratic initiatives by helping participants, observers, and stakeholders engage with the issues at stake in a more informed and meaningful way.

In the first stage, the Panoramic Platform will serve as a space for **online participants** to ask questions and engage directly with the process. The data that will be displayed and provided will allow participants that join on the online platform to better understand the topic at hand. This ensures that a broad range of **informed voices** can contribute from the outset, even before the pilot assembly meets. The users here are the participants in the online consultation.

In the second stage, the platform will also become available to the pilot assembly participants themselves. At this point, the results of the online participation process will be integrated into the platform, allowing pilot assembly members to **access, review, and reflect** on the insights gathered from the wider public - on top of the expert insights. Users: participants of the pilot assembly.

While the platform broadens participation, it is also important to acknowledge that digital tools can carry exclusionary risks. Differences in digital literacy, access to the internet, or ease in navigating online environments can constrain some age groups to engage fully, which from an intersectionality perspective cannot be ignored. In that context, it is important to highlight that the digital solutions outlined are set to complement, not replace, synchronous formats. Their role is to reinforce inclusion by adding an additional, accessible layer on top of synchronous online or in-person processes, ensuring that participants who may be less vocal or less available during such meetings can still contribute meaningfully. By combining digital asynchronous and synchronous offline platforms, the project aims to mitigate the digital divide and strengthens the overall inclusiveness of the deliberative process.

X. Evaluation Plan

This section outlines the evaluation methodology for the three EU-CIEMBLY pilot citizens' assemblies. A separate companion document prepared by IMI contains the full set of data collection instruments and operational protocols, which have been through an extensive process of partner feedback and refinement.

1. Purpose and Scope

The evaluation measures the effectiveness of the pilot assemblies against the intersectionality framework established in prior project deliverables (see Deliverables 2.2, 2.3 and 3.3). That framework rests on three normative dimensions: **intersectional equality** (recognising and mitigating structural barriers and power imbalances); **intersectional inclusion** (ensuring adequate participation and engagement of marginalised groups); and **intersectional deliberation** (designing processes that address structural biases and support meaningful contribution from diverse voices).

A single, unified evaluation framework covers all three pilots to enable direct comparison. Each pilot implements a distinct set of **targeted design interventions**, including community power-sharing at the local level, intersectionality-driven recruitment and materials at the national level and enclave deliberation at the transnational level. All three share a common topic (housing) and a uniform methodology of three deliberative stages (plenary consultation, working groups and final decision plenary). This consistency allows the comparative evaluation design to isolate the influence of each pilot's specific design choices. Data are collected from participants, facilitators and observers before, during and after each assembly through a mixed-methods approach integrating quantitative and qualitative survey data with qualitative interview and observational data.

2. Methodological Framework

The evaluation framework operationalises the three normative dimensions into measurable indicator categories drawn from the project's analytical and normative framework. Tables 1–3 summarise the indicator categories for each dimension.

2.1. Intersectional equality

Conventional citizens' assembly evaluations rely on formal equality metrics such as equal speaking time or demographic representativeness. The EU-CIEMBLY framework requires the evaluation of substantive equality: whether design choices effectively reduced structural barriers and disrupted power dynamics for Persons Belonging to Multiple Intersecting Marginalised Groups (PMIMG).

Indicator category	Definition
<i>Removal of structural barriers</i>	The extent to which participants experienced practical, structural and socio-economic barriers to participation (e.g. compensation, logistics, caring responsibilities, digital access).
<i>Substantive influence (co-design)</i>	The extent to which co-design and governance structures provide meaningful decision influence for community partners and participant representatives.
<i>Mitigation of power dynamics</i>	The extent to which facilitation and process design reduced perceptions of domination, marginalisation and unequal voice in deliberation, especially for PMIMG. The facilitation approach described in Section VI is evaluated directly against this indicator.
<i>Linguistic accessibility</i>	The extent to which language and communication needs are met (translation, interpretation, plain language, accessible formats) so all participants can participate fully. This indicator connects to the language policies set out in Section VII.

Table 1. Indicator categories for intersectional equality

2.2. Intersectional inclusion

This dimension moves beyond simple demographic quotas. The evaluation tests the epistemic value of each pilot's inclusion strategy, determining whether the substantive presence of PMIMG perspectives introduced distinct forms of knowledge that would have been absent in a purely random sample.

Indicator category	Definition
<i>External inclusion</i>	The extent to which recruitment and selection result in the substantive presence of PMIMG perspectives, including retention and attrition patterns across social groups.
<i>Internal inclusion</i>	The extent to which PMIMG participants can participate meaningfully in deliberation once present (e.g. sufficient understanding of purpose, perceived opportunities to speak, comfort to contribute).
<i>Feeling heard</i>	Whether participants feel listened to by other participants and facilitators, and that their contributions had space in the process.
<i>Perceived recognition</i>	The extent to which participants feel respected, valued and not judged, and that their contributions are treated as legitimate inputs.
<i>Output co-ownership</i>	The extent to which participants, especially PMIMG, feel their perspectives are reflected in final outputs and feel ownership over the recommendations.

Table 2. Indicator categories for intersectional inclusion

2.3. Intersectional deliberation

Standard deliberative theory prizes rational argumentation, which can alienate participants whose primary mode of political expression is storytelling, emotional or non-verbal. Therefore, the EU-CIEMBLY evaluation captures the use and efficacy of techniques designed to validate diverse communicative modes within deliberation. The intersectionality activators operationalised through the facilitation training are a central focus of this dimension.

Indicator category	Definition
<i>Diverse communication modes</i>	The extent to which different forms of expression and learning (e.g. storytelling, emotion, visual and non-verbal contributions) are enabled and validated.

<i>Epistemic gain</i>	Changes in understanding, confidence and perceived knowledge relevant to the assembly topic, including differential effects across social groups.
<i>Preservation of dissent</i>	The extent to which disagreement and minority viewpoints are perceived as expressed and preserved in outputs.
<i>Perceived procedural fairness</i>	Whether participants perceive decision-making and facilitation as fair, impartial and transparent.
<i>Reflexivity</i>	The extent to which participants and facilitators reflect on positionality, power relations and how these shape deliberation and outcomes.

Table 3. Indicator categories for intersectional deliberation

3. Research Questions

The evaluation research questions are organised across the input, throughput and output stages of the pilots. They map onto the project's design-choice framework (who participates, when and how often deliberation occurs, how rules and facilitation operate, what impact and influence outputs have). The core subject of analysis is the experience of participants, with particular focus on PMIMG. For every research question, the analysis compares the experiences of PMIMG participants with those of participants from other social groups across the different pilots.

RQ	Research question
RQ1	Which early organisational choices (recruitment strategy, compensation, logistical support, communication channels) effectively remove structural barriers and promote access, inclusion and commitment for PMIMG, and to what extent?
RQ2	Did the implementation of power-sharing and co-design elements influence participants' perceptions of agenda-setting and governance? How aligned are the perceptions of power-sharing between organisers and CA participants?
RQ3	How effectively did recruitment methods in each pilot achieve the substantive inclusion and demographic diversity goals set for PMIMG?

RQ4	What was the impact of using various learning formats (such as storytelling, expert debates, infographics, presentations and written summaries) on self-reported deliberative confidence among PMIMG?
RQ5	How do PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants perceive the shorter-duration pilot assembly format in terms of willingness to participate, legitimacy, respecting their time constraints and quality of the deliberative process?
RQ6	To what extent did intersectionality-informed facilitation strategies (including the activators of valuing diverse communication modes, identifying and mitigating power dynamics, practising reflexivity) successfully mitigate power dynamics & prevent internal exclusion experienced by PMIMG?
RQ7	How did the features of the chosen decision-making model (e.g. consensus, voting thresholds, meta-consensus) affect the expression of minority perspectives? Did it encourage or discourage authentic expressions of dissent by PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants?
RQ8	How did pilot CA design choices (e.g. community co-design, intersectional learning materials, application of the 'deeply affected' principle to sampling) affect the inclusion of diverse perspectives? How did these choices affect the pilot's perceived legitimacy and inclusivity among PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants?
RQ9	How was the use of information and communication technology experienced across the hybrid (local, national) and online (transnational) pilots in terms of impact on the quality of deliberation, accessibility and capacity to fully participate from the perspective of PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants?
RQ10	How did the assemblies' language policies and language-support arrangements (including translation, interpretation, plain-language practices and any AI-mediated support) affect participants' ability and willingness to participate, their engagement with the topic and their perceived equality of access to deliberation, particularly for PMIMG participants?
RQ11	To what extent did PMIMG and non-PMIMG feel that the final recommendations and documentation reflected their substantive perspectives and minority viewpoints articulated during deliberation?
RQ12	What was the uptake of the assembly recommendations by relevant policy-makers and institutions at the local, national and transnational levels?
RQ13	To what extent did participation influence PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants' personal outcomes regarding self-reported deliberative confidence, sense of political agency and sustained interest in future civic engagement?

Table 4. Evaluation research questions

Input stage (RQ1–RQ5). These questions evaluate how successfully the initial pilot design and pre-assembly processes minimise barriers and maximise inclusion. They address the effectiveness of specific organisational choices (recruitment strategy, compensation, logistical support, communication channels) in removing structural barriers and promoting access for PMIMG. They examine the influence of power-sharing and co-design elements on participants' perceptions of governance. They assess the demographic outcomes of each recruitment method, the impact of varied learning formats on deliberative confidence, and the effect of the shortened pilot duration on willingness to participate and perceived legitimacy.

Throughput stage (RQ6–RQ10). These questions assess the quality of the assembly process itself. They examine whether intersectionality-informed facilitation strategies successfully prevented internal exclusion of PMIMG. They address the effect of decision-making model features on the expression of minority perspectives. They evaluate how pilot-specific design choices (community co-design, intersectional learning materials, enclave deliberation) influenced perceived inclusivity and legitimacy, how information and communication technology performed across hybrid and online formats and how language policies and support arrangements affected participation and engagement.

Output stage (RQ11–RQ13). These questions evaluate whether assembly outcomes produced equitable results. They measure whether PMIMG and non-PMIMG participants felt the final recommendations reflected their substantive perspectives and minority viewpoints. They assess uptake of recommendations by relevant policy-makers and institutions, and the impact of participation on self-reported deliberative confidence, political agency and sustained civic engagement.

4. Data Collection Plan

For the purposes of gathering data, evaluation employs a mixed-methods design, integrating quantitative data for breadth and comparability with qualitative data. The design aims to enable triangulation. Data collection occurs through seven instruments, each calibrated to minimise respondent burden while maximising evaluative coverage.

Tool	Purpose	Timing
<i>Co-design participant survey</i>	Evaluates experiences of participants involved in pre-assembly co-design workshops and governance bodies.	Pre-CA, after co-design sessions
<i>Participant registration survey</i>	Develops the sampling pool and collects baseline demographic and attitudinal data for each pilot.	Pre-CA
<i>Participant diary survey</i>	Repeated-measures surveys collecting participant experience data on inclusion, equality, deliberation quality and engagement at multiple time points.	Pre-CA (baseline) and after each CA session
<i>Follow-up participant survey</i>	Collects participant impact data on outcomes, co-ownership of recommendations, political efficacy and future civic engagement intentions.	Post-CA
<i>Facilitator diary survey</i>	Repeated-measures surveys collecting facilitator experience data, including the reflexivity journal measuring positionality awareness and power dynamics management.	Pre-CA (baseline), during CA
<i>Observer diary survey</i>	Structured observation data focusing on physical cues, timing, procedural actions and deliberation dynamics, including the reflexivity journal.	Pre-CA (baseline), during CA
<i>Qualitative interviews</i>	Semi-structured interviews with participants, facilitators and observers.	Post-CA

Table 5. Data collection instruments

Baseline items for the registration stage are included in the recruitment registration form for each pilot. Where possible, survey design is aligned with prior citizens' assembly evaluations to aid comparability with existing findings (see Deliverable 3.3). Instruments will be translated into Greek and the languages required for the transnational pilot using AI tools, with checks delegated to partners with the relevant language capacity.

5. Fieldwork and Quality Assurance

Data collection follows a phased approach across the three staggered pilots. Pre-Assembly data collection begins approximately seven days before each pilot event, with follow-up reminders to maximise response rates. During-assembly diary surveys are administered after each session, with automated email reminders, alongside structured observation by designated observers. Post-assembly semi-structured qualitative interviews are conducted within four weeks of each pilot's conclusion. Live testimonials and vox pop questions (coordinated with ASPON's communications coverage) serve as supplementary data.

Ongoing data quality reviews run throughout the fieldwork period (January–October 2026). IMI will hold review meetings after each pilot to assess data quality, discuss initial findings and agree any necessary adjustments. Interview and survey data submitted in languages other than English will be translated using AI tools with checks delegated to partners with the relevant language capacity. All data management complies with the Data Management Plan (Deliverable 1.3) and GDPR requirements.

XI. Conclusion

This deliverable has documented the micro-design phase of the EU-CIEMBLY pilots and shown how the project's intersectionality framework has been translated into concrete organisational choices across the local, national, and transnational pilot assemblies. Building on the macro-design decisions set out in Deliverable 3.4, it has explained how the project team sought to embed intersectionality throughout the design of the pilots by remaining explicit about its normative commitments, reflecting on positionality, adopting a context-based approach, and developing targeted interventions across the input, throughput, and output stages of the assembly process. It has also provided details on decisions, actions, and plans regarding Recruitment, Facilitation, Language, and Online deliberative spaces for the pilots.

A key message running through this deliverable is that intersectionality-oriented assembly design must remain reflexive, adaptive, and context-sensitive. The staggered nature of the three pilots means that the project is intentionally iterative: lessons from the first pilot can inform the design and implementation of the next two. At the same time, the report acknowledges the practical constraints, uncertainties, and limitations that inevitably accompany real-world experimentation in deliberative processes. This is particularly important in a project that seeks not to apply a rigid template, but to test and refine alternative approaches in different settings.

Ultimately, this deliverable lays the practical and conceptual groundwork for the next stages of Work Package 4. By documenting the rationale behind the pilots' design choices, it provides an essential basis for the later evaluation of their effectiveness. Connected to this, the report has also explained the Evaluation plan for the pilots, including the key research questions and methodological tools designed for this project. In doing so, the deliverable contributes to the broader ambition of EU-CIEMBLY: to generate evidence-based recommendations on how citizens' assemblies can be designed and conducted in ways that are informed by intersectionality considerations therefore supporting more inclusive forms of democratic participation.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Online Positionality Training Presentation Delivered by Karen Bowlby

Whose voices shape the Room?

Power, Privilege, and Team Positionality

Karen Bowlby
Inclusion Manager

Session Objectives

- Reflect on individual and shared positions of privilege and marginalisation
- Explore how positionality influences design and facilitation of citizens' assemblies
- Identify concrete ways to use your privilege collectively to design more inclusive spaces

Quick re-cap

Privilege is...

..... 'an invisible **package of unearned assets** that I can count on cashing in each day **An invisible, weightless knapsack** of special provisions, maps, passports, codebooks, visas, clothes, tools and blank cheques'

Peggy McIntosh *White Privilege: Unpacking the Invisible Knapsack* 1988
<https://www.racialequitytools.org/resourcefiles/mcintosh.pdf>

Privilege is...

The luxury not to think about the characteristic in question

A norm of visibility in (*politics, leadership, media, literature, art (etc)*)

Expectations of fair treatment (*in services and systems*)

Experience of Advantaged treatment

Slide 5

Photo by [Skyler Ewing](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Privilege & Power

Slide 6

Racism & Power

What isn't accounted for in the Equality Act 2010

Slide 7

Privilege and Intersectionality

'...our many identities interact to produce effects that are not simply the sum of each of them'

- Crenshaw, 1991,
Mapping the Margins

Intersectionality refers to an analytical framework that views people through the interaction of their social identities (including gender, race, sexual orientation, socioeconomic class, etc.) resulting in a unique lived social experience of oppression and privilege, as opposed to an additive model of oppression that views people as the sum of their social identities

Slide 8

The challenges of using privilege

Responses to the term **often evoke feelings of guilt, shame and denial that can shut down conversations** (e.g. 'white tears')

<https://ma-consultancy.co.uk/blog/language-is-important-why-we-will-no-longer-use-allyship-and-privilege-in-our-work>

Slide 9

The challenges of using privilege

The term **locates advantage at the individual level:**

- We attach privilege to individuals, without exploring or understanding how it has been produced by systems of oppression
- We therefore talk about 'privilege' **as if it is the cause and not the consequence of oppression**
- The focus becomes on what we can do *individually*, rather than *collectively* to challenge the system

<https://ma-consultancy.co.uk/blog/language-is-important-why-we-will-no-longer-use-allyship-and-privilege-in-our-work>

Slide 10

Positionality

In Research & Design

Positionality

Why it matters

- Positionality refers to the recognition that our identities, values and social positions shape what we research, how we research, and how we interpret findings.

Why it matters:

- Ensures awareness of biases and blind spots
- Promotes ethical and inclusive research design
- Highlights power dynamics and privilege in research relationships

Positionality

Connection to Power, Privilege and Intersectionality

- Positionality helps us understand where we hold privilege and where we experience marginalisation
- Our multiple identities interact, creating unique experiences of privilege and oppression that influence research decisions

Slide 13

Team Positionality Map

Where do you sit in the system – individually and collectively?

Activity: Team Positionality Map

Step 1: Individual Reflection

Using the Wheel of Power, ask yourself:

- Where do I hold unearned advantage?
- Where do I feel invisible or marginalised?
- What identifies do I rarely think about?
- What parts of my identity shape how I design or facilitate?

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Systemic Advantages/ Disadvantages

- Where do I hold unearned advantage?
- Where do I feel invisible or marginalised?
- What identifies do I rarely think about?
- What parts of my identity shape how I design or facilitate?

Credit: Leyla Okhai, Diverse Minds

Slide 15

Slide

Activity: Team Positionality Map

Step 2: Sharing

- What surprised you within this individual reflection?
- Has anything shifted in your understanding of power and privilege?

Slide 17

Activity: Team Positionality Map

Step 3: Full Team Reflection

- Where do you hold collective privilege as a team?
- Are there gaps in lived experience, perspective, language, or access in your team?
- What risks do you run if you design from only this vantage point?

Slide 18

Power in the Assembly Room

Who holds the knife that slices the pie?

Discussion: Who holds the knife that slices the pie?

- Within citizens' assemblies – who controls time, voice, tone?
- Who might feel 'grateful to be included'?
- Who might feel 'entitled to participate fully'?

- How does your positionality as a team impact who speaks, who is listened to, who feels safe in the assemblies / pilots?

Design Tensions

How Would You Respond?

Activity: Practice Scenarios

Design tensions

- What assumptions about power or voice are being made?
- How might your team's privilege impact how you interpret that moment?
- What would an intersectional design intervention look like here?

Moving forward

What will you do differently?

Team reflection

What is something you can change going forward?

- Is there something you'll keep in mind about your positionality?
- Is there something you can do to use your privilege better?
- Is there a part of your design process that could be shifted that you hadn't thought about before?

Slide 24

**Any
questions?**

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Appendix 2. Review of Researcher Positionality

EU-CIEMBLY Project Review of Researcher Positionality

Consent Note

By returning a completed version of this questionnaire to euciembly@essex.ac.uk I consent to the following:

- I agree to participate in this positionality review as a researcher/collaborator on the EU-CIEMBLY project.
- This agreement has been given voluntarily and without coercion.
- I have been given full information about the exercise, and the contact details of the researcher(s).
- I have read and understood the information provided in '2. Guidance for Project Team Members' below.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions about this exercise and my role in it.

Signed:

Date:

This exercise has received ethics approval under ERAMS reference ETH2324-0311

1. Guidance for Project Team Members

You will find a template for completing this positionality exercise below in Section 3. The present Section 2 provides guidance on the process.

1. Introduction

As we now embark on the practical design and implementation of the project's pilot citizens' assemblies, it is important that we as a project team take the time **to reflect further** on our own positionality and how this might relate to the design choices, conduct, and evaluation of the

three pilots. We all have differing identities, values, and memberships of various intersecting social groups and we may have differing motivations that led to our interest and participation in the EU-CIEMBLY project, to which we are all contributing in complementary ways. The purpose of examining the positionality of individual researchers in a project, or of a project team as a whole, is to allow the team to acknowledge how values and lived experiences can impact research design or findings and can be used as a means through which to ‘manage or neutralize the influence of values’ or ‘to minimize the possibility of bias’ (Cooper et al., 2024 p. 1).

The EU-CIEMBLY project is in a different position to some other social science research projects in that positionality and social relations/dynamics of power are also central to the concept of intersectionality. The very purpose of our project is to explore how experiences and perceptions of citizens’ assembly participation might differ depending on membership of social groups and the relationship between them. As such, understanding and reflecting on positionality are inherent normative and methodological aspects of the design and conduct of our pilot citizens’ assemblies, rather than a way of reducing biases in research. In other words, reflecting on positionality both contributes to the project’s overall objectives of integrating intersectionality considerations into the design of citizens’ assemblies and constitutes an important step in making our understanding and operationalisation of intersectionality more explicit. This is also expressed in Deliverable 3.4, which states that being mindful of our own positionality is a key consideration in the design of the project’s pilot assemblies (see ‘Key Consideration 2’ in Deliverable 3.4).

While no research is value-free, it is the case that some of the values espoused by the EU-CIEMBLY project have already been foregrounded. For example, the choice to integrate intersectionality as an analytical lens reflects a normative position as to the value and role of that concept in addressing inequality and exclusion, and in enhancing good deliberation within the context of citizens’ assemblies. Intersectionality, which is itself a value-laden concept, therefore guides the design, conduct, and eventual evaluation of the research. The added value of conducting a positionality assessment of the project team is to foreground not only the stated, but also the unstated values and beliefs, power, and privileges of the project team as a whole (Cooper et al., 2025 p. 2) and the extent to which these might have an influence on the project.

Aspects of positionality that are particularly relevant to researchers include: (1) ontological assumptions (beliefs about reality and what is knowable); (2) epistemological assumptions (beliefs about the nature of knowledge); and (3) assumptions about human nature (the way humans interact with the environment) (Cooper et al., 2024 p. 3).

There are essentially two steps involved in conducting a positionality analysis: (1) **reflection** on our individual positionality (thinking reflectively); and (2) **reflexion**, which involves taking an external view of one’s positionality (thinking reflexively). We have made the decision to conduct a positionality review in three ways to ensure its proper integration into the design and delivery of our pilot citizens’ assemblies:

1. The first (and present) positionality review entails the assessment of the **positionality of the project team** as a whole given our role as researchers and

collaborators in making key decisions as to how the pilots will be designed and conducted (this is part of Task 4.1 and will be reflected in Deliverable 4.1).

2. The second way is to conduct a more targeted **positionality review of the pilots' facilitators** as part of the training to be conducted under Task 4.2, given the particular importance of facilitation in integrating intersectionality considerations into the pilots (this part of Task 4.2 will be reflected in Deliverable 4.2).
3. Finally, a **positionality review of the pilots' participants** will allow the researchers to evaluate the implications of the participants' reflection for the conduct and evaluation of the pilots, including whether an emphasis on positionality has an impact on the way in which individuals deliberate in an assembly. This will take place during the pilot assemblies.

It is our aim that the above **suite of positionality tools** will be useful to us as a project team and will provide a blueprint for positionality reviews by other teams involved in citizens' assembly design or deliberative mini-public design, who are keen to embed intersectionality considerations into their practices.

The following sets out in more detail the way in which we intend to conduct a positionality review of the project team.

2. Positionality Review of the Project Team

The below positionality exercise has been adapted from Cooper et al., (2024) who—following an analysis of the existing literature and guidance on positionality—have developed positionality tools that can be found [here](#) and [here](#). Part of the first exercise i.e. the reflection on social groups and intersectionality has been adapted from the Power Flower (JASS, adapted by Lisa VeneKlasen and Valerie Miller, originally designed by Bev Burke, Barb Thomas, et. al), which can be found [here](#). Further guidance has been taken from the questions deployed by Western University in their dimensions of positionality reflection worksheet, available [here](#).

Both exercises below (reflection and reflexion) have been tailored to the precise context and needs of the project, including in the choice of social groups to emphasise as well as the specifications relating to the different roles that each of us have been—or will be—involved in over the duration of the project.

The next few pages provide the guidance to the exercise. In Section 3 you can find a template which you can complete either by printing and filling it in, or on your desktop.

1. Reflection on Social Groups, Intersectionality, Lived Experience, and Beliefs

This first **reflective stage** involves a consideration of your individual identity and membership of (intersecting) social groups and how your own positionality aligns with dimensions of privilege and marginalisation, bearing in mind the relevant social location and context in which you find yourself.

The first step is to reflect on who you are by considering your membership of many intersecting social groups. The second step is to reflect on where you are positioned within each social group with regard to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation. You should reflect on whether you are in a marginalised position with respect to multiple (intersecting) social groups.

The above reflections can be achieved through the construction of a Power Flower. You can draw the Power Flower yourself or simply copy and paste the below.²⁴

Figure 1. Blank Power Flower

In the central (dark blue) part of the flower, you should add your **nationality/nationalities**.

The inner (light blue) part of the flower indicates your membership of specific social groups. You should include the social groups of relevance to the EU-CIEMBLY project, i.e. **race/ethnicity, sex/gender, age, and socio-economic status**.

For the remaining two petals, you can add social groups that are of particular importance to **you/your identity or for power relations** in the geographic/social context in which you are located, e.g. religion, education etc.

The outer part of the flower represents the social characteristics of those who possess power or are in a privileged position in your geographic/social location (this will usually be in relation to the **country** in which you are based).

²⁴ The Power Flower templates derive from Jass (n.d.).

Figure 2. Completed Power Flower

Precise iterations of privilege and marginalisation can be context-dependent (social, geographic, economic context etc), but in general, we can be guided by the Wheel of Power/Privilege—which can be found [here](#) and is reproduced below—in determining markers of privilege and marginalisation.

WHEEL OF POWER/PRIVILEGE

Figure 3. Wheel of Power/Privilege

It can also be seen that there are different ways of categorising or labelling social groups. For example socio-economic status can be expressed as 'class', which allows for broader categorisations (such as poor, middle class, rich as found in the Wheel of Power/Privilege). Similarly, age can be expressed either in terms of broad categorisations (e.g. middle aged) or as an age range or an exact age (e.g. 45–55 or 47). **It is up to you how much detail or specificity to provide.** For instance, you can be quite specific in saying that you are 47 years old, or you can keep it more generic by saying you are middle aged, or by saying that you are of a relatively privileged age.

Once you have completed the Power Flower, please reflect more broadly on your positionality in relation to privileged and marginalised social groups by considering the following reflection points in your own time:

How many of your personal characteristics are different from the privileged characteristics in each social group?

Has your positionality in relation to privilege/marginalisation changed over time for any social groups?

What does your overall positionality say about your own power or your potential for exercising power over others?

How would you position your lived experiences in relation to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation? (Think e.g. about your education, family life, housing situation, career stage etc).

How might your lived experiences affect your ability to empathise with others with different lived experiences and understand issues relevant to diverse lived experiences?

You can choose whether or not to share your completed Power Flower and self-reflection with the UE team, by sending these to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

The above self-reflection points can now be used to conduct a **reflexion** as to how your positionality might influence your participation in the project. The instructions for the reflexion part of the positionality are provided in part B., below.

We ask that you do share this reflexion with the UE team to allow us to conduct an overall analysis of the project team's positionality.

2. Reflexion on Implications for the EU-CIEMBLY Project's Design and Implementation

Having conducted your reflection, you are now in a position to recognise how membership of intersecting privileged and marginalised social groups can influence how you engage in research, whether more generally but also specifically on the EU-CIEMBLY project. The below reflexive exercise enables you to identify any potential **biases and values** that you bring to the project by virtue of your positionality. We ask that you share your reflexion with the UE team (eu-ciembly@essex.ac.uk) to allow that team to conduct a more holistic assessment (without identifying individuals) of the project team's positionality and how this may have influenced the research questions we have asked, the methods we have chosen to adopt, the interpretations we make, and how we have gone about designing, delivering, and eventually evaluating the pilot citizens' assemblies. **Individual identifying features will not be included in this aggregate analysis**, with the intention being to present a more general narrative on the positionality of the project as a whole.

The below sets out the questions that you will be asked to address (see the template in Section 3).

1. Selecting Research Topics and Questions

How does your positionality impact what research you choose to do?

What was your motivation for joining the EU-CIEMBLY project? Did your positionality have an influence on your decision to join the project, or on the specific role you have chosen to conduct within the project?

How do you think the attributes of the project team relate to the topic of the project and its framing?

2. Ontological Assumptions

How does your positionality impact what you can observe as a researcher/project team member?

Might you have views similar to (an insider) and different from (an outsider) current and potential participants and partners?

3. Epistemological Assumptions

How does your positionality impact how you know what you know?

(As an example, you can think about this from a critical or an objective perspective. A critical approach recognises that knowledge is shaped by social, cultural, and personal contexts and thereby places values on lived experiences, while challenging power dynamics. A more objective approach aims for neutrality and assumes that the researcher can separate themselves from the research)

4. Methodological Assumptions

How does positionality impact how you make methodological choices?

(Think about what influences your method, whether that is historical traditions, research alignment with methods, disciplinary norms etc)

5. Reciprocity

How does your positionality impact how you relate to EU-CIEMBLY project partners and to current and potential research participants?

How might your positionality lead to better insights or to blind spots in reciprocity in design e.g. in determining who the EU-CIEMBLY project is for?

In what ways does your positionality influence your sense of responsibility and obligations to the interests, values, and priorities of the participants?

(Think about your marginalised and privileged positions and whether this might give you a personal connection to participants, communities and relevant organisations)

6. Communication

How does your positionality impact how you represent yourself in writing and other communication?

(Think about which of your identities are or can be communicated or perceived and do you make conscious decisions to disclose aspects of your identity?)

References

Cooper, C. et al., A Positionality Tool to Support Ethical Research and Inclusion in the Participatory Sciences 9(1): 28 *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* (2024) 1
<https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.684>

JASS. (n.d.). Power Flower: Our Intersecting Identities. <https://werise-toolkit.org/en/toolkit>

Western Research, Equitable Partnership in Research Module – Positionality Worksheet

3. Template

STEP 1: Reflection on Social Groups, Intersectionality, Lived Experience, and Beliefs

1.1 Complete the power flower

Figure 1. Blank Power Flower

1.2 Consider the following reflection points in your own time:

- How many of your personal characteristics are different from the privileged characteristics in each social group?
- Has your positionality in relation to privilege/ marginalisation changed over time for any social groups?

- What does your overall positionality say about your own power or your potential for exercising power over others?
- How would you position your lived experiences in relation to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation? (Think, e.g., about your education, family life, housing situation, career stage etc).
- How might your lived experiences affect your ability to empathise with others with different lived experiences and understand issues relevant to diverse lived experiences?

1.3. If you wish, you can share your completed Power Flower and self-reflection with the UE team by sending these to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

STEP 2. Reflexion on Implications for the EU-CIEMBLY Project's Design and Implementation

2.1 Complete the following reflexive exercise in your own time.

2.1.1 Selecting Research Topics and Questions

- How does your positionality impact what research you choose to do?
- What was your motivation for joining the EU-CIEMBLY project? Did your positionality have an influence on your decision to join the project, or on the specific role you have chosen to conduct within the project?
- How do you think the attributes of the project team relate to the topic of the project and its framing?

2.1.2 Ontological Assumptions

- How does your positionality impact what you can observe as a researcher?
- Might you have views similar to (an insider) and different from (an outsider) current and potential participants and partners?

2.1.3. Epistemological Assumptions

- How does your positionality impact how you know what you know?

2.1.4. Methodological Assumptions

- How does positionality impact how you make methodological choices?

2.1.5 Reciprocity

- How does your positionality impact how you relate to EU-CIEMBLY project partners and to current and potential research participants?
- How might your positionality lead to better insights or to blind spots in reciprocity in design e.g. in determining who the EU-CIEMBLY project is for?
- In what ways does your positionality influence your sense of responsibility and obligations to the interests, values, and priorities of the participants?

2.1.6 Communication

- How does your positionality impact how you represent yourself in writing and other communication?

2.2. Please send your completed reflexion exercise to the UE team at euciembly@essex.ac.uk to allow that team to conduct a more holistic assessment (without identifying individuals) of the project team's positionality and how this may have influenced the research questions we have asked, the methods we have chosen to adopt, the interpretations we make, and how we have gone about designing, delivering, and eventually evaluating the pilot citizens' assemblies. Individual identifying features will not be included in this aggregate analysis. Instead, a more general narrative of the positionality of the project as a whole will be presented.

Appendix 3. Review of Facilitator Positionality

EU-CIEMBLY Project Review of Facilitator Positionality

1. Consent Note

By returning a completed version of this questionnaire to euciembly@essex.ac.uk I consent to the following:

- I. I agree to participate in this positionality review as a facilitator on the EU-CIEMBLY project.
- II. This agreement has been given voluntarily and without coercion.
- III. I have been given full information about the exercise, and the contact details of the researcher(s).
- IV. I have read and understood the information provided in the guidance below.
- V. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about this exercise and my role in it.

Signed:

Date:

This exercise has received ethics approval under ERAMS reference ETH2324-0311

2. Guidance for Facilitators

You will find a template for completing this positionality exercise below in Section 3. The present Section 2 provides guidance on the process.

3. Introduction

As we move towards the pilot stage of the EU-CIEMBLY project, it is important that the pilot assemblies' facilitators take the time to reflect on their own positionality and how this might influence decisions relating to facilitation both before and during the pilots as well as at the evaluation stage.

We all have differing identities, values, and memberships of various intersecting social groups and we may have differing motivations that led to our interest and participation in the EU-CIEMBLY project, to which we are all contributing in complementary ways. The purpose of

examining the positionality of individual researchers in a project, or of a project team as a whole, is to allow the team to acknowledge how values and lived experiences can impact research design or findings and can be used as a means through which to ‘manage or neutralize the influence of values’ or ‘to minimize the possibility of bias’ (Cooper et al., 2024 p. 1).

The EU-CIEMBLY project is in a different position to other social science research projects in that positionality and social relations/dynamics of power are also central to the concept of intersectionality. The very purpose of our project is to explore how experiences and perceptions of citizens’ assembly participation might differ depending on membership of social groups and the relationship between them. As such, understanding and reflecting on positionality are inherent normative and methodological aspects of the design and conduct of our pilot citizens’ assemblies, rather than a way of reducing biases in research. In other words, reflecting on positionality both contributes to the project’s overall objectives of integrating intersectionality considerations into the design of citizens’ assemblies and constitutes an important step in making our understanding and operationalisation of intersectionality more explicit. This is also expressed in [Deliverable 3.4](#), which states that being mindful of our own positionality is a key consideration in the design of the project’s pilot assemblies (see ‘Key Consideration 2’ in Deliverable 3.4). Moreover, Deliverable 3.4 identified facilitation as an important cross-cutting intervention for the incorporation of intersectionality considerations into the design and delivery of all three pilots.

While no research is value-free, it is the case that some of the values espoused by the EU-CIEMBLY project have already been foregrounded. For example, the choice to integrate intersectionality as an analytical lens reflects a normative position as to the value and role of that concept in addressing inequality and exclusion, and in enhancing good deliberation within the context of citizens’ assemblies. Intersectionality, which is itself a value-laden concept, therefore guides the design, conduct, and eventual evaluation of the research. The added value of conducting a positionality assessment of the pilots’ facilitators is to foreground not only the stated, but also the unstated values and beliefs, power, and privileges of the facilitation team (Cooper et al., 2025 p. 2) and the extent to which these might have an influence on the conduct of the pilots.

There are essentially two steps involved in conducting a positionality analysis: (1) **reflection** on our individual positionality (thinking reflectively); and (2) **reflexion**, which involve taking an external view of one’s positionality (thinking reflexively). We have made the decision to conduct a positionality review in three ways to ensure its proper integration into all aspects of the design and delivery of our pilot citizens’ assemblies:

- a. The first positionality review, which some of you will already have participated in, entailed the assessment of the **positionality of the project team** as a whole given our role as researchers and collaborators in making key decisions as to how the pilots will be designed and conducted (this is part of Task 4.1 and will be reflected in Deliverable 4.1).
- b. The second (and present) way is to conduct a more targeted **pre-pilot positionality review of the pilots’ facilitators** as part of the training to be

conducted under Task 4.2, given the particular importance of facilitation in integrating intersectionality considerations into the pilots (this will be reflected in Deliverable 4.2). Facilitators will also be asked to reflect on their positionality at various stages throughout and subsequent to the pilots.

- c. Finally, a **positionality review of the pilots' participants** will allow the researchers to evaluate the implications of the participants' reflection for the conduct and evaluation of the pilots, including whether an emphasis on positionality has an impact on the way in which individuals deliberate in an assembly.

It is our aim that the above **suite of positionality tools** will be useful to us as a project team and will provide a blueprint for positionality reviews by other teams involved in citizens' assembly design or deliberative mini-public design, who are keen to embed intersectionality considerations into their practices.

The following sets out in more detail the way in which we intend to conduct a pre-pilot positionality review of the facilitation team.

4. Pre-Pilot Positionality Review of the Facilitation Team

The below positionality exercise has been adapted from Cooper et al., (2024) who—following an analysis of the existing literature and guidance on positionality—have developed positionality tools that can be found [here](#) and [here](#). Part of the first exercise i.e. the reflection on social groups and intersectionality has been adapted from the Power Flower (JASS, adapted by Lisa VeneKlasen and Valerie Miller, originally designed by Bev Burke, Barb Thomas, et. al), which can be found [here](#). Further guidance has been taken from the questions deployed by Western University in their dimensions of positionality reflection worksheet, available [here](#).

Both exercises below (reflection and reflexion) have been tailored to the precise context and needs of the project, including in the choice of social groups to emphasise as well as the specifications relating to the role of facilitators throughout the citizens' assemblies to be piloted at a local, national, and transnational level.

The next few pages provide the guidance to the exercise. In Section 3 you can find a template which you can complete either by printing and filling it in, or on your desktop.

1. Reflection on Social Groups, Intersectionality, Lived Experience, and Beliefs

This first reflective stage involves a consideration of your individual identity and membership of (intersecting) social groups and how your own positionality aligns with dimensions of privilege and marginalisation, bearing in mind the relevant social location and context in which you find yourself.

The first step is to reflect on who you are by considering your membership of many intersecting social groups. The second step is to reflect on where you are positioned within each social group with regard to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation. You should reflect on whether you are in a marginalised position with respect to multiple (intersecting) social groups.

The above reflections can be achieved through the construction of a Power Flower. You can draw the Power Flower yourself or simply copy and paste the below.²⁵

Figure 1. Blank Power Flower

In the central (dark blue) part of the flower, you should add your **nationality/nationalities**.

The inner (light blue) part of the flower indicates your membership of specific social groups. You should include the social groups of relevance to the EU-CIEMBLY project, i.e. **race/ethnicity, sex/gender, age, and socio-economic status**.

For the remaining two petals, you can add social groups that are of particular importance to **you/your identity or for power relations** in the geographic/social context in which you are located, e.g. religion, education etc.

The outer part of the flower represents the social characteristics of those who possess power or are in a privileged position in your geographic/social location (this will usually be in relation to the **country** in which you are based).

²⁵ The Power Flower templates derive from Jass (n.d.).

Figure 2. Completed Power Flower

Precise iterations of privilege and marginalisation can be context-dependent (social, geographic, economic context etc), but in general, we can be guided by the Wheel of Power/Privilege—which can be found [here](#) and is reproduced below—in determining markers of privilege and marginalisation.

WHEEL OF POWER/PRIVILEGE

Figure 3. Wheel of Power/Privilege

It can also be seen that there are different ways of categorising or labelling social groups, for example socio-economic status can be expressed as 'class', which allows for broader categorisations (such as poor, middle class, rich as found in the Wheel of Power/Privilege). Similarly, age can be expressed either in terms of broad categorisations (e.g. middle aged) or as an age range or an exact age (e.g. 45–55 or 47). It is up to you how much detail or specificity to provide. For instance, you can be quite specific in saying that you are 47 years old, or you can keep it more generic by saying you are middle aged, or by saying that you are of a relatively privileged age.

Once you have completed the Power Flower, you will be asked to reflect more broadly on your positionality in relation to privileged and marginalised social groups by considering the following reflection points in your own time:

How many of your personal characteristics are different from the privileged characteristics in each social group?

Has your positionality in relation to privilege/marginalisation changed over time for any social groups?

What does your overall positionality say about your own power or your potential for exercising power over others?

How would you position your lived experiences in relation to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation? (Think for e.g. about your education, family life, housing situation, career stage etc).

How might your lived experiences affect your ability to empathise with others with different lived experiences and understand issues relevant to diverse lived experiences?

You can choose whether or not to share your completed Power Flower and self-reflection with the UE team (eu-ciembly@essex.ac.uk).

The above self-reflection points will then be used to conduct a **reflexion** as to how your positionality might influence your role as a facilitator in the pilots. We ask that you do share this reflexion with the UE team to allow us to conduct an overall analysis of the project team's positionality (more details below).

2. Reflexion on Implications for your role as a facilitator for the EU-CIEMBLY Project's Pilot Citizens' Assemblies

Having conducted your reflection, you are now in a position to recognise how membership of intersecting privileged and marginalised social groups can influence how you engage in your role as a pilot facilitator. This reflexive exercise enables you to identify any potential **biases and values** that you bring to your role by virtue of your positionality. We ask that you share your reflexion with the UE team (euciembly@essex.ac.uk) to allow that team to conduct a more holistic assessment (without identifying individuals) of the facilitation team's positionality and how this may have influenced the conduct and evaluation of the pilot citizens' assemblies. Individual identifying features will not be included in this aggregate analysis, with the intention being to present a more general narrative on the positionality of the facilitation team as a whole. Further, more targeted, positionality exercises for facilitators and other role-holders will be conducted as part of each individual pilot. The below sets out the questions that you will be asked to address (see the template in Section 3).

- **Motivation for Engaging in Facilitation**

What was your motivation for taking on the role of a facilitator in the EU-CIEMBLY pilot citizens' assemblies? Did your positionality have an influence on your decision to take on this facilitation role?

How do you think your attributes and those of the pilots' facilitation team relate to the design and conduct of the pilot citizens' assemblies?

What values and qualities do you bring to the role of facilitator and has your positionality had an influence on these?

- **Designing and Managing the Facilitation Process**

How does your positionality impact what you can observe as a facilitator?

How might your positionality influence your ability to foster a welcoming environment in which all participants feel welcome and included?

How might your positionality affect your understanding, explanation, and management of pilot assembly processes such as timekeeping and decision-making?

- **Ensuring Intersectional Good Deliberation**

Might you have views similar to (an insider) and different from (an outsider) the participants in the pilots?

How might your positionality impact on your knowledge and views about the topic of the pilot assemblies?

How might your positionality influence your ability to remain neutral and impartial?

How might your positionality influence your ability to ensure that all voices are heard in the creation of a respectful deliberative space?

- **Reciprocity and Capacity Building**

How might your positionality impact how you relate to the participants and other facilitators in the pilot citizens' assemblies? Think for example about how you might chose to (or not to) present yourself and your identity to the participants.

In what ways does your positionality influence your sense of responsibility and obligations to the interests, values, and priorities of the pilots' participants?

In what ways might your positionality influence your 'transformative' role in providing training, conveying knowledge, and fostering skills among the pilots' participants?

References

Cooper, C. et al., A Positionality Tool to Support Ethical Research and Inclusion in the Participatory Sciences 9(1): 28 *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* (2024) 1 <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.684>

JASS. (n.d.). Power Flower: Our Intersecting Identities. <https://wise-toolkit.org/en/toolkit>

Western Research, Equitable Partnership in Research Module – Positionality Worksheet

3. Template

STEP 1: Reflection on Social Groups, Intersectionality, Lived Experience, and Beliefs

Please note: If you have already completed a positionality review as a member of the wider project team, you can move directly to Step 2 below (reflexion). You may, however, find it useful to conduct the reflection exercise (Step 1) again, so that you have a renewed awareness of your positionality in relation to dominant and marginalised social groups.

1.1 Complete the power flower

Figure 1. Blank Power Flower

1.2 Consider the following reflection points in your own time:

- How many of your personal characteristics are different from the privileged characteristics in each social group?
- Has your positionality in relation to privilege/marginalisation changed over time for any social groups?
- What does your overall positionality say about your own power or your potential for exercising power over others?
- How would you position your lived experiences in relation to the concepts of privilege and marginalisation? (Think e.g. about your education, family life, housing situation, career stage etc).
- How might your lived experiences affect your ability to empathise with others with different lived experiences and understand issues relevant to diverse lived experiences?

1.3. If you wish, you can share your completed Power Flower and self-reflection with the UE team by sending these to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

STEP 2. Reflexion on Implications for your role as a facilitator for the EU-CIEMBLY Project's Pilot Citizens' Assemblies

2.1 Complete the following reflexive exercise in your own time.

2.1.1 Motivation for Engaging in Facilitation

- What was your motivation for taking on the role of a facilitator in the EU-CIEMBLY pilot citizens' assemblies? Did your positionality have an influence on your decision to take on this facilitation role?
- How do you think your attributes and those of the pilots' facilitation team relate to the design and conduct of the pilot citizens' assemblies?

- What values and qualities do you bring to the role of facilitator and has your positionality had an influence on these?

2.1.2 Designing and Managing the Facilitation Process

- How does your positionality impact what you can observe as a facilitator?
- How might your positionality influence your ability to foster a welcoming environment in which all participants feel welcome and included?
- How might your positionality affect your understanding, explanation, and management of pilot assembly processes such as timekeeping and decision-making?

2.1.3. Ensuring Intersectional Good Deliberation

- Might you have views similar to (an insider) and different from (an outsider) the participants in the pilots?
- How might your positionality impact on your knowledge and views about the topic of the pilot assemblies?
- How might your positionality influence your ability to remain neutral and impartial?
- How might your positionality influence your ability to ensure that all voices are heard in the creation of a respectful deliberative space?

2.1.4. Reciprocity and Capacity Building

- How might your positionality impact how you relate to the participants and other facilitators in the pilot citizens' assemblies? Think for example about how you might choose to (or not to) present yourself and your identity to the participants.
- In what ways does your positionality influence your sense of responsibility and obligations to the interests, values, and priorities of the pilots' participants?
- In what ways might your positionality influence your 'transformative' role in providing training, conveying knowledge, and fostering skills among the pilots' participants?

2.2. Please send your completed reflexion exercise to the UE team at euciembly@essex.ac.uk to allow that team to conduct a more holistic assessment (without identifying individuals) of the project team’s positionality and how this may have influenced the research questions we have asked, the methods we have chosen to adopt, the interpretations we make, and how we have gone about designing, delivering, and eventually evaluating the pilot citizens’ assemblies. Individual identifying features will not be included in this aggregate analysis. Instead, a more general narrative of the positionality of the project as a whole will be presented.

Appendix 4. Colchester Pilot Context-Based Analysis for Facilitators and Observers

Local Pilot Context-Based Analysis for Facilitators and Observers

Colchester, Essex, United Kingdom

Colchester is a small city located in the East of England in the United Kingdom. Colchester was awarded city status in 2022 as part of Queen Elizabeth II's Platinum Jubilee celebrations. Colchester is located approximately 84 kilometres from London and London Liverpool Street station can be reached by train in approximately one hour from Colchester North station.

Map of Central Colchester, Colchester City Council

I. Demographic Information

A. Colchester

The demographic information below is drawn from the latest [census](#) figures (from 2021), with a focus on those social groups of particular relevance to the EU-CIEMBLY project (age,

race/ethnicity, socio-economic status, and sex/gender) as well as demographics of particular relevance to the top of the pilot citizens' assembly housing (e.g. household size).

In 2021, the population of Colchester was 192,700 (an 11.3% increase on the 2011 census). This is a faster increase than the East of England (8.3%) and England (6.6%).

Percentage population change, Colchester and surrounding areas, 2011 Census to Census 2021

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

The average (median) age of Colchester is 39 years, which is lower than the East of England (41 years) and England (40 years). The number of people aged 50-64 increased by 14%, while the number aged 16-19 fell by 6.1%.

Percentage of usual residents by age group, Colchester

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

160,500 residents stated that they were born in England. This represents 83.3% of the local population.

Percentage of usual residents by country of birth, Colchester

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

Percentage of usual residents by national identity, Colchester

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

44.4% of Colchester residents reported having no religion.

Percentage of usual residents by religion, Colchester

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

17.5% of Colchester households included a couple but no children (down from 19.2% in 2011). The same figure for the East of England was 17.2% and for England as a whole, 16.8% both which represented a decrease).

Percentage of households by household composition, **Colchester**

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

37.5% of residents had never been married or in a civil partnership.

Percentage of usual residents aged 16 years and over by legal partnership status, **Colchester**

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

56.7% of respondents said that they were in current employment (excluding full-time students) down slightly from 57.8% in 2011 (note that the 2021 census took place during the Covid-19 pandemic).

Percentage of usual residents aged 16 years and over by economic activity status, Colchester

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

64.6% of Colchester households own their own home (down from 66.3% in 2011). 21.5% of households rent their home privately, while 13.3% lived in socially rented property.

Percentage of households by housing tenure, **Colchester**

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

6.8% of residents were identified as being disabled and limited a lot.

Age-standardised proportion of usual residents by long-term health condition or illness, **Colchester**

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

87.0% of people in Colchester identified their ethnic group as 'White' (down from 92% in 2011).

Percentage of usual residents by ethnic group, **Colchester**

Source: Office for National Statistics – 2011 Census and Census 2021

It should be noted that students are counted as usually resident at their term-time address even if they were not physically present there on Census Day and so they are captured in the above census dated from 2021.

B. University of Essex

The University of Essex also conducts an annual analysis of the demographic make up of the student population. The latest available [report](#) at the time of writing dates from the Academic Year 2023-2024.

1. Undergraduate students

The data shows that 47% of Undergraduate students were White, 19% Black, 12% Asian, 8% Chinese, and 6% of mixed ethnicity. 54% of UK-domiciled Undergraduate students were White, while 40% of non-UK domiciled Undergraduate students were White.

Domicile	Ethnicity	2019-20		2020-21		2021-22		2022-23		2023-24	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
All Domicile	Grand Total	13,595	100%	14,205	100%	13,655	100%	12,810	100%	10,980	100%
	White	6,855	50%	7,130	50%	6,730	49%	6,085	48%	5,170	47%
	Black	2,485	18%	2,710	19%	2,670	20%	2,460	19%	2,095	19%
	Asian	1,470	11%	1,465	10%	1,390	10%	1,420	11%	1,330	12%
	Chinese	1,185	9%	1,135	8%	985	7%	1,085	9%	870	8%
	Mixed	745	6%	815	6%	790	6%	730	6%	620	6%
	Other	455	3%	480	3%	495	4%	525	4%	525	5%
	Unknown	400	3%	470	3%	595	4%	510	4%	375	3%

UK Domicile	Grand Total	9,300	100%	9,845	100%	9,630	100%	8,845	100%	5,425	100%
	White	4,850	52%	5,200	53%	5,165	54%	4,835	55%	2,935	54%
	Black	2,235	24%	2,420	25%	2,370	25%	2,155	24%	1,365	25%
	Asian	1,060	11%	1,020	10%	920	10%	830	9%	515	10%
	Chinese	95	1%	90	1%	75	1%	60	1%	35	1%
	Mixed	615	7%	650	7%	630	7%	570	6%	345	6%
	Other	250	3%	260	3%	235	2%	215	2%	135	3%
	Unknown	200	2%	205	2%	235	2%	175	2%	95	2%
Non-UK Domicile	Grand Total	4,295	100%	4,370	100%	4,035	100%	3,975	100%	5,560	100%
	White	2,005	47%	1,930	44%	1,570	39%	1,250	31%	2,235	40%
	Black	250	6%	290	7%	295	7%	305	8%	730	13%
	Asian	410	10%	450	10%	465	12%	585	15%	810	15%

	Chinese	1090	25%	1050	24%	910	23%	1025	26%	835	15%
	Mixed	130	3%	165	4%	160	4%	155	4%	270	5%
	Other	210	5%	220	5%	260	6%	305	8%	390	7%
	Unknown	200	5%	270	6%	370	9%	340	9%	285	5%
% Gap (UK - Non-UK)	White		5.5%		8.6%		14.7%		23.3%		13.9%
	Black		18.2%		18.0%		17.3%		16.7%		12.1%
	Asian		1.9%		0.1%		-1.9%		-5.3%		-5.1%
	Chinese		-24.4%		-23.1%		-21.8%		-25.1%		-14.4%
	Mixed		3.6%		2.8%		2.5%		2.5%		1.5%
	Other		-2.2%		-2.4%		-4.0%		-5.3%		-4.5%
	Unknown		-2.5%		-4.1%		-6.8%		-6.6%		-3.3%

Registered UG students 2019/2020-2023/2024 by Ethnicity (UK and Non-UK)

2. Postgraduate students

The data at postgraduate level shows that 21% of all postgraduate students were White, 16% were Black, 50% were Asian, 5 % were Chinese and 3% were of mixed ethnicity. For UK-domiciled postgraduate students, 66% were White, while 17% of non-UK domiciled postgraduate students were White.

Domicile	Ethnicity Groups	2019-20		2020-21		2021-22		2022-23		2023-24	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
All Domicile	White	1,059	44	1,249	40	1,194	28	1,130	20	1,077	21
	Black	256	11	315	10	405	9	769	13	831	16
	Asian	337	14	887	28	1987	47	3196	56	2,579	50
	Chinese	406	17	286	9	249	6	239	4	234	5
	Mixed	102	4	115	4	131	3	105	2	136	3
	Other	137	6	149	5	175	4	188	3	213	4
	Unknown	120	5	112	4	123	3	131	2	124	2
	Grand Total	2,417	100	3,113	100	4,264	100	5,758	100	5,194	100

UK Domicile	White	709	68	891	68	847	67	754	70	262	66
	Black	176	17	212	16	199	16	144	13	67	17
	Asian	70	7	76	6	78	6	66	6	24	6
	Chinese	3	0	6	0	14	1	15	1	5	1
	Mixed	47	4	66	5	62	5	47	4	20	5
	Other	17	2	21	2	21	2	22	2	6	2
	Unknown	27	3	34	3	38	3	30	3	12	3
	Total	1,049	100	1,306	100	1,259	100	1,078	100	396	100
Non-UK Domicile	White	352	26	358	20	347	12	378	8	818	17
	Black	80	6	103	6	206	7	625	13	765	16
	Asian	267	19	811	45	1909	64	3130	67	2,555	53
	Chinese	403	29	280	15	235	8	224	5	229	5
	Mixed	55	4	49	3	69	2	58	1	116	2
	Other	120	9	128	7	154	5	166	4	207	4
	Unknown	93	7	78	4	85	3	106	2	118	2
	Total	1,370	100	1,807	100	3,005	100	4,687	100	4,808	100
% Gap (UK - Non-UK)	White	42.0		48.0		55.0		62.0		49.0	
	Black	11.0		10.0		9.0		0.0		1.0	
	Asian	-12.0		-39.0		-58.0		-61.0		-47.0	
	Chinese	-29.0		-15.0		-7.0		-4.0		-4.0	
	Mixed	0.0		2.0		3.0		3.0		3.0	
	Other	-7.0		-5.0		-3.0		-2.0		-2.0	
	Unknown	-4.0		-1.0		0.0		1.0		1.0	

Registered PGT students 2019/2020-2023/2024 by Ethnicity (UK and Non-UK)

At both undergraduate and postgraduate levels, it should be noted that India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Malaysia and China are particularly important markets for student recruitment at Essex. It should also be noted that the majority of postgraduate students were international (i.e. domiciled outside of the UK).

II. Housing Issues in the Local Context

A. Housing in Colchester

Recent [analysis](#) shows that the average monthly rent in Colchester as of December 2025 was £1,208 per month (a 6.5% increase on the previous year) which is slightly lower than the UK average of £1,368. The average cost was £826 for one bedroom, £1,072 for two bedrooms, £1,311 for three bedrooms, and £1,819 for four bedrooms. For flats and maisonettes, the average rent was £965, for terraced houses it was £1,239, for semi-detached houses £1,278 and for detached houses the average was £1,582.

Annual change in rents in Colchester

Private rental price annual inflation, Colchester, January 2016 to December 2025

Source: Price Index of Private Rents from the Office for National Statistics

The average price for a home is now £301,000 (as of November 2025, a 1% increase on the previous year). The average paid by first time buyers was £253,000).

Annual change in house prices in Colchester

House price annual inflation, Colchester, January 2005 to November 2025

Source: UK House Price Index from Office for National Statistics and HM Land Registry

The Greater Essex Areas [Profile](#) from 2025 (conducted by Essex County Council). In 2023, the median gross weekly earnings in Colchester were £549, compared to £566 for England. In 2023, the median Colchester house price was £325,000 and the median annual gross income was £36,125, giving an affordability ratio of 9, compared to 8.3 for England, meaning that houses in Colchester are less affordable compared to England.

Since 2014 the housing affordability ratio in Colchester has increased by 33.9%, faster than England (over the same period England's ratio increased by 16.5%).

Housing affordability ratio

Higher values indicate lower affordability

Greater Essex Area Profile Colchester 2025

B. The Role of the Central Government

Within the central UK Government, housing is the responsibility of the Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government which is also responsible for housing within England (housing is a devolved matter in Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland).

1. The Renters' Rights Act 2025

The most significant recent Central Government intervention on housing is the [Renters' Right Act 2025](#). The aim of the Act is to improve security, standards, and transparency for tenants, changing landlord responsibilities and strengthening the enforcement powers of local authorities.

The most important change introduced by the Act is the end of 'Section 21 "No Fault" Evictions', meaning that landlords will no longer (from 1 May 2026) be able to evict tenants without a valid legal reason. Before this change, most tenancies were of a short and fixed duration (usually 12 months), meaning that tenants could easily be evicted with two months' notice i.e. in month 10

of their tenancy, without the landlord needing to give any reason. All tenancies have now become 'periodic' or 'rolling' tenancies, giving tenants greater flexibility (to leave their tenancy with two months' notice) and greater security (they can no longer be evicted without a good reason).

The Act provides controls on rent increases, in that rents can only be increased once per year with two month's notice, but tenants can also challenge any increases at a tribunal. Rental bidding will be banned. Landlords and letting agents will not be permitted to do anything that would make it less likely for a person to rent a property because they have children or receive benefits.

Landlords will no longer be able to outright refuse to allow tenants to have a pet at the property. Landlords must provide a valid reason to refuse permission to allow a pet.

The Act provides for a new private rented sector ombudsman, with the aim of supporting faster and cheaper resolution of disputes between landlords and tenants. This, along with other aspects of the Act will be implemented [over time](#), including the new decent homes requirement for the private sector. It will also take longer for the no fault eviction clause to become applicable to the social housing sector. Social housing are homes where the rent is linked to income (around 50% of the market rate of rent), in order that they remain affordable and secure. Social housing can be provided either by a housing association (not for profit organisation that manages social housing) or the local authority. The terms 'council housing' and 'social housing' are often used [interchangeably](#). There are currently 1.3 million households on a waiting list for social housing and supply is not keeping up with demand. A further exacerbating factor is the 'right to buy' social housing. This right initially derived from the Thatcher governments of the 1980s and granted social housing residents the right to buy their homes at a discounted rate. The consequence was a decrease in the supply of social housing. Certain local authorities, such as Manchester, have recently paused the right to buy as a consequence.

2. Government Agencies

The [Planning Inspectorate](#) is an executive agency within the Housing Ministry. It deals with planning appeals from planning decisions made by local authorities, planning applications for

national infrastructure (e.g. power generating stations), examines local plans, and other planning-related and specialist casework in England.

The [Building Safety Regulator](#) (an executive non-departmental public body sponsored by the Housing Ministry and established following the Grenfell Tower tragedy) regulates high risk buildings and aims to raise safety standards for England's buildings.

[Homes England](#) is the Government's housing and regeneration agency, which has the objective of accelerating the pace of housing building across the country. The agency aims to increase supply of housing, including decent and affordable housing by working with partners and local leaders.

The [Housing Ombudsman](#) assesses complaints about registered providers of social housing (e.g. housing associations and other landlords). Their services are free, independent, and impartial. Private landlords and tenants can also volunteer to become members of the Housing Ombudsman Scheme.

C. The Role of the Local Authority

There are two levels of local government in Colchester, [Essex County Council](#) and [Colchester City Council](#). It is the City Council that has responsibility for housing and local planning as well as collecting council tax (a tax based on the type of property owned or rented). The County Council has responsibility for roads, which is an important aspect of accessibility to new housing developments.

[Colchester Borough Homes](#) is responsible for the management and maintenance of social housing in Colchester, while the City Council remains the landlord for the purposes of regulation by the Regulator of Social Housing. The standards against which social housing landlords are assessed are (1) safety and quality of homes and landlord services; (2) open communication, fairness and respect between landlords and tenants; (3) safe and well-maintained neighbourhoods; (4) requirements for the fair allocation and letting of homes.

The most recent tenant satisfaction [survey](#) conducted by the City Council of its tenants shows that overall satisfaction is improving (78.1% satisfaction, meaning the Council is now in the top

25% of landlords in England). There is reported good tenant satisfaction with home repairs (72.2% satisfied with the duration of repairs) and maintenance (75.9% satisfied that their home is well-maintained).

The City Council provides guidance on [renting](#) in the private sector as well as [guidance](#) on buying or selling a home and seeking help with [homelessness](#).

The City Council also administers [Housing Benefit](#) for eligible residents. This benefit is available to certain residents (mostly pensioners) on a low income who need support towards paying their rent, but it is not available to those who own their own home. Those who are working are more likely to receive housing benefits as part of their Universal Credit.

D. University of Essex Accommodation

On campus accommodation is provided by the [University of Essex](#) for its students. The cost of accommodation includes energy bills, internet access, contents insurance, security, and well-being support. On the Colchester campus, silver gym membership is also provided at no additional cost. Accommodation is spread across the campus and there are also enhanced (refurbished), premium (bigger bed) and premium+ (bigger bed and more space) options. Prices range from £82.88 per week for a shared twin ensuite room to £277.90 per week for a self-contained apartment.

The University guarantees on-campus accommodation for the duration of their studies for all undergraduate and postgraduate students at the Colchester campus, provided the student applies before the deadline.

The Student's Union also provides a house-finding service called [SU Homes](#), which helps students to find private accommodation.

Colchester Campus Map, University of Essex

E. Housing Issues Arising in the Co-design Process.

As part of the co-design process for the local pilot, we engaged in a listening exercise with Citizens Essex and had discussion with the University of Essex Students' Union, Citizens Essex and members of the local community to determine issues related to housing that were of most importance to the relevant groups (local community and students). We have collated the issues raised in this exercise as follows:

1. Lack of Affordable Housing

Rising costs, 'unaffordable' new builds, and barriers to securing long-term stable housing.

2. Shortage of Social Housing

Insufficient council housing stock and long waiting lists for those in need.

3. Impact of Right to Buy Policies

Net loss of social housing, discounted sales, and consequences for local housing availability.

4. Poor Treatment of Social Housing Tenants

Issues related to landlord behaviour, communication, delays, and tenant rights.

5. Homelessness and Rough Sleeping

Support for street homeless people, emergency shelter needs, and concerns about care for people with complex needs.

6. Families and Children in Temporary Accommodation

Experiences of children housed far from school, frequent moves, and instability.

7. Location of New Housing Developments

Concerns about where new estates are being built—too far from services, jobs, or transport.

8. Infrastructure Failures Around New Developments

Lack of link roads, inadequate transport, insufficient health and education facilities.

9. Underuse of Brownfield and Empty Properties

Vacant central sites, unused buildings, and missed opportunities for redevelopment.

10. Protection of Green Belt and Agricultural Land

Concerns about development on farmland/green belt and proposals to prioritise alternative land uses.

11. Housing Quality and Disrepair Across Tenures

Issues such as cold homes, maintenance failures, damp, and slow repairs from landlords or property managers.

12. Student Housing Affordability

High rents, perceived low value for money, and financial pressure on students.

13. Barriers for International Students

Guarantor requirements, upfront payments, limited routes to complain, and experiences of exploitation.

14. Impacts of Changing Tenancy Rules (e.g., Renters' Rights Act)

Uncertainty, contract issues, potential market shifts, and implications for students and renters generally.

15. Safety and Security in Rented and Student Accommodation

Slow response to safety incidents, unreliable locking systems, and general perceptions of insecurity.

16. Accessibility Challenges for Disabled Residents

Higher costs, lack of suitable accessible accommodation, restrictions on modifications, and inconsistent support.

17. Housing Challenges for Neurodivergent People

Noise sensitivity, unpredictable housemates, difficulty navigating tenancy issues, and emotional regulation challenges.

18. Housing Needs of People Who Cannot Share

Financial penalties for single occupancy, limited solo-living options, and barriers until age-based benefits begin.

19. Student–Community Tensions Related to Housing

Conflicts around noise, bins, council tax, and the mixed impacts of student markets on local neighbourhoods.

20. Income Insecurity, Cost of Living, and Housing Pressure

People working constantly to afford basics, rent increases, transport costs, and the link between low income and housing instability.

Appendix 5. Presentation of Local Context Analysis, Colchester, to Facilitators and Observers, 19 February 2026

A reminder of why we're doing this

- The project has developed four key considerations for incorporating intersectionality into the design and delivery of citizens' assemblies:

A snapshot of Colchester

2021 Census

Age

- Median age: **39** (slightly younger than England average)
- 50–64 age group increased
- 16–19 decreased

Ethnicity

- **87% White** (down from 92% in 2011)
- Increasing diversity

Religion

- **44.4% no religion**

Employment

- 56.7% in employment (pandemic year context)

Disability

- 6.8% disabled and limited a lot

What about the University?

Undergraduate population:

- 47% White
- 19% Black
- 12% Asian
- 8% Chinese
- 6% Mixed ethnicity

Postgraduate population:

- 50% Asian
- Majority international

How about housing?

Housing Tenure (2021 Census)

- 64.6% homeowners
- 21.5% private renters
- 13.3% socially rented

Social Housing:

- National waiting list: 1.3 million households
- Local social housing under pressure
- Right to Buy historically reduced stock

What about the cost?

Rental Costs (Dec 2025):

- Average rent: **£1,208/month**
- 1 bed: £826
- 2 bed: £1,072
- 3 bed: £1,311

Property Prices:

- Average home: ~£301,000
- Affordability ratio: **9** (higher than England average 8.3)

University accommodation

- Guaranteed for full duration of studies and located close to the University campus
- Prices range from £82.88 per week for a shared twin ensuite room to £277.90 per week for a self-contained apartment

Institutional landscape: national picture

Central Government

- Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government
- Renters' Rights Act 2025:
 - End of 'no fault' evictions (from May 2026)
 - Limits on rent increases
 - Rental bidding banned
 - Greater tenant protections and flexibility

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Institutional landscape: the local picture

Local Authority

- Colchester City Council:
 - Housing & planning responsibility
 - Social housing landlord

Local Housing Satisfaction:

- 78.1% overall tenant satisfaction
- Repairs satisfaction ~72%

Our listening exercise

- Affordability and Supply
- Quality and Safety
- Vulnerable Groups
- Planning and Infrastructure
- Student–Community Relations

Affordability and Supply

- Lack of affordable housing
- Shortage of social housing
- Right to Buy impact
- Income insecurity & cost of living

Quality and Safety

- Housing disrepair
- Safety and security
- Accessibility challenges (disabled residents)
- Housing challenges for neurodivergent people

Vulnerable Groups

- Homelessness
- Families in temporary accommodation
- Barriers for international students
- People who cannot share housing

Planning and Infrastructure

- Location of new developments
- Infrastructure failures
- Underuse of brownfield/empty properties
- Protection of green belt

Student–Community Relations

- Student housing affordability
- Student–community tensions

Potential tensions

- Students and local residents
- Green belt protection and housing need
- ‘Overdevelopment’ and ‘Not enough homes’
- Homeowners and renters
- Landlords and tenants
- Social housing tenants and private renters
- UK and international renters
- Disabled residents and inaccessible housing stock
- Perceptions of unfairness around benefits or allocation

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Colchester is a....

- ...Growing city
- ...with a tight housing market
- ...faced with a politically shifting environment
- ...city made up of a local (long-term) community and a (short-term) student community
- ...city with a diverse but unevenly empowered population

Appendix 6. Text of Participant Registration Survey

Participation in the Colchester Citizens' Assembly on Housing

Have your say on housing in Colchester!

We are inviting residents of Colchester and students of the University of Essex to take part in a **Citizens' Assembly**: a group of local people coming together to talk, listen, and discuss possible ways forward about an issue that affects everyday life: **housing in our community**.

The Citizens' Assembly is part of a wider European research project called [EU-CIEMBLY](#), which explores how citizens from different backgrounds can take part in inclusive and meaningful public decision-making.

By taking part, you will help shape ideas that matter to Colchester and to the student body, and contribute to learning about how citizens' voices can better inform public decisions – locally and beyond.

What will you do as part of the Assembly?

You will join a group of students and residents to learn about housing, hear from different perspectives, share experiences, and come up with recommendations that will then be forwarded to those who hold the power to improve things.

Participants are supported by trained facilitators to ensure that everyone has the chance to speak and be heard, and that discussions are respectful and constructive.

No prior knowledge or expertise is needed – just a willingness to listen, reflect, and take part.

To thank you for your time and contribution, participants will receive £50 in Amazon vouchers and a certificate of participation.

What will the Colchester Assembly focus on?

The Colchester Citizens' Assembly will focus on **housing** – including the challenges people face locally and on campus, and ideas for improving housing outcomes in the community. The aim is to develop practical recommendations that reflect peoples' real experiences.

How will it work?

The Assembly will take place over three sessions:

- Tuesday 24th February 2026 (online, on zoom), 5:30pm - 8:30pm
- Saturday 28th February 2026 (in person, at University of Essex Colchester campus, [here](#)), 10:00am - 4:00pm 2026 (Tea, coffee, and lunch will be provided)
- Tuesday 10th March (online, on zoom), 5:30pm - 8:30pm

What happens after you complete this questionnaire?

A member of our project team will be in touch with you with further details about the Assembly and about ways we can best support you in taking part.

Participation in this survey

The following is to inform you about why you are being asked to complete this questionnaire and what happens to the information you provide. You'll be asked to provide your explicit consent below.

Please complete this survey if you are interested in being a participant in the Colchester Citizens' Assembly on Housing - one of the EU-CIEMBLY Citizens' Assemblies. This research is being carried out by the EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly project team. Your input collected via this survey will be used to help plan the assembly and as part of the evaluation for the project.

If you are invited to participate in the assembly, we will ask you to complete **one more survey before** the assembly process begins, and **follow-up surveys after each assembly session**.

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire in full after you provide your consent on this page to participate. This questionnaire should take you about 10 minutes to complete. However, you may withdraw from participating in this project at any time, for any reason.

Please see the Participant Information Sheet for details about the project and your rights as a participant at the following link: [Insert link to Google Drive version of the PI sheet once approved]

What happens to the information you provide?

Providing your consent to participate in this survey means that your responses will only be used for assembly planning, research, and evaluation purposes, to understand your

views relating to the EU-CIEMBLY project activity that you have participated in. If you have any questions or concerns relating to your participation in this survey or would like to withdraw your consent after having completed the survey, please contact euciembly@essex.ac.uk

Statement of Consent

I consent to the following:

- I agree to participate in this survey as part of the [EU-CIEMBLY](#) project.
- I confirm I am 18 years of age or older.
- I agree I have received adequate information about my participation in this survey, the contact details of the researcher(s), and I understand what will happen to the information I provide.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research and my participation in it.
- I understand that my responses to the following survey will be anonymously stored on the QuestionPro survey platform and used for assembly planning, research and evaluation purposes only. After **identifying information is removed** from my responses to this questionnaire, I understand the data and results will be made publicly available.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I can withdraw at any time.
- I understand that if I participate in this survey and I am invited to take part in the assembly, I will be contacted to participate in additional evaluation surveys.

Please indicate whether you understand the information provided above, that you agree with the statements above, and that you are willing to participate in this survey: [Checkbox (Inline)]

Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey.

*Shown if Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey. is NOT selected in 1.1.
[Applies to text below]*

If you would like clarification about any of the information above before starting, or if you have difficulties completing this form, please email euciembly@essex.ac.uk.

*Shown if Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey. is NOT selected in 1.1.
[Applies to text below]*

Agreement to Participate

If you do not agree with any of the statements above, you will not be able to proceed with the survey.

Additional Consent for Future Contact

In addition, please let us know if you opt-in to each kind of future contact: (Tick all that apply)

- Yes, you may contact me about participating in project-related activities such as follow-up interviews.
- Yes, you may keep me up to date on the EU-CIEMBLY project results using the contact details I provide.
- Yes, you may contact me to participate in future projects.

Shown if Yes, I understand, agree, and am willing to participate in this survey. selected in 1.1. [Applies to text below]

Please click Next to continue.

Your contact details

Email: [Textarea]

Phone number: [Textarea]

What is your name?

First name [Text box]

Last name [Text box]

The Colchester Citizens' Assembly on Housing is planned to take place on the following dates:

- Tuesday 24th February 2026 (online, on zoom), 5:30pm - 8:30pm
- Saturday 28th February 2026 (in person, at University of Essex Colchester campus, [here](#)), 10:00am - 4:00pm (Tea, coffee, and lunch will be provided)
- Tuesday 10th March 2026 (online, on zoom), 5:30pm - 8:30pm

Please indicate whether you are available to attend these sessions:

Yes, I am available to attend all three sessions

No, I am not available for at least one of these sessions

Shown if No

Thank you for taking the time to consider taking part. Unfortunately, availability for all three sessions is necessary for this citizen's assembly, as each session builds on the previous one. This means it is not possible to take part if any session cannot be attended.

To help inform how future assemblies are designed and made more accessible, it would be helpful to know what has made it difficult to attend all of the sessions. Sharing this information is entirely optional and will not affect any future opportunities to take part.

What is the main reason you are not able to attend all three sessions? [Tick all that apply]

- Work commitments or caring responsibilities that cannot be changed
- Health or disability-related reasons, including energy levels or access needs
- Difficulty taking part in online sessions due to internet access, equipment, or confidence using digital tools
- Difficulty attending the in-person session due to travel, cost, or accessibility
- Language or communication barriers
- Difficulty committing to the dates or planning this far ahead
- Other reason (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

[Submit]

Shown if Yes

Please click Next to continue.

About you

We are asking these questions to make sure the assembly is as diverse as possible.

What is your gender? [Radio box]

[Helper text: The response options 'Woman' and 'Man' include trans women and men.]

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary or Genderqueer or Agender or Polygender or Gender-fluid
- Other (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

Do you identify, or have ever identified, as trans? [Radio box]

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

What is your age? [Age]

(Please write in the whole number, e.g. 23)

To what extent are you an ethnic or racial minority in your primary country of residence?

[Helper text: “Ethnic or racial minority” refers to a group that is smaller in number in this country. Such groups are often identified by shared background, culture, language, religion, or visible characteristics, and are different from the largest or most socially dominant group. This question asks how strongly you feel you belong to such a group in this country.]

	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all							Very strongly

What is your ethnic or cultural background? (Tick all that apply)

- White
- Roma, Gypsy or Traveller
- Black / African / Afro-Caribbean / Black European
- East or Southeast Asian
- South Central Asian
- West Asian
- Arab / Middle Eastern / North African
- Latin American / Hispanic
- Native American, Indo-American/Indigenous/Abya Yala Native
- Mixed or multiple ethnic backgrounds
- Other ethnic group (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

In which country were you born?

- Full country list ([response list from Eurostat SCL GEO](#))
- Prefer not to say

Which of the descriptions below comes closest to how you feel about your financial situation nowadays?: [Dropdown]

- Living comfortably on present income
- Coping on present income
- Finding it difficult on present income
- Finding it very difficult on present income
- Prefer not to say

What is your highest educational qualification? [Dropdown]

- No educational qualification
- Educational qualification below university degree
- University degree (e.g., Bachelor of Arts or Bachelor of Science)
- Postgraduate degree (e.g., Master's, PhD)
- Prefer not to say
- Other (please specify)

Which of the following best describes your current sexual orientation?

- Straight / Heterosexual
- Gay or lesbian
- Bisexual
- Asexual
- Another sexual orientation (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

For at least the past six months, to what extent have you been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do?

- Severely limited
- Limited but not severely
- Not limited at all
- Prefer not to say

This citizens' assembly is planned to be run in English. Would you need any translation or interpretation support to be able to take part fully?

(The citizens' assembly will involve you speaking, listening, and reading learning materials in English)

- No, I can take part in English without translation
- I can take part in English, but some translation support would help
- Yes, I would need translation or interpretation to take part
- Not sure
- Prefer not to say

Shown if Yes. OR some translation support

Which language would you need support in? [Textarea]

People use languages in different ways. Please write any languages you know, and indicate how you can use each one.

Language: [Textarea]

Shown if Text entered

- I can speak this language
- I can write this language
- I can understand spoken language (listening)
I can understand written text (reading)

[Optional 'Add another language' button which repeats the language block]

Two of the citizens' assembly sessions will take place online. Do you have any concerns about your ability to participate online? (Tick all that apply)

- No, I do not have any concerns about taking part online
- I do not have regular access to a suitable device (for example laptop, tablet or smartphone)
- My internet connection or data allowance may not be reliable enough for video calls
- I do not have a quiet or private space I can use for the sessions
- I am not confident using video meeting tools and would need support
- I would need specific accessibility support (for example captioning, sign language interpretation, screen reader, large print or similar)
- Other concern about taking part online (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

In general, how often are you involved in any of the following activities outside of paid work?

	Every day	Several days a week	Once or twice a week	Less often	Never	Not applicable	Prefer not to say
Caring for and/or educating children							
Cooking and/or housework							
Caring for disabled or infirm family members, neighbours, or friends							

Which of the following best describes the area where you live?

- A big city
- The suburbs or outskirts of a big city
- A town or small city
- A country village
- A farm or home in the countryside
- Prefer not to say

Do you consider yourself to belong to any particular religion or belief?

- Yes, Christian
- Yes, Muslim
- Yes, Jewish
- Yes, another religion (please specify)
- No, I do not belong to any religion
- Prefer not to say

Your housing situation

Which of the following best describes your housing situation at the moment?

- Own the home outright (no mortgage or loan)
- Own the home with a mortgage or loan
- Rent from a private landlord or agency
- Rent from a public, municipal or social housing provider
- Member of a housing co-operative
- Live in student or university accommodation
- Live with parents or other relatives and do not pay rent
- Live with friends or other people and do not pay rent
- Live in temporary or emergency accommodation (for example hostel, shelter, hotel or reception centre)
- No fixed place to live / move between places
- Other (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

How easy or difficult is it for your household to pay for your housing costs (rent or mortgage, service charges, property taxes and regular utilities)?

	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	
Very easy								Very difficult

Have you ever experienced any of the following housing issues in your life? (Tick all that apply)

- Not having enough bedrooms / overcrowding
- Significant mould, condensation or damp problems
- Home that cannot be kept warm in winter and/or cool in the summer
- Safety hazards in the home (for example faulty wiring or fire risks)
- Home that is not structurally sound (for example serious defects in walls and/or roof)
- Having to cut back on household essentials, such as food or heating, in order to pay the rent or housing costs

- Being unable to move out or live independently because you cannot afford suitable housing
- Worry that you might be evicted
- Being sent an eviction notice or being evicted
- Experiencing discrimination relating to your housing situation
- Rough sleeping (for example sleeping outside, in a car, or in a place not meant for living)
- Living in temporary or emergency accommodation (for example hostel, shelter, hotel or reception centre)
- Other housing problem (please specify)
- None of the above
- Prefer not to say

Thank you for completing this registration form! A member of our team will be in touch with you shortly regarding the next steps.

Please click on Submit to finish.

Appendix 7. Participants' Information Booklet for the Colchester Pilot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694. This booklet reflects only the authors' view. The Commission is not responsible for its content or any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Booklet for Participants

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Welcome

Welcome to the EU-CIEMBLY Colchester Citizens' Assembly on Housing! We are really pleased that you have chosen to spend some time with us discussing an important issue for our local community.

As a reminder, please read the Participant Information Sheet and return your completed Consent Form to euciembly@essex.ac.uk if you have not already done so. You can also complete your consent form in the Pre-Assembly Survey which is available at: <https://methodsinnovation.questionpro.com/par-diary>

You will find below an agenda for the three sessions of the Citizens' Assembly, some suggestions on how to participate online, as well as a glossary explaining some of the key terms that we may be using throughout the Assembly - we hope you find this useful.

If you have any questions, doubts, or concerns during the assembly session, please alert a project team member in the room/on Zoom or drop a message to euciembly@essex.ac.uk or on WhatsApp at +447593220604

We look forward to engaging with you and we hope you enjoy the session!

The EU-CIEMBLY team

Join the Assembly's Participants WhatsApp group using this QR code:

Colchester Citizens' Assembly
Participants Group
WhatsApp group

Scan this QR code using the WhatsApp
camera to join this group

If you need support or help:

The three sessions of this Citizens' Assembly are designed to be inclusive, respectful, and accessible to everyone taking part.

We are committed to creating a welcoming space where all participants feel comfortable contributing in ways that suit them.

If you need any support before or during the sessions, whether related to accessibility, communication, or if you need directions during the in-person or if something troubles you during the assembly please do not hesitate to contact our team's **Inclusion Supporter**, Alice Leal, by messaging her privately in the Chat or by emailing her at alice.leal@wits.ac.za Alice is the Assembly's "go-to" person for anyone feeling like they need extra support, help, encouragement, or needing to express a complaint during the assembly sessions.

We have also set up a dedicated **Inclusion Support** team who will be monitoring an inbox where you can email with any complaints regarding the process. The team consists of Ileana Steccolini, Joana Ricarte, and Fernando Vannier Borges, and is accessible at fernando.borges@ij.uc.pt

Agenda for the Citizens' Assembly Sessions

Day 1: 24 February 17:30-19:30 (online, via Zoom)

- 17:30-17:50: Welcome: the whys, hows, and whats
- 17:50-18:30: An introduction to intersectionality and positionality (icebreaker)
- 18:30-18:40: Break
- 18:40-19:15: Engaging with the topic of housing
- 19:15-19:30: Developing the ground rules for the remaining sessions

Day 2: 28 February 10:00-16:00 (in-person, University of Essex Colchester Campus, North Teaching Centre, Floor 3)

- 10:00-10:20: Welcome & Coffee
- 10:30-11:30: Deliberation in subgroups
- 11:30-12:30: Testimonies from experts and lived experience
- 12:30-13:30: Lunch
- 13:00-13:20: Q&A based on testimonies
- 13:20-14:15: Deliberation in subgroups
- 14:15-14:45: Break
- 14:45-15:50: Building recommendations in subgroups
- 15:50-16:00: Closing

Day 3: 10 March 17:30-19:30 (online, via Zoom)

- Finalising recommendations (the agenda is left open at this stage so we can build on what we have learned as a group on days 1 and 2)

Suggestions for Online Participation

- Try to be on time for all sessions (we know that life can get in the way).
- Dress however you feel comfortable.
- Try to keep your camera on if you can. We want to get to know each other and have an open conversation, especially in small group discussions. Try to use a photo instead of a blank screen if your camera isn't working.
- Feel free to turn your camera off if you need a break, whether to grab a cup of tea, eat your dinner, feed your pet, or put the kids to bed! Just let us know you are still here via chat or thumbs up reaction.
- Please keep your microphone muted unless speaking so we all avoid talking over each other.
- Raise your hand if you would like to say something, unless the conversation is already in full flow, then feel free to interact as you normally would, being mindful of allowing others a chance to speak.
- You are inviting us into your homes, so please find a space that you are comfortable in. Be sure there is nothing inappropriate or that you would not like to be visible behind you (feel free to use a blur filter if you prefer).
- Try to give your complete attention to the discussion and activities (again, we know life gets in the way). Feel free to bring your food / coffee/ water to the meeting, we will all be hungry.
- Always be polite and respectful to others. We can disagree, as long as we treat each other with respect.

A Quick Guide to Zoom

We will be using zoom for our online sessions. Here you can find a quick guide to its key functionalities. If you have any trouble with participating during the session just let us know in the Chat.

With these two buttons you can modify your audio and video settings, including turning on and off your microphone and your camera.

You can blur your background, or choose a virtual background via “Adjust background & effects” .

You can access the Zoom Chat by clicking on this button. Once in the Chat, you will be able to type a message to everyone and read messages from the organisers and participants.

You can click on the “React” button to Raise your hand or to send an emoji reacting to something that someone else has said.

You can enable the Captions (shown underneath the speaker) or the Transcript (shown as a rolling text on the side) by clicking on these buttons.

The In-Person Session (28 February)

The in-person session of the Assembly will take place on Saturday 28 February in the North Teaching Centre (NTC) [Building](#) at the University of Essex Colchester campus. We will be using the rooms on Floor 3 of the building, and you will find signs there directing you where to go.

There are no dress requirements, so please dress however you feel comfortable. Toilets (including accessible toilets) are available on Floor 3 and throughout the building.

Lunch and tea/coffee will be provided, so you just need to bring yourself along. We have ordered a selection of food also to cater for gluten free and vegetarian options, but if you have a particular additional dietary requirement or allergy, please let us know at euciembly@essex.ac.uk

Participant Information Sheet

Participation in the pilot citizens' assemblies for the research project EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Dear participant,

The EU-CIEMBLY project is exploring how citizens' assemblies can involve individuals in political decision-making by bringing citizens from all backgrounds together to share experiences and shape policies. The project focuses on designing a citizens' assembly that puts intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation at the forefront of understanding how different aspects of an individual's identity overlap and impact people's ability to participate in public life. Intersectionality is a concept that can describe and be used to address disadvantage and marginalisation caused by the interaction of overlapping sites of marginalisation.

As part of this work, the EU-CIEMBLY team is developing models for the design of an intersectional citizens' assembly and running a series of pilot citizens' assemblies at the local, national, and transnational level. These pilots will take place at the local level in Colchester, the national level in Cyprus and transnationally across multiple EU countries. You are being invited to participate in the local pilot.

For further information on the project please visit: www.eu-ciembly.eu

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to bring together a range of individuals to take part in a pilot citizens' assembly on the topic of housing. There are two main aims of the pilot citizens' assembly. The first is to develop recommendations on the topic of housing that will be given to power holders who make decisions related to housing at the local, national, and/or transnational level. The second aim is to understand your experience of taking part in the pilot citizens assembly and how the design of the pilot has impacted your experience.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You have been invited to participate as a member of the public to take part in the pilot citizens' assembly and share your opinions on the topic of housing throughout the

sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly. Throughout the process, you will also be asked to share your experience of the pilot citizens' assembly itself.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not you wish to take part in this research study. If you decide to take part, you will be asked to provide us with your written consent. You are free to withdraw from this project at any time. However, once any of the sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly have taken place, it may not be possible to remove individual data. If you wish to withdraw from the study, please contact the researchers, whose details can be found below.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part, you will be invited to attend a pilot citizens' assembly focused on the topic of housing. The pilot will take place across three sessions and the expectation is that participants will attend all three of these sessions. Two of the sessions will be held online and one will be in-person. If required, you will be offered support to attend the sessions (online and/or in-person) and this can be specified on the registration survey or by contacting a member of the research team listed below. The sessions will be interactive and you will be invited to take part in a range of different activities such as group discussions, reflective activities, and listening to experts and testimonies from those deeply affected by issues related to housing. In each of the sessions there will be notetakers who will take detailed notes of group discussions and observers who will observe the pilots and make notes on their own reflections. The sessions will also be recorded and photographs will be taken. Throughout the pilot citizens' assemblies and following the final session, you will be asked to complete an evaluation survey. Additionally, you may be asked to take part in an interview.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Taking part in the pilot citizens' assembly will take up some of your time, but we have provided the dates of the pilot sessions in advance and will offer you a thank you gift in the form of a voucher to thank you for your time. There are no known risks to taking part in the pilot citizens' assembly.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The likely benefits of being involved are twofold. You will be able to contribute to the development of recommendations focused on the topic of housing at the local level. By participating in the pilot citizens' assembly, you will also help to inform the findings of this research project on the development of an intersectional citizens' assembly which aims to improve inclusivity, equality, and good deliberation across the practice of citizens' assemblies.

Will my information be kept confidential?

All information collected will be securely treated and saved by the project team on QuestionPro or an alternative secure survey platform. The data collected through surveys will be pseudonymised, although your socio-demographic data will be linked to the responses given in the evaluation surveys. If you choose to take part in any interviews, you can choose whether or not your data will be pseudonymised. Data collected via interviews or audio/video recordings will be stored in a password protected folder in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan. For datasets that may include personal data, access will only be allowed to the project management team and Work Package members directly involved in data collection, processing, and cleaning and on a secure password protected platform. Once any identifying data has been removed through anonymisation or pseudonymisation, the data may be added to a shared project workspace on Google Drive, accessible only to the project's members.

You can specify your preferences for how your data will be used on the consent form. We intend to retain the research data generated for at least 10 years following the end of the project. In addition, if you agree in your consent form your information will be deposited as part of the EU-CIEMBLY project to an open access research repository to be determined by the project co-ordinator.

What is the legal basis for using the data and who is the Data Controller?

The legal basis for processing the data collected from this project is informed consent. The Data Controller for this project is the University of Essex and the contact is the University Information Assurance Manager (dpo@essex.ac.uk).

What should I do if I want to take part?

If you would like to take part in this research, please complete the consent form and send it to the University of Essex EU-CIEMBLY project team euciembly@essex.ac.uk.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The output of the pilot citizens' assembly will be a set of recommendations that will be shared with power holders who make decisions related to housing at the local, national and/or transnational level. The data collected on your experience of the pilot citizens' assembly will be used to inform and shape the findings of the EU-CIEMBLY project through a range of outputs including but not limited to reports, research publications, presentations, social media posts, blogs and an oral history exhibition. All outputs from the EU-CIEMBLY project will be available to the public.

Who is funding the research?

This project is being funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed and received approval by the Ethics Sub-Committee at the University of Essex.

Concerns and complaints

If you have any concerns about any aspect of the study or you have a complaint, in the first instance please contact the principal investigator on the project, Dr. Anastasia Karatzia at a.karatzia@essex.ac.uk and the project's Data Management and Protection Officer Fernando Borges at fernando.borges@ij.uc.pt. If you are still concerned, you think your complaint has not been addressed to your satisfaction or you feel that you cannot approach the above persons, please contact the departmental Director of Research in the department responsible for this project, Dr. Anil Yilmaz Vastardis ayilma@essex.ac.uk. If you are still not satisfied, please contact the University of Essex REO Research Integrity Manager, (reo-integrity@essex.ac.uk). Please include the ERAMs reference which can be found at the footer of this page so that the study can be

identified, details of the name or description of the study, the researcher(s) involved, and the details of the complaint you wish to make.

Research Team Members

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Sarah Noles, Institute for Methods Innovation, sarah@methodsinnovation.org

Participant Consent Form

Participation in the pilot citizens' assemblies for the research project EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Dear participant,

On behalf of the EU-CIEMBLY project team, we would like to thank you for your willingness to participate in the pilot citizens' assembly. If you agree to participate in this research project, you will be invited to take part in a pilot citizens' assembly on the topic of housing which will consist of three sessions, and to complete evaluation activities based on your experience of the pilot citizens' assembly.

Your participation in the pilot citizens' assembly will be recorded by note takers and observers who will observe the sessions and make notes based on their own reflections. Online sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly will also be recorded using Zoom. You will also be asked to complete evaluation surveys about your experience participating in the pilot citizens' assembly and may be asked to take part in an interview, both of which are entirely voluntary. All data collected will be stored in secure systems, guaranteeing the privacy of any data you share with us. The data will then be analysed by the project team for the purposes of the study.

Further details about how your information will be used can be found in the Participant Information Sheet along with details about the study and your rights as a participant.

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

We remain at your disposal should you have any questions regarding this form.

Kind regards,

The University of Essex EU-CIEMBLY project team

Statement of Consent	Please initial each box
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided in the Participant Information Sheet for the above study. I have had an opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had any questions satisfactorily answered. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time. I understand that, once the sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly have taken place, whether fully or in part, it may not be possible to remove my individual data due to the nature of the sessions. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that all data collected will be securely treated and saved by the project team, as per my wishes in this consent form. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree for the sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly to be audio and video recorded. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I give permission for the data to be stored in the form of audio/video recordings, survey data bases, written exercises completed in the sessions and in notes taken by note takers and observers during the pilot citizens' assembly. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree for photographs (or screenshots, if online) and videos to be taken during the sessions of the pilot citizens' assembly for publicity and research purposes. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree to take part in an interview about the pilot citizens' assembly and for the interview to be audio and video recorded. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that any data or quotations from the interview or audio/video recordings of the session will be pseudonymised before being used in subsequent outputs such as project reports, academic publications, oral history exhibition or social media. 	OR I would prefer that my data is not pseudonymised in outputs.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that data collected through surveys that are used in outputs such as project reports, academic publications, presentations will be pseudonymised. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that the data collected will be used as part of all research and publications of the EU-CIEMBLY project. This will include reports to the European Union, research publications and other outputs which may include social media posts, blogs and an oral history exhibition. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that the data collected about me may be used to support other research in the future and may be shared, according to my wishes as indicated above, with other researchers. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I give permission for the data I provide to be deposited, according to my wishes as indicated above, in a data repository as part of the wider EU-CIEMBLY project so that they will be made available for future research and learning activities by other individuals. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree to participate in the above study. 	

Participant Name

Date

Participant Signature

Researcher Name

Date

Researcher Signature

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

Glossary

The glossary below contains a number of terms relating both to the assembly itself, as well as to the topic of housing, which we will be discussing. You can return to it at any point during the three sessions.

<h1>Acceptance</h1>		
Attitude of respecting others and their values, even if they belong to a minority or vulnerable group.		
PLAIN LANGUAGE	Respectful attitude towards others	
	Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee on the Proposal for a Decision of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the European Year of Intercultural Dialogue (2008)	
	Inclusion, Intolerance, Minority, Social groups, Tolerance	

<h2>Affordable Housing</h2>	
<p>There is no agreed definition, but affordable housing has usually been defined as housing that is judged to be affordable to a particular householder or group by analysing the cost of housing, levels of income, and other factors and so will usually be below the normal 'market rate'.</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAG E</p>	<p>Homes that are affordable to everyone in a given area</p>
	<p>https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-7747/CBP-7747.pdf</p> <p>https://urbanistarchitecture.co.uk/what-is-affordable-housing-and-why-is-it-so-important-to-london/</p>
	<p>Social Housing (the two terms are often used interchangeably, but they do not have the same meaning)</p>

<h2>Assured Periodic Tenancy</h2>		
<p>A tenancy of indefinite duration, usually on a monthly basis that can be ended by giving the required notice. All tenancies in England will become period tenancies after 1 May 2026 as part of the reforms introduced by the Renters' Rights Act 2025.</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>A tenancy with no specified end date</p>	
	<p>https://www.gov.uk/guidance/renting-out-your-property-guidance-for-landlords-and-letting-agents/ending-a-tenancy</p>	
	<p>Assured Shorthold Tenancy</p>	

<h2>Assured Shorthold Tenancy</h2>		
<p>A tenancy of a fixed duration (often 12 months, though could become a periodic rolling tenancy if not explicitly renewed for a new fixed term). Fixed duration tenancies are no longer permitted from 1 May 2026 as part of the reforms introduced by the Renters' Rights Act 2025. All Assured Shorthold Tenancies will be converted into Assured Periodic Tenancies on that date.</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>A tenancy with a specified end date</p>	
	<p>https://england.shelter.org.uk/housing_advice/private_renting/assured_shorthold_tenancies_with_private_landlords</p>	
	<p>Assured Periodic Tenancy</p>	

<h1>Bias</h1>		
<p>Subjective distortion which prevents one from an objective and impartial decision, deferring to a pre-existing prejudice or judgement and stopping one from correct assessment.</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Supporting or opposing someone or something in an unfair way because personal opinions influence a fair judgment</p>	
	<p>APA Dictionary of Psychology</p>	
	<p>Stereotype Bias, Algorithm Bias; Communication Bias</p>	

<h2>Conciliation</h2>	
<p>The act or process of reconciling the positions of individuals or groups whose interests and goals are in opposition or incompatible. It can be used in deliberative processes - once agreement is reached, the deliberative process can continue to the next phase.</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Reaching an agreement by reconciling different or opposite positions</p>
	<p>https://dictionary.apa.org/conciliation</p>
	<p>Mediation, Facilitators</p>

<h1>Consensus</h1>	
<p>Method of decision-making according to which a proposal will only be adopted if all persons are not in disagreement. Consensus decisions or recommendations are built through dialogue, compromise, and mutual understanding and not through formal voting.</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Method of decision-making according to which a proposal will only be adopted if all persons agree</p>
	<p>Rules of Procedure and Code of Conduct for members of the European Economic and Social Committee Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the deliberative wave Article 15(4) of the TEU - https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2bf140bf-a3f8-4ab2-b506-fd71826e6da6.0023.02/DOC_1&format=PDF</p>
	<p>Unanimity</p>

<h2>Constructive Abstention</h2>	
<p>Form of vote that allows a participant to abstain while formally stating their reservations, committing to respect of the final decision and refraining from actions that could undermine it.</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>It occurs when a participant abstains but respects the group's decision</p>
	<p>Article 31(1) The Treaty on European Union Article 238(4) of the TFEU https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2bf140bf-a3f8-4ab2-b506-fd71826e6da6.0023.02/DOC_1&format=PDF</p>
	<p>Abstention</p>

<h2>Deliberative Democracy</h2>	
<p>Process of active engagement and direct deliberation by citizens amongst themselves or with the participation of other stakeholders on a substantive policy or legislative area.</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Process of direct deliberation by citizens on a substantive policy or legislative area</p>
	<p>https://search.coe.int/cm?i=0900001680ac627a</p> <p>Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions OECD</p> <p>https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/CC-DEMOS%20Brief_Me.pdf</p>
	<p>Public Participation; Deliberation, Participatory Democracy</p>

<h2>Effective Participation</h2>		
<p>Adoption of appropriate measures to protect, support and empower citizens and civil society organisations to participate fully and meaningfully and influence policymaking.</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Meaningful engagement and influence in policymaking</p>	
	<p>https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=pi_com:C%282023%298627</p>	
	<p>Public Participation, Symbolic Participation</p>	

<h1>Freehold</h1>		
<p>Houses are usually sold freehold, meaning that the owner owns both the property and the land on which the house sits.</p>		
PLAIN LANGUAGE	<p>Owning a property and the land beneath it</p>	
	<p>https://www.gov.uk/leasehold-property</p>	
	<p>Leasehold</p>	

<h2>Housing Status</h2>		
<p>An individual's or household's living condition, considering the stability and adequacy of their shelter; for example, being homeless, or living in conventional housing that meets basic standards of safety and comfort</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>A person's living situation, such as being homeless or having a stable home</p>	
	<p>"European Parliament resolution of 21 January 2021 on access to decent and affordable housing for all (2019/2187(INI))"</p>	
	<p>Working Status, Age Status, Health Status</p>	

<h1>Inclusive Language</h1>		
<p>The way of expression that represents all human beings, regardless of gender –gender inclusive language–, but also religion, ethnicity, origin and disability</p>		
PLAIN LANGUAGE	<p>Way of expression without discrimination</p>	
	<p>Council of the European Union, Inclusive communication in the GSC, 2018</p> <p>European Parliament. Inclusive communication Guidelines for DG COMM output.</p> <p>ECAS. Gender-inclusive language guidelines. 2023</p>	
	<p>Hate speech, Inclusion</p>	

<h1 style="text-align: center;">Intersectionality</h1>	
<p>The unique experiences of discriminations and privileges that come from being a member of more than one marginalised group</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Unique experiences that come from being a member of more than one marginalised group</p>
	<p>https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1050?language_content_entity=en</p> <p>EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly, 2024</p>
	<p>Multiple Discrimination</p>

<h1>Leasehold</h1>	
<p>Ownership of a property (usually a flat) without owning outright the land on which the property sits, meaning that a rent has to be paid. Recent reforms aim to make changes to how leaseholds work in order to improve the protection of leaseholders</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAG E</p>	<p>Owning a property without owning the ground beneath it</p>
	<p>https://www.gov.uk/leasehold-property</p>
	<p>Freehold</p>

Marginalised Groups

Communities, peoples or groups whose particular situation or characteristics result in reduced access to resources, opportunities, and power and whose needs may be compromised due to discrimination or stigmatisation

<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Groups of people with certain characteristics who suffer discrimination</p>
	<p>https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1175?language_content_entity=en</p> <p>https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015IP0402</p>
	<p>Systemic Discrimination, Structurally Marginalised</p>

<h2 style="text-align: center;">Responsible Communication</h2>	
<p>The exchange of ideas, opinions, or information in a coherent way, while considering the impact that could have on others</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Empathetic and thoughtful exchange of information</p>
	<p>https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-44700-1_5</p>
	<p>Ethical Communication, Empathy</p>

<h1>Right to Buy</h1>		<h1>£</h1>
A scheme that allows most council tenants to purchase their council home at a discounted price		
PLAIN LANGUAG E	A right to buy your house from the council	
	https://www.gov.uk/right-to-buy-buying-your-council-home	
	Social Housing	

<h1>Social Groups</h1>		
<p>Multiple individuals who share common characteristics, interests, or goals and may have a sense of unity and belonging as a collective</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>People who share common interests or goals and feel connected to each other</p>	
	<p>Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union</p>	
	<p>Acceptance, Marginalised groups</p>	

<h1>Social Housing</h1>		
<p>Homes that have their rent linked to local incomes to improve affordability. This is typically based on a formula, whereby social rents are set at around 50% of the market rate.</p>		
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Homes with reduced rent to help with affordability</p>	
	<p>https://england.shelter.org.uk/support_us/campaigns/social_housing/what_is_social_housing</p> <p>https://www.housing.org.uk/about-housing-associations/about-social-housing/</p>	
	<p>Affordable Housing</p>	

Structurally Marginalised

Individuals or communities who are socially excluded from participating in social and political processes due to systemic factors, such as laws or policies that limit their access to resources, opportunities, and power

<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>People or groups excluded from participation due to unfair systems or policies</p>
	<p>https://rm.coe.int/icc-policy-brief-identifying-and-preventing-systemic-discrimination-at/1680a00ef5</p>
	<p>Marginalised Groups, Positive Action</p>

<h2>Systemic discrimination</h2>	
<p>Unfair treatment that is deeply embedded in laws, policies, or social structures, leading to the exclusion of individuals or communities from social and political participation and limiting their access to resources, opportunities, and power, reinforcing inequality over time</p>	
<p>PLAIN LANGUAGE</p>	<p>Unfair treatment rooted in laws, policies, or systems that marginalises certain groups</p>
	<p>https://rm.coe.int/icc-policy-brief-identifying-and-preventing-systemic-discrimination-at/1680a00ef5</p>
	<p>Marginalised Groups, Positive action</p>

<h1>Unanimity</h1>		
<p>Complete agreement among all members casting a vote in order to reach a decision. Constructive abstention does not prevent adoption by unanimity</p>		
PLAIN LANGUAGE	All members that vote are in favour or against	
	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/293000/Handbook%20on%20the%20Ordinary%20legislative%20procedure_January%202025.pdf	
	Voting, Consensus, Constructive Abstention	

Appendix 8. Online Ice-breaking Activity

Online Ice-Breaking Activity Developed for the EU-CIEMBLY Pilots

Colchester Pilot Session 1 Activity 1

Context and Format

- **Duration:** 40 minutes
- **Setting:** Online on Zoom
- **Participants:** about 50
- **Language:** English
- **Facilitation:** 1 main facilitator (Anastasia) plus 1 helping facilitator (Niall) plus the observers and facilitators
- **Tools:** Zoom Whiteboard

1. Objectives of the Activity

The ice-breaking activity serves multiple, interconnected purposes within an online deliberative setting:

- **Build trust and connection** among participants from the very beginning, creating a safe and welcoming environment.
- **Encourage engagement** in a creative and accessible way, helping participants feel comfortable interacting with one another before addressing substantive topics.
- **Explore individual and group positionality** to make visible the diversity of backgrounds, experiences, and intersectional identities within the group.
- **Introduce the basis for reflection on privilege, power, and disempowerment**, highlighting how social positions are unevenly distributed and how they may influence participation and decision-making (further explored during the deliberation phase).
- **Link personal experiences to the topic of housing**
- The activity does not require participants to disclose personal details verbally. Participation is voluntary, and reflection can take place through visual positioning and shared observation.

2. Step-by-Step Description of the Ice-breaking Activity (30 minutes)

2.1 Introduction and Ground Rules (5 minutes)

The facilitator of the activity (Anastasia Karatzia) welcomes participants and briefly explains the objectives of the activity, clarifying that:

- There are no right or wrong answers.
- Participants can choose how much they want to engage.
- Sharing feelings or explanations is optional, however, their inputs and reflections will help shape the process in a way that the participants feel secure and comfortable along the entire participatory process.

She then explains the **whiteboard mechanism**: e.g. for each question, participants will place a marker (dot, sticky note, or name tag) in one of two clearly labelled areas. The board represents positions, not judgments.

2.2 Warm-up Questions (Ice-breaking only – no reflection) (5 minutes)

Purpose: lighten the atmosphere and help participants become familiar with the tool.

Ask **2/3 general and non-sensitive questions**, for example:

- 'If you live/come from a city close to the sea, place your marker on the left side. If not, place it on the right side'.
- 'If you are a dog person, place your marker on the left side. If you are a cat person, place the marker on the right side'.

Place the marker on the left side if you enjoy reading books in your free time, place your marker on the left side. Otherwise, place it on the right side.

I enjoy reading books in my free time	I do NOT enjoy reading books in my free time
---------------------------------------	--

Place your marker/post-it where you recognise yourself. Observation and reflection will follow.

2.3 Core Ice-breaking and Reflection Questions (7/8 questions – approx. 25 minutes total)

The facilitator then moves the group to the second part of the activity, where each question follows the same structure:

1. The questions are read aloud by the facilitator
2. Participants position themselves on the whiteboard
3. Silent observation
4. Shared reflection (voluntary)

Suggested core questions (Housing-focused)

The following 7 **suggested questions** are in line with the exercise design, which displays one slide at a time and asks participants to indicate whether to place the marker on the left or the right.

1. **Housing Security**

'If you feel the current day's young citizens experience instability and uncertainty with regard to housing due to lack of affordable housing options, place your marker on the left, otherwise on the right'.

2. Education and cultural capital

'If you feel confident in understanding housing contracts, rules, and formal procedures, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right'.

3. Economic Resources

'If housing costs significantly limit the place where you choose to live, place your marker on the left, otherwise on the right'.

4. Language and Origin

'If your name, accent, or place of origin has never been an obstacle in the housing market, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right'.

5. Citizenship and Legal Status

'If paperwork or legal requirements have never limited your housing options, place your marker on the left. If they have, place it on the right'.

6. Access to Institutions

'If you feel confident asserting your rights with landlords or housing institutions with regard to your housing conditions, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right'.

7. Housing Conditions

'If you feel the quality of your housing situation has generally met basic standards of safety and comfort, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right'.

Visual Setup – Whiteboard Mock-up (to include in the whiteboard layout)

The suggested layout provides a simple way for the participants to express their point of view and positionality. It does not employ any ranking or hierarchy, and it is anonymous. It allows for visualising the collective picture of the group positionality.

Place the marker on the left side, if you feel the current days' young citizens experience instability and uncertainty regarding to housing due to scant institutional attention, place your marker on the left, otherwise on the right.

"I feel that young citizens experience instability and uncertainty regarding housing due to scant institutional attention"	"I do NOT feel young citizens experience instability and uncertainty regarding housing due to scant institutional attention"
--	--

Place your marker/post-it where you recognise yourself. Observation and reflection will follow.

3. Closing Reflection and Meaning of the Activity (5 minutes)

Facilitator-led debrief:

- Explain that the final outcome of the activity is a **collective visual map** of different positions.
- Emphasise that positions may reflect unequal access to resources, stability, and voice.

The facilitator asks: Based on what emerged, could you write in the chat:

Which voices or experiences risk being less visible, and how can we keep these differences in mind as we deliberate together on housing?

Thank participants and transition to the next step (break).

4. During and post-activity actions by the project team

A member of the project team will be responsible for taking screenshots of the completed whiteboards once each question finishes.

These screenshots will then be printed in big pieces of paper, to be displayed in the second, in-person session of the assembly in an exhibition-style format e.g. saying 'This is us'.

The following are screenshots from the Zoom Whiteboard setup of the Ice-Breaking Activity that we ran at the Colchester Pilot:

<p style="text-align: center; color: red; font-weight: bold;">INSTRUCTIONS</p> <p>We will move through a number of boards.</p> <p>On top of each board, you will see an instruction, which I will read out.</p> <p>Put your cursor on a red marker from the bottom of the whiteboard and drag it to place it where you recognise yourself in one of the two clearly labelled areas of the board.</p> <p>There are no right or wrong answers.</p> <p>You can choose how much and with which of the questions you want to engage.</p> <hr/> <p>If anything in the activity makes participation difficult, please let us know in the chat.</p> <p>You are all following me (Anastasia) by default. If you get lost in the whiteboards, click on "Follow my view" next to my icon and it will bring you back.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">If you come from a city close to the sea, place a marker on the left side. If not, take place it on the right side.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I come from a city close to the sea</td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I do not come from a city close to the sea</td> </tr> </table> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> </div>	I come from a city close to the sea	I do not come from a city close to the sea
I come from a city close to the sea	I do not come from a city close to the sea		

<p>Same as before, I will read out the statement and ask you to move your markers to one of the two areas of the board.</p> <p>I will then ask you to silently observe the distribution of the red markers on the left and the right sides of the board.</p> <p>In the middle and at the end of the activity I will invite you to share your reflections with us either by speaking up or by typing in the chat.</p>	</div>	I feel that, currently, young people experience instability and uncertainty with regard to housing because secure, affordable housing options are limited	I do not feel that, currently, young people experience instability and uncertainty with regard to housing because secure, affordable housing options are limited	
I feel that, currently, young people experience instability and uncertainty with regard to housing because secure, affordable housing options are limited	I do not feel that, currently, young people experience instability and uncertainty with regard to housing because secure, affordable housing options are limited			

<p style="text-align: center;">If paperwork or legal requirements have never limited your housing options, place your marker on the left. If they have, place it on the right.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">Paperwork and legal requirements have never limited my housing choices</td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">Paperwork and legal requirements have limited my housing choices</td> </tr> </table>	Paperwork and legal requirements have never limited my housing choices	Paperwork and legal requirements have limited my housing choices		<p style="text-align: center;">If you feel confident asserting your rights with landlords or housing institutions with regard to your housing conditions, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I feel confident</td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I do not feel confident</td> </tr> </table>	I feel confident	I do not feel confident
Paperwork and legal requirements have never limited my housing choices	Paperwork and legal requirements have limited my housing choices					
I feel confident	I do not feel confident					

<p style="text-align: center;">If you feel the quality of your housing situation has always met basic standards of safety and comfort, place your marker on the left. If not, place it on the right.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I feel that the quality of my housing has always met basic standards of safety and comfort</td> <td style="width: 50%; padding: 5px;">I feel that the quality of my housing has not always met basic standards of safety and comfort</td> </tr> </table>	I feel that the quality of my housing has always met basic standards of safety and comfort	I feel that the quality of my housing has not always met basic standards of safety and comfort	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; background-color: #e6e6fa;"> <p>When you think of your observations of the three boards:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">What do you notice ? What surprises you? How does this observation relate to housing experiences?</p> <p>Share your reflections either by speaking up or by typing in the chat.</p> </div>
I feel that the quality of my housing has always met basic standards of safety and comfort	I feel that the quality of my housing has not always met basic standards of safety and comfort		

Appendix 9. Engaging with the Topic of Housing

ENGAGING WITH THE TOPIC OF HOUSING

Colchester Pilot Session 1 Activity 2

Context and format

During the first, online session of the Colchester Pilot, and after the ice-breaking activity, participants engage with the topic of housing in order to identify and discuss relevant themes, choosing those sub-themes that they care most about and that they think should be discussed in the Assembly.

Organisers share a Zoom Whiteboard with a selection of sub-themes related to housing. The facilitator of the activity (Niall O'Connor) explains how the themes came from, and how they were developed:

1. Explaining the sub-themes and where they came from

“Over the past few months, we have been doing a lot of listening in the community. That listening has taken place in a few different ways:

- First, through working with Citizens Essex we heard directly from people across the local community—people with different housing experiences, different backgrounds, and different needs.
These conversations helped us understand the realities people are facing day-to-day.
- Second, we incorporated listening with students that has taken place across several years as part of a community organising module which had campaigns focused on housing issues, during the listening, students shared their own challenges around affordability, guarantors, safety, accessibility, and the pressures of private renting. These insights highlighted issues that might not show up in broader community conversations.
- Third, we ran co-design workshops with community members, practitioners, and organisers, as well as with current students and members of the University’s Student Union who represent and are close to the student community
In those workshops, people helped us interpret what we were hearing, identify patterns, and ensure we were not missing any major areas of concern.

All of that listening work—community voices, student voices, and co-design input—has been brought together to create the 10 themes you see on your screen.

These themes are not our opinions.

They are reflections of what people told us, in their own words, based on their own lived experiences.

2. Opening up for input from the group

But your input is essential here.

Even though these themes come directly from real listening, you might notice something important that didn't surface earlier, or you may feel that something needs to be phrased differently to reflect your own experience."

The facilitator of the activity asks participants:

- If you see one that feels incomplete, tell us.
- If something meaningful is missing, you can name it.
- If you think an issue is bigger or more complex than the theme suggests, we want to hear that too.

The message to the participants here is: "This Assembly is designed to be shaped by *you*, not predetermined by us. The themes we are presenting today are a starting point, not a limit. Your job now is to help refine them, challenge them where needed, and make sure they represent the realities of the people in this room—and the people who couldn't be here today."

Participants are asked to share with the group if they feel like something significant is missing.

Instructions for participants: On your screen you can see the issues that we have identified, in random order. Take some time to read the list and feel free to add if there is something significant you think is missing. You can either write in the chat or raise your hand to speak up.

Instructions for organisers: Give 2 minutes in silence for people to read and add. The facilitator of the activity gives the floor to anyone who has raised their hand, and another team member (Rebecca Warren) monitors the chat for suggestions (to avoid duplication with existing themes). A third team member (Anastasia Karatzia) makes the additions to the whiteboard in live time.

3. Group votes on their priorities

The final step of the activity is for the participants to vote on their priorities.

Instructions for the participants: On your screen you can see the issues that we have identified, in random order. You will be asked to vote on your top three priorities, meaning the top three issues that you would like to discuss on Saturday. We will review the group's responses after the end of the meeting, and plan for the next session according to those.

- Title of the voting session: What would you like to discuss in the Assembly?
- Votes per person: 3

4. De-brief and next steps

Between the first and the second session of the Assembly, the organising team collects the outcome of the voting process, and uses it to create the small groups for the in-person assembly discussion.

Copy of the Zoom Whiteboard used for this Activity:

Appendix 10. Ground Rules Development

SETTING THE GROUND RULES FOR THE ASSEMBLY

Colchester Pilot Session 1 Activity 3

Context and format

During the first, online session of the Colchester Pilot, and after the ice-breaking activity and the engagement with the topic of housing, organisers and participants will take some time to co-establish the ground rules for working together in the Assembly. The message to the participants will be: “These ground rules aren’t here to restrict you — they’re here to help us create a space where everyone feels able to speak, listen, and be heard.”

1. Sharing Baseline Ground Rules

The facilitator (Rebecca Warren) starts the activity by sharing the ground rules that have already been developed through the listening exercises, the co-design workshops, and the preparation work that the project team completed prior to the Assembly. These reflect what people said they needed in order to feel safe and respected in a shared space.

The organiser will read out the following ground rules, and participants will be given a chance to react to them, add to them, or change them, through the use of the Zoom Whiteboard tool.

1. “Consider your positionality”

This means taking a moment to notice the parts of your life and of the environment and society that you grew up in that make it easier for you to speak, be heard, or feel comfortable — and being mindful of people for whom those things might be harder.

2. “Step in / Step back”

If you’re someone who speaks a lot, try stepping back to make space for those who may feel less confident.

If you’re someone who waits or hesitates, know that this is a space where we’d love you to step in.

We want everyone to have space to contribute in their own way.

3. Be respectful

Respect for each other’s experiences, identities, and stories.

That includes not interrupting, avoiding judgmental language, and disagreeing without making it personal.

4. Be understanding

We're all coming from different places, with different histories and different relationships to housing.

Understanding means assuming good intentions and giving each other the benefit of the doubt.

5. Be kind

Kindness is a way of keeping this process human.

It means being gentle with each other, acknowledging emotions, and remembering that people may be sharing things that are personal, painful, or complicated.

6. Practise active listening

This means really listening to understand, not just waiting for your turn to speak.

Listening is just as important a contribution as talking.

These six ground rules will be used as a starting point, not as the final list. The message to the participants here is: "This Assembly belongs to all of you, and the ground rules need to reflect what *you* need in order to feel safe, valued, and able to take part."

2. Co-shaping the Rules

The organisers then invite participants to help co-shape the rules, via the use of the Zoom Whiteboard tool.

Instructions: On your left hand side, you can see the rules we've just talked about. In the middle, you can see sticky notes - you can grab one, stick it on the whiteboard (anywhere) and write a new suggested rule. On the right hand side you can see red hearts - feel free to drag a heart and put it next to a rule that is particularly close to your heart. The chat is also open if you prefer to participate by writing something there, and of course you can always raise your hand to speak up if you want to. There are no wrong suggestions. If there is something that would help you participate fully, this is the moment to name it.

Once the exercise finishes, the group goes through the additions together, group similar suggestions, and shape them into a final set of ground rules that they all agree on and carry into the next sessions of the Assembly.

Copy of the Zoom Whiteboard used for this Activity:

Shaping the Assembly Ground Rules together

Consider your **positionality**

Step in / Step back : Make space for those who may feel less confident to speak up

Respect each other's experiences, identities, and stories.

Understand : Assume good intentions and give others the benefit of the doubt

Be **kind** to each other

Listen with respect, even when you disagree

Sticky note

Sticky note

Appendix 11. Activities for the In-Person Assembly Session

SMALL GROUP ACTIVITIES FOR THE IN-PERSON ASSEMBLY SESSION

Colchester Pilot Session 2

Context and format

The in-person assembly planned to take place on 28 February 2026 at the University of Essex campus, in Colchester, includes 3 rounds of deliberation in 5 small groups of around 10 people each. Each group is given their own, dedicated room for their small group deliberations.

This Appendix explains the plans for each round of small group deliberation.

Subgroup deliberations round 1 (10:20 - 11:30):

Participants get into small groups for deliberation on particular issues that were identified and prioritised in the previous session: 1 issue per group.

- Small groups are formed in advance to make sure that each group will have a range of people in the group.
- Each group has 1 facilitator and 1 observer.

1/ Facilitators first share an intro to explain the session: we are here to dig into the issue based on participant's personal experience, in order to then (in future sessions) be able to build recommendations

2/ Then they ask each participant to share:

- their name
- an emotion linked to their current housing situation
- what's most important in their opinion about the issue on which they are focusing, based on their own experience/what they have observed/what they have heard of.

Participants can choose how to share: they can either describe the emotion in their own words during the sharing round; put their emotion in a piece of paper in writing or by drawing, or even use song lyrics. Each room has coloured pieces of paper, markers, and large post-its, and facilitators tell participants that they can use whatever they want to express themselves.

Facilitators ask participants if they need to take a few minutes to think of and express their ideas, then start a round of sharing. Participants go 1 by 1. Facilitators write the generic ideas relating to what participants are sharing on the white board, putting together the ones that talk about the same thing. 5 min max / participant

3/ If there's time left, facilitators ask the group to look at the whiteboard and share if something is missing in their opinion.

4/ Facilitators send participants back to plenary for expert talks

The objective of this session is to get participants to talk about themselves and their own experiences with housing in Colchester.

Experts' presentations, Lunch & Expert Q&A

Subgroup deliberations round 2 (13:20 - 14:15) will be a Mapping Activity tailored to the EU-CIEMBLY Colchester pilot.

The Activity aims to help participants identify perspectives that may not have been identified in round 2 / of persons from different backgrounds and positionalities that may not be in the room / of people with different lived experiences than their own:

Here the participants go back to the same sub-group as in the morning (with the same facilitator), working on the same issue.

Facilitators give the following instructions:

In our small group earlier, we got to hear about people's individual lived experiences and the experiences of others they know of in the community. One of the things that a citizens' assembly does is to consider an issue from the perspective of the broader community but it often misses the voices of those who are not always visible in the public domain. We want this assembly to actively consider voices in the community that are being excluded from the decisions on housing.

We are going to engage in an activity where we will try to think outside of our own experience and in addition to what the speakers have told us. The overall question is: 'Let's try to bring into our conversation the way in which this particular problem that we are talking about (i.e. the theme of the small group deliberation) may affect people differently, and what are the roots of that problem.'

To help you do this, we will use a mapping tool:

- *Mapping round (approximately 40 minutes):*

The whiteboard is split into 4 parts. In the middle, there is the story of a fictional person who is a PMIMG. Participants are not told that that person is a PMIMG. Instead, they are told a story about that person and that person's housing situation. The purpose is that the group thinks about the four quadrant questions (see below) regarding the specific issue that their group is focusing on.

The example: [Our person] is an international student who came to study on campus. She is a mature student who has brought her two small kids with her, one is neurodivergent. In parallel to her studies, she has to work part-time to cover her and her family's living expenses. She is renting a house. [see below for potential problems with the house - each relates to the issue that the group is discussing]

EXAMPLE: Facilitators can use the following if a prompt is needed to provoke the conversation:

For lack of affordable housing/social housing:

She originally hoped to live in university accommodation, but there were no suitable family-sized options available. She is now renting a house, but the property has become increasingly unaffordable: the landlord has raised the rent twice in the last year, and the home is in poor condition.

For lack/high cost of student accommodation:

She originally hoped to live in university accommodation, but there were no suitable family-sized options available. As a result, she had to enter the private rental market, where student-appropriate accommodation is scarce and expensive.

Income insecurity and the cost of living:

Her income is unpredictable: her part-time hours fluctuate week to week, and when shifts are cut, her earnings drop immediately. Because she is on a student visa, she is also restricted in how many hours she can legally work, which limits her ability to increase her income when costs rise.

Social & economic barriers to accessing housing / lack of housing support for disabled people & those on Universal Credit

She originally hoped to live in university accommodation, but there were no suitable family-sized options available. She needs housing that is suitable for her neurodivergent child, but her options for suitable housing are extremely limited. The private rental market offers almost no properties with accessible or adaptable features. When she asks landlords whether small adjustments could be made, they refuse.

Accessibility challenges related to housing

She originally hoped to live in university accommodation, but there were no suitable family-sized options available. She needs housing that can be suitable for her neurodivergent child, but her options for suitable housing are extremely limited. The private rental market offers almost no properties with accessible or adaptable features. When she asks landlords whether small adjustments could be made, they refuse. Finding a home that is physically and sensory-accessible has been one of her biggest challenges.

The whiteboard will look like this:

Each participant is asked to fill in **three post-its** for each of the four core quadrants relating to the story of the person in the middle of the whiteboard. The participant then adds their post-its to the respective quadrant on the whiteboard.

The Four Core Quadrants

- **What do they SAY?**
 - How might they try to express their feelings?
- **What do they THINK?**
 - What hopes do they have?
 - What values matter most to them?
- **What do they DO?**
 - What behaviours might they adopt?
 - How might they try to change things?
- **What do they FEEL?**
 - What worries them?
 - What pressures or influences affect them?

Participants are given approx. 20 minutes to complete the above task.

Once everyone has put their post-its, the facilitator opens the floor for 15 minutes to reactions from participants: “Take a few minutes to observe the whiteboard. What do you observe? Who else from the community might be affected in similar or in different ways when it comes to the issue that we are discussing?” It may be that post-its put up by different people are saying the same thing, or reveal the same underlying value. Participants reflect on the post-its.

When participants don't have ideas anymore, facilitators take 5 minutes to finalise: Do you think anything is missing from the discussion that we have had?

The group is asked to go on a break in the plenary room / in the corridor.

The objective of this session is to get participants to empathise with different forms of intersectional marginalisation but are not asked to speak *on behalf of* the marginalised.

During the 30-minute break between round 2 and 3:

This time can be taken by the group for a break if they need it. Participants are directed to the break room / room with the coffee and biscuits. Members of the project team will be with the participants during the break while the facilitators focus on synthesising with the assistance of the observers.

Facilitators (with the help of the observer): For each quadrant, gather and read the post-its and come up with common themes and patterns. Note both the commonalities and the differences in what was said i.e. if someone has posted something very different than the others, do not discard it.

The next step is to go from that individual story and that individual person to the broader problems around the group's issue, that concerns the group / the community. You need to slightly reformulate the sub-issues by taking into consideration the intersectionality lens. Make sure that reformulations are accurate and that the group agrees if there are major changes in the sentences.

An example of a wording can be:

For your synthesis as a facilitator, you can use this wording if it helps you:

'People in Colchester are struggling with _____, which affects _____ most, and creates particular difficulties for _____'.

(ex: 'Not knowing if you can stay in your home' Can be rewritten into: 'Housing insecurity — not knowing if you can stay in your home — affects many people, but creates particular risks for private renters, migrants, and families with children'.)

Subgroup deliberations round 3 (14:45 - 15:50):

Share the findings of your synthesis with the group and confirm consensus on the empathy map
- Do we all agree? Does this reflect your understanding of the exercise?

Here the purpose is to move from reflecting on the sub-issue from an intersectional perspective, to slowly moving to solutions / recommendations. For the issue that the group is discussing, based on the facilitators' summary of the input to the mapping, the group tries to identify a number of different recommendations or solutions, and run them through a round of: "PAINS AND GAINS"

1/ Facilitators brief the group: 'Let's suggest recommendations/solutions to the problem that we have identified so far'

2/ Participants gather in groups of 4 or 5 - facilitator to put groups together, making sure there is diversity in who sits with whom, and make initial recommendations/ suggestions on their sub-topic. They write their initial recommendations on paper. For each recommendation, they fill in the GAIN & PAIN template:

GAINS

What benefits or improvements would this bring for the community?

PAINS

What burdens, barriers, or trade-offs would each of your recommendations face?

Facilitator encourages groups to:

1. Refer back to speakers' testimonies.
2. Note where there may be internal conflicts or a lack of agreement within the group.
 - a. **Tips for the facilitator to help participants get inspired:** Ask questions like: 'If you were the decision maker what would you do about this problem?' 'If you had the power what would you do?' 'What would be a specific solution that would help improve people's lives?'
 - b. If participants struggle to identify solutions, keep in mind a few challenges or solutions you noted down from the speakers' presentations and ask people to think around those. Get them sharing solutions based on these stories.
- 3/ The groups of 4-5 share their recommendations with the rest of their group.
- 4/ Finish with recording solutions / recommendations: all recommendations from participants are stuck to the wall and will be moved to the third day for further discussion and elaboration.

Between Day 2 and Day 3: The facilitators together with the organisers put together the pains and gains that each couple developed in their small groups and identify patterns, common themes, but also recommendations that may be standing out.

They prepare a whiteboard on Zoom with these recommendations that will then be discussed in the small group on Day 3 (Day 3, session 1) before being taken to the plenary for voting (Day 3, session 2)